

Applications of selected tools by Learning Sites, their specific configurations and main outputs to test tipping points and thresholds

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1. GES4SEAS Project Summary

Human activities at sea (e.g., maritime transport, extraction of living and non-living resources, etc.) and in coastal areas (e.g., agriculture, leisure and recreation, etc.) have expanded considerably, leading to an increased level of pressures and subsequent degradation of ocean health and, ultimately, human health. Single and cumulative impacts of these activities are likely to increase, driven by human demands and enhanced by climate change.

Human activities evolve following socio-economic drivers leading to pressures, which often are studied in isolation from each other even though their impacts on marine ecosystems can interact, making the effects cumulative (e.g., synergistic, antagonistic or a combination). Knowledge on these interactions and their cumulative effects in the marine environment has increased in recent years, but huge challenges still remain to be solved. Thus, there is little predictability with which to inform decision-making processes, especially on ecological tipping points, which, if exceeded, could lead to a point of no-return for the system. In this context, an ecosystem-based management (EBM) approach to the management of human activities at sea and on land should ensure that the combined pressure of such activities is kept within levels compatible with the achieving Good Environmental Status (GES) (requirements of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive – MSFD), against a background of climate change. This means that the capacity of marine and coastal ecosystems to respond to human-induced changes is not compromised, enabling the sustainable use of marine goods and services by present and future generations.

Thus, the main objective of GES4SEAS is to inform and guide marine governance in minimizing human pressures and their impacts on marine biodiversity and ecosystem functioning, while maintaining the sustainable delivery of ecosystem services. This will be achieved through developing an innovative and flexible toolbox, tested, validated, demonstrated and upscaled, in the context of adaptive EBM approach. The toolbox will allow competent authorities to assess and predict the effect of multiple stressors (including climate change) and pressures from human activities, at the national, sub-regional, regional and European level. Ultimately, this will ensure they achieve GES, and support different policies at national, European and global levels (e.g. Birds and Habitats Directives (BHD), Biodiversity Strategy 2030, United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDG)).

Stakeholders and the key competent authorities (including national, regional and European levels) are integrated in a Practitioner Advisory Board (PAB) to co-create and validate the toolbox and the EBM

approach. This will result on a real problem-solving approach with iterative and incremental development steps.

GES4SEAS will also rely on existing multi-actor networks to involve and engage with stakeholders. This multi-actor approach will ensure that the research and deliverables are relevant to marine managers all around the world. Lastly, it is important to highlight that the toolbox will be tested and demonstrated at 11 Learning Sites (LSs) covering all European regional seas (and also overseas), and environments. Thus, it is expected that GES4SEAS will achieve Technological and Societal Readiness Levels 6. This will be achieved by the participation of 20 partners, covering the four European regional seas and Canada.

It is expected that GES4SEAS will:

- Operationalize integrative and holistic solutions for EBM, based upon a software toolbox for analyzing, assessing and mapping cumulative pressures, GES and ecosystem services.
- Provide evidence (and training) to key stakeholders of the benefits of using the toolbox that will be developed in GES4SEAS for assessing the environmental status of marine waters and the ecosystem services considering the effects of multiple pressures so opt for using it.
- Ensure the EBM approach and guidelines for the management of Invasive Alien Species (IAS), harmful algal blooms (HABs) and jellyfish, the approach for monitoring top predators are used by end-users.
- Investigate, using models, the best ways to obtain thresholds of GES/non-GES status and tipping points (system breaking points).
- Reach and engage a wider society, and specifically young people and educators, on key messages stemming from this project, so GES4SEAS contributes to societal ocean literacy and responsible behaviours.

2. Deliverable summary and objectives

2.1 Introduction to tipping points and tools to test thresholds

Marine ecosystems are subjected to multiple pressures. The interaction between these pressures (e.g., synergistic, antagonistic, or additively) drives different levels of stress on ecosystems and, hence, varying patterns of response can be observed in diverse ecosystems (Halpern et al., 2015). In most instances, a non-linear depletion of an ecosystem in relation to the intensity of pressures is observed. Such non-linear response often leads to a tipping-point, which involves a threshold of accumulated pressures intensity past which the state of the ecosystem shifts. Past this threshold, the pressures driving the ecosystem deeply change the processes and feedback loops, hence ecological state, within the ecosystem (van Nes et al., 2016). Determining the thresholds of pressures that cause ecosystem state shifts can be complex and, importantly, thresholds can be pressure, ecosystem component, or system specific.

Determining the intensity of pressures that lead to a tipping point in an ecosystem, or specific components of the ecosystem, is often a question of understanding the impact of individual pressure and the cumulation of simultaneous pressures. In many ecosystems, even if there are few pressures that are especially more intense, and tend to drive the ecosystem response (e.g., excess nitrogen in the Baltic Sea), often the cumulation with other pressures (e.g., extensive bottom trawling) mean that the overall impact on the ecosystem and the threshold of pressures that can cause a state shift may vary vastly (Large et al., 2015; Carrier-Belleau et al., 2021). Therefore, it is important to consider how individual pressures interact with each other, and what the cumulative effect on the ecosystem is likely to be (e.g., synergistic, antagonistic, or additively). There are a variety of statistical methods that can incorporate various number of pressures. For example, there are multiple regression-based methods with a “hinge” function (segmented regression) or curve-based methods (Generalized Additive Models) that can very accurately identify where a shift in ecosystem response occurs along a pressure intensity (tipping point) (Andersen et al., 2009; Hemraj et al., 2024). While very useful, such inferences on single pressures may limit our understanding of the ecosystem response, how we avoid tipping points, or how we manage the ecosystem. On the other hand, methods that include multiple pressures in their assessment provide a better understanding of the processes that may be involved in driving the ecosystem to a tipping point and how to manage the ecosystem. Nonetheless, two issues remain: (1) many of these statistical methods can include numerous pressures in their assessment, but only some can truly incorporate interactive effects of pressures (Hemraj et al., 2024). (2) The

inclusion of multiple pressures is dependent on good quality and quantity of data, which in many cases is not available.

The second major factor that is important for understanding thresholds and tipping points is the components of the ecosystem themselves. Ecosystem components are extremely interlinked through food web processes or mutualism- and commensalism-based relationships. Such interlinkage networks can be exceptionally complex, based on non-linear relationships (Novak and Wooton 2008, Gonzalez et al., 2020), and difficult to combine into one assessment. While there are assessment methods that can incorporate multiple ecosystem components (e.g., principal component score-based, or regression tree-based), currently, none is particularly suited to incorporate multiple ecosystem components and the non-linear dynamics between them into an assessment that accounts for feedback mechanisms between each ecosystem component based on the pressures that affect them individually or together. This remains a major gap in the state of research centred around tipping point detection for broader ecosystems rather than few ecosystem components at a time. It also means that a very large and comprehensive dataset is required to fulfil such an assessment. Therefore, assessing tipping points in an ecosystem is currently more often based on one or a few ecosystem components. This is especially the case for ecosystem components that are of interest to fisheries, or are foundation species (e.g., seagrass or biogenic reefs). While such assessments generally focus on the management of a few, but important, ecosystem components, they remain valuable in developing an understanding of the more specific processes that drive shifts in these ecosystem components, and how this can expand over the processes driving the ecosystem as a whole. For instance, assessment of tipping points in a few ecosystem components may be used as an indicator of the overall ecosystem state based on the pressures involved in the assessment (Fu et al., 2019). This is dependent on the availability of enough information on the influence of the ecosystem components included in the assessment in driving other processes in the ecosystem. For example, excess nutrients can shift the health and distribution of seagrass meadows through epiphytes build up and light attenuation, which then can alter fish production through a lack of nursery habitat (see Hemraj et al., 2024).

On a broader spatial perspective, where multiple ecosystems exist, a major consideration remains the level of interaction or dissociation between these ecosystems. For example, in connected ecosystems, the dynamics of spatially interacting and coupled food webs can increase the stability of food web in an ecosystem (McCann et al., 2005; Gross et al., 2020), even if that ecosystem is under more pressure. Under such circumstances, analysing tipping points with disregard to spatial feedback can produce an assessment that does not represent the conditions of the processes driving the ecosystem or specific ecosystem components (Rietkerk et al., 2021). On the other hand, when ecosystems are well

dissociated, it is imperative to assess the ecosystem within its own boundaries and apply methods that are specifically suited for that ecosystem. For example, the combination of pressures, their range of intensities, and the ecosystem impact across that range of intensity may differ between ecosystems. In addition, since the amount and quality of data available from an ecosystem drives the level of assessment possible and specific statistical methods applicable, methods or models need to be properly adjusted so that they can be applied for the assessment of different ecosystems, especially if these are well disconnected.

Albeit of the challenges associated with determining tipping points, the aim of this deliverable is to use multiple ecosystems as case studies to understand the biological mechanisms that determine the response of key ecosystem components to multiple pressures and the thresholds in pressure intensity that are likely to cause, or have already caused, shifts in the ecological state of these ecosystem components or the ecosystem as a whole. Therefore, we focus on the most relevant ecosystem components and pressures throughout our learning sites to assess the mechanisms and thresholds that are associated with tipping points.

A range of mechanistic modelling approaches have been developed to study marine ecosystem dynamics, climate change and cumulative effects on good environmental status. The project was able to apply Ecopath with Ecosim foodweb models, EwE (Christensen and Walters, 2004; Christensen et al 2014), across multiple regional European Seas (North Sea, Baltic Sea, Bay of Biscay and the Western Mediterranean Sea), and sub-regions of these areas (Local Baltic Sea, and the Portuguese Shelf) (Table 4.1). This ability built on the model development within EU project FutureMARES (Coll et al., 2024a) and specifically the spatial implementation of Ecospace through the digital marine laboratories approach. The models were developed to explore the consequences of Climate Change (CC), the implementation of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs), restoration activities for habitat forming species alongside fisheries management for biodiversity, ecosystem function and service provision (Coll et al., 2024b). We demonstrate how these models can be used to investigate cumulative impacts by including offshore wind farms (both fixed and floating) into the marine environment alongside changes in shipping traffic and test scenarios of potential change due to management measures.

2.2 Main objectives of deliverable

1. Identify which components within different systems are prone to disturbance and potential shift in state.

2. Identify combinations of pressures that have led, or are likely to lead, to tipping points in different systems.
3. Formulate conceptual understanding of how cumulative pressures lead to ecosystem change and potentially tipping points in different systems.
4. Identify how tipping point assessments for different ecosystem components and cumulative pressures on ecosystems relate to our assessment of the MSFD descriptors and criteria.

3. Tipping points Empirical Case Studies

3.1 Analysing long-term trends and tipping-points of *Gelidium corneum* macroalga biomass decline across the Basque coast (Bay of Biscay)

Canopy-forming macroalgae are important marine ecosystems components in intertidal and subtidal environments supplying critical ecosystem services in coastal habitats (Duffy et al. 2019). Over the last decades, a growing body of research has shown a consistent decline of these algae tied to climate change as well as to human pressures (Harley et al. 2012, Crowe et al. 2013, Strain et al. 2014, Arriaga et al. 2024, Chust et al. 2024, Wernberg et al. 2024), implying important biogeographical shifts and habitat loss across the North Atlantic, Mediterranean, the Baltic Sea and other regions worldwide (Airoldi and Beck 2007, Hanley et al. 2024).

Canopy-forming macroalgae are not only considered one of the most productive and ecologically valuable ecosystems (Steneck et al. 2002, Smale and Wernberg 2013) but serve as crucial foundation species, creating three-dimensional habitats for associated organisms including meso-grazers, herbivorous fish, and invertebrates (Davenport and Anderson 2007, Bustamante et al. 2017). Further, they enhance the complexity and spatial heterogeneity of rocky substrates, increasing biodiversity and productivity of marine ecosystems (Steneck et al. 2002, Gorman et al. 2020). Hence, efforts on long-term monitoring of canopy-forming macroalgae are vital to the informed management and sustainability of this resource (Borja et al. 2018), if we are to assess how levels of marine biodiversity are maintained or compromised by anthropogenic activities in nearshore coastal ecosystems.

Particularly in the Bay of Biscay's Basque coast, data compilations from monitoring programs and surveys have shown strong climate regime shifts and diverse biodiversity components redistribution over the last four decades in the area (Chust et al. 2022). These large changes in the ocean properties including increased extreme wave events and reduced sun hours have resulted in an observed long-term decline of the canopy-forming macroalga *Gelidium corneum* in the southeastern Bay of Biscay (Borja et al. 2018), while other authors have hypothesised that such observed decrease is more linked to the effects of temperature and irradiance (Muguerza et al. 2017). The magnitude of decline of *G. corneum* and the lack of recovery across the Basque coast rise the question of an existing potential tipping point perhaps driven by the cumulative impact of multiple stressors (Scheffer et al. 2001, Hemraj and Carstensen 2024).

In this case study, we are investigating the *G. corneum* response to several environmental and human stressors across the Basque coast over the last 30 years (1993-2024), including wastewater discharge, macroalgae exploitation and ocean warming. To do so, based upon time series analysis and modelling techniques, we have analysed the potential factors underpinning the consistent decline of *G. corneum* in the area across 30 transects and three sampling depths (5, 10, and 15 m) using long-term monitoring data across the Basque coast. We have analysed the resilience of the *G. corneum* ecosystem to different perturbations, exploring the occurrence of potential tipping points across the historic time series (Scheffer et al. 2001).

3.1.1 Hypothesis

We hypothesize that:

- 1) transects with stronger environmental change over time and higher influence of human activity will show no (or limited) recovery relative to transects with less impact.
- 2) transects with no human pressure will be more resilient and will likely take longer to be affected by environmental change relative to more impacted transects.
- 3) *G. corneum* decline over time will be stronger in samples at surface (5 m) relative to samples at 15 m due to increased wave exposure or flux energy, implying a stronger detaching of the algae from the substratum in the surface.

Together, these objectives and hypotheses provide valuable insights into the dynamics of *G. corneum* ecosystem and their responses to the cumulative impact of multiple stressors in the southeastern Bay of Biscay.

3.1.2 Analyses applied

Monitoring of *Gelidium corneum* in the Basque coast

The Basque coast is in the south-eastern part of the Bay of Biscay (Figure 3.1). This coast is about 150 km length, very steep, dominated by rocky substrata, with vertical cliffs and abrasion platforms, occasionally interrupted by stretches with sandy beaches (Borja and Collins 2004). The coast is also very exposed to the dominant N and NW winds, determining the extent and composition of the communities, living in both the intertidal and the subtidal coastal habitats (Borja et al. 2004). The narrow continental shelf (15-20 km) causes also the swell to reach the coast, with high strength and wave energy.

G. corneum, which extends from North Africa to the southern Bay of Biscay (Borja 1987), has been sampled annually during June since 1993 in the Basque Coast (Borja et al. 2018). The on-going monitoring is carried out within 3 sectors with a varying degree of anthropic pressures across 30 transects (Figure 3.1). Samples of *G. corneum* are taken by divers at 5, 10, and 15 m depths, in 50x50 squares for biomass and cover (Borja et al. 2018). The standing stock biomass is calculated following the method described by Mann (1972) and Niell and Soneira (1976). Cover is recorded following a semiquantitative scale (1-6), based upon the Braun-Blanquet (1932) scale. So far, we have focused on biomass trends, but at a later stage of the research we will look at cover too.

Figure 3.1. Study area, within the eastern part of the Basque coast (Bay of Biscay). Transect sampled (black triangles), together with the sectors determined for *Gelidium corneum* biomass calculation; MO = Donostia-San Sebastián Meteorological Observatory; HC = Higer Cape, A = Donostia-San Sebastián Aquarium; (o) Water Quality Monitoring Network stations for physico-chemical samples. Figure taken from Borja et al. (2018).

Environmental drivers

To study the effect of the environmental drivers on *G. corneum* development, several environmental variables have been used as part of a regular monitoring undertaken by the Basque Water Agency since 1995 (Borja et al. 2016), as well as from other sources including San Sebastian Meteorological Observatory and the Spanish Port Agency. These encompass Sea Surface Temperature (hereafter SST, in °C), sunlight hours (Sun, as proxy of irradiance, in number of hours), significant wave height exceeding 5 m (Hs5m, as a proxy of wave exposure, in number of events), oxygen saturation (O2) (%), ammonia (NH3) (mg/l), nitrate (NO3) (mg/l), phosphate (PO4) (mg/l), silicate (SiO4) (µmol/l), suspended solids (SS in mg/l), and turbidity (NTU) (Table 3.1). In addition, we calculated the wave energy flux (flux model) at the bottom of the seabed at 5 m, 10 m and 15 m water depths based upon

the conservation of energy flux and Snell's law under linear theory (Dean and Dalrymple 1991). Mean values for these set of environmental variables were calculated for the January-June period during the *G. corneum* growing season. More details on the variables used can be found in Borja et al. (2018).

SST, Sun and Hs5m were compiled at regional level i.e., one observation per year for the whole study area, while the other set of variables were gathered at sector level, i.e., three observations per year across the study area (Sector 1, 2, and 3). Flux was calculated at transect level for each depth, that is, 90 observations per year (30 transects and 3 sampling depths) across the study area. The highly resolved flux data in time and space permitted us to add additional analysis on *G. corneum* temporal patterns.

Human activities and pressure drivers

Human pressure drivers encompassed wastewater discharges (“dump”) and exploitation of algae by hand picking (“harvest”) levels (Table 3.1). Dump included aquaculture, industrial and urban wastewater. *G. corneum* was harvested only between 1992 and 1999. Harvest was undertaken during even years in Sector 1 and during odd years in Sectors 2 and 3. Human pressure variables were measured qualitatively for each transect, that is, thirty observations per year, according to the following scale: 0 = no direct pressure; 1 = low pressure; 2 = moderate pressure; 3 = high pressure. We typified harvest levels for each transect considering the most frequent level across the years. In this analysis, we only focused on harvest levels.

Table 3.1. Information about the pressures and environmental variables studied for Gelidium corneum case-study in the Basque coast. MSFD: Marine Strategy Framework Directive.

Ecosystem component	MSFD descriptor (D)	MSFD Criteria	Human activity	Pressure/Stressors indicators
<i>G. corneum</i>	D5 Eutrophication	<p>D5C7 — Secondary:</p> <p>The species composition and relative abundance or depth distribution of macrophyte communities achieve values that indicate there is no adverse effect due to nutrient enrichment including via a decrease in water transparency, as follows:</p> <p>(a) in coastal waters, the values set in accordance with Directive 2000/60/EC;</p> <p>(b) should this criterion be relevant for waters beyond coastal waters, values consistent with those for coastal waters under Directive 2000/60/EC. Member States shall establish those values through regional or subregional cooperation.</p>	Harvesting of the algae and discharge of wastewater in the area	<p>SST, Sun hours, waves higher than 5 m, wave energy, oxygen saturation, ammonia, nitrate, nitrite, phosphate, silicate, suspended solids, turbidity</p> <p>Biomass and cover</p>

The dataset

The dataset included 5850 observations of *G. corneum* from 1993 to 2024. Each row represented an observation for *G. corneum* biomass as well as the environmental and human pressure variables for each sector, transect and depth. The dataset consists of spatially explicit temporal data on one ecosystem component (*G. corneum* biomass), and multiple pressures or drivers limiting the algae

Specific analyses

Here we undertook a twofold analysis. On one hand, we explored how *G. corneum* biomass varies according to different sectors and depths and its link with environmental and human pressures using linear models, and on the other hand, we analyzed nonlinear trends to detect regime shifts or tipping points across the time series using Generalized Additive Models (GAMs)(Wood 2006).

Biomass trends over time across depth, environmental drivers and human pressures

We analysed the trend of *G. corneum* biomass over time using linear models (lm) (Eq. 1) with interactions across sector and depth, which are two categorical variables with 3 levels each (Sector 1, Sector 2, Sector 3 and Depth 5m, Depth 10m, Depth 15m). We log transformed biomass data to satisfy parametric test assumptions

$$\text{lm}(\log(\text{Biomass}+1) \sim \text{Sector} * \text{Year} + \text{Depth} * \text{Year} \text{ (Eq. 1)}$$

Since each of the transects are nested within sectors, we also analysed the data using mixed models with nested data (Eq. 2). Mixed models explicitly model hierarchical data structures by clustering observations into groups (Gelman 2007, Bolker et al. 2009). The key consequence of nesting is the pooling of the interaction variance with the main effect variance of the nested factor (Schielzeth and Nakagawa 2013). The linear mixed model (lmm) in Eq. 2 included sector and depth-specific terms to account for linear trends over time (i.e., interaction of year and sector and year and depth), as well as interaction across year, sector and depth, and accounted for hierarchical structure nesting transects within sectors.

$$\text{lmm}(\log(\text{Biomass}+1) \sim \text{Year} + \text{Sector} + \text{Depth} + \text{Year} : \text{Sector} + \text{Year} : \text{Depth} + \text{Sector} : \text{Depth} + \text{Year} : \text{Sector} : \text{Depth} + (1|\text{Sector}/\text{Transect}) \text{ (Eq. 2)}$$

ANOVA analysis of the model in Eq. 2 was used to select significant factors underlying *G. corneum* biomass change over time.

Further, we also explored the *G. corneum* patterns at “Transect” level. To do so, we build two models, one to analyse biomass changes over time at each transect (Eq. 3) and other (Eq. 4) to analyse if the different harvest intensities across the transects had an effect in the degree of *G. corneum* decreasing

trends over time. The model in Eq. 3 included Transect and Depth specific terms to account for linear trends over time (i.e., interaction of Year and Transect and Year and Depth):

$$\text{lm}(\log(\text{Biomass}+1) \sim \text{Year} + \text{Depth} + \text{Transect} + \text{Transect}:\text{Year} + \text{Depth}:\text{Year} \text{ (Eq. 3)}$$

Similarly, the model in Eq. 4 included Harvest and Depth specific terms to account for linear trends over time (i.e., interaction of Year and Harvest and Year and Depth):

$$\text{lm}(\log(\text{Biomass}+1) \sim \text{Year} + \text{Depth} + \text{Harvest} + \text{Harvest}:\text{Year} + \text{Depth}:\text{Year} \text{ (Eq. 4)}$$

Next, we analysed the correlation between biomass change over time and environmental variables using linear models. Prior to this, we tested for collinearity between explanatory variables by calculating variance inflation factors (VIF) with the CAR package in R (Zuur et al. 2009). We excluded any variable that had a VIF > 3 and then recalculated VIF for the remaining variables. We iterated this process until all variables had a VIF < 3. Consequently, we undertook a two-fold analysis. On one hand, (i) we build a model considering annual means of biomass vs annual means of environmental variables (Eq. 5), and on the other, (ii) we build a model (Eq. 6) between biomass and environmental variables according to the level of harvest (0, 1, 2, 3). The set of variables selected within the models in Eq. 5 and Eq. 6 were used as drivers to explore potential tipping points on the *G. corneum* time series. The model selection was carried out applying the second-order Akaike Information Criterion (AICc); recommended for small sample sizes (Burnham and Anderson 2002). We used the dredge function of ‘MuMIn’ R language to compare all possible combinations of terms and selected the best model based on lowest AICc (Barton 2009).

The model in Eq. 5 included a set of environmental drivers previously selected upon VIF analysis to account for linear relationships in *G. corneum* biomass patterns.

$$\text{lm}(\log(\text{Biomass}+1) \sim \text{SST} + \text{Sun}_h + \text{NTU} + \text{PO4} + \text{SS} + \text{NH3} + \text{O2} + \text{flux_model} \text{ (Eq. 5)}$$

In the same way, the model in Eq. 6 included a set of environmental drivers previously selected upon VIF analysis to account for linear relation in *G. corneum* patterns according to Harvest level, where $i = 0,1,2,3$.

$$\text{lm}(\log(\text{Biomass}+1) \sim \text{SST} + \text{Sun}_h + \text{NTU} + \text{PO4} + \text{SS} + \text{Am} + \text{O2} + \text{flux_model} + \text{Harvest}. \text{ (Eq. 6)}$$

Finally, we build a mixed model (Eq. 7) to analyze the relationship between *G. corneum* biomass and wave energy flux across depth at each transect (ID). In the model, the depth and wave energy flux interact as fixed effect and the transect as random effect. Building upon Eq. 7, we also analyzed if the potential difference in biomass levels according to flux and depth were tied to harvest intensity (Eq. 7). We did not include interaction across Harvest and Depth since there is no Harvest data for each

Depth. A priori, stronger correlations between biomass and wave energy flux should be observed in transects with no exploitation relative to transects influenced by human pressures.

$\text{Imm}(\log(\text{Biomass}+1)) \sim \text{flux_model} * \text{Depth} + \text{Harvest} + (1 | \text{ID})$ (Eq. 7)

*Non-linear trends of *G. corneum* biomass*

We used mixed GAMs (GAMMs) including all observations of *G. corneum* biomass to determine abrupt changes in the time series. Specifically, we modelled biomass trends over time with year as a fixed effect with a smoothing term (Year) and two random effects (Transect and Depth):

$\text{gamm}(\log(\text{Biomass} + 1) \sim \text{s}(\text{Year}), \text{random} = \sim (1 | \text{Depth}) + (1 | \text{ID}))$ (Eq. 8)

Tipping point analysis

Considering the nature of our spatial-temporal dataset with one ecosystem component and many environmental and human drivers, four tipping point methods were explored.

Breakpoint analysis

The breakpoint analysis is based on an estimation and inference of regression models with piecewise linear relationships, also known as segmented regression models, with several breakpoints fixed or to be 'selected' (Muggeo 2003). We used the "segmented" package in R which aims to estimate linear and generalized linear models having one or more segmented relationships in the linear predictor (*G. corneum* biomass change). Estimates of the slopes and breakpoints are provided along with standard errors. We used the breakpoint analysis to determine significant differences across the slopes within the time series of *G. corneum*.

Threshold analysis

This approach fits a GAM (with or without autocorrelation) to a response variable as a function of an environmental driver (e.g., temperature). The first and second derivatives of the GAM are used to detect the presence of a threshold and tipping point. We fit a GAM to a response variable (*G. corneum* biomass) as a function of an environmental driver (SST, Sun h, SS) and the first and second derivatives of the GAM were used to detect the presence of a threshold and a tipping point.

Integrative Resilience Analysis (IRA)

The IRA is a three-step methodological framework which applies the concepts of resilience and folded stability landscapes in an empirical multivariate context through the combination of multivariate analysis, non-additive modelling and a resilience assessment (Vasilakopoulos et al. 2017). IRA quantifies resilience by identifying two or more multiple stable states of a system, affected by one

driver that acts as a system stressor. In the IRA framework, the relationship between the system and its drivers is assessed using GAMs and threshold-GAMs (TGAMs) (Ciannelli et al. 2004) adjusted to account for abrupt changes in the response mechanism.

Stochastic cusp Modelling (SCM)

The cusp is one of seven geometric elements in catastrophe theory and represents a 3D surface combining linear and non-linear responses of a state variable to one control variable (called the asymmetry variable) modulated by a second so-called bifurcation variable. This model describes the dynamics of a state variable (i.e. a variable taken to represent the status of the system, here *G. corneum* biomass) based on two interactive stressors (or drivers, here SST and Sun h) and allows to test which, out of three possible alternative dynamics for the state variable, that is, linear, nonlinear but continuous, or discontinuous (i.e. a regime shift), represents the best description of the system behavior over time (Diks and Wang 2016, Sguotti et al. 2022).

3.1.3 Results and interpretation

***G. corneum* temporal and spatial trends**

Analysis of *G. corneum* observations including three sectors shows a strong decline in biomass over time during 1993-2024, consistent across depths (Figure 3.2).

Figure 3.2. *Gelidium corneum* biomass (log+1) trends using observed data from 1993-2024 across three sampling depths (5 m, 10 m and 15 m). Each point in the plot shows the mean biomass value for each year across all transects.

It appears that at 5 m depth the decrease is stronger relative to 10 m and 15 m. The general gentle decrease of biomass from 1993-2010 is followed by a sharp decline within 2010-2015. Afterwards, the biomass seems to keep stable at minimum levels. The same pattern is confirmed by the linear model (Eq. 1) which shows biomass change over time considering the interactions across Sector and Depth factors (Figure 3.3). Results from the model in Eq.1 revealed that *G. corneum* biomass is decreasing significantly over time in all three sectors, with a significantly higher decrease velocity in Sector 1 relative to Sector 2 and 3. Similarly, *G. corneum* biomass is decreasing significantly over time at all sampling depths, and this decrease appears to be significantly stronger in 5 m relative to 10 m and 15 m (Figure 3.3).

Figure 3.3. *Gelidium corneum* trends over time across depth for each sector during 1993-2024 based on linear models. The linear model (m1) shows biomass change over time considering the interaction between Sector (Sector 1, 2 and 3) and Depth 5 m, 10 m and 15 m). The black line in the plot represents the fitted values of the model with the colour shades showing the 95% confidence interval for each depth.

The ANOVA analysis of the model in Eq.2 (Table 3.2) revealed the “Year” and the “Depth” as significant factors driving temporal patterns of *G. corneum*. However, we found no significant relationship between the “Sector” and *G. corneum* biomass patterns over time, hence we excluded the “Sector” from the subsequent analysis and explored the patterns at “Transect” level.

Table 3.2. ANOVA analysis of the linear mixed model (Eq. 2) to analyse *Gelidium corneum* trends over time across depths and sectors. The model included sector and depth specific terms to account for linear trends over time (i.e. interaction of time and depth and sector). Transects were nested within sectors due to the hierarchical structure of the dataset (Figure 1).

Terms	df	F	p-value
Year	31	42.39	<.0001
Sector	2	1.94	0.1635
Depth	2	9.99	0.0002
Year:Sector	62	1.19	0.1588
Year:Depth	62	2.61	<.0001
Sector:Depth	4	2.52	0.0524
Year:Sector:Depth	124	0.91	0.7525

Potential drivers of *G. corneum* biomass change

Environmental drivers

We looked to the influence of environmental drivers in *G. corneum* biomass patterns. Nitrate and Silicate were excluded from the analysis due to VIF > 3. Hs5m and Nitrite were also excluded, the former was highly correlated with “Flux model”, the latter had very low concentrations in the samples, with levels not considered as limiting for macroalgae. SST increased significantly over time at a rate of 0.29 °C decade⁻¹, while the observed increase in Sun was not significant (Figure 3.4). The strongest changes in the remaining set of variables were observed in SS, with a very steep slope and a significant increase over time (Figure 3.4). On the other hand, pairwise correlations across *G. corneum* biomass and environmental drivers showed strong significant negative trends with SST, and SS, as well as weaker, but still significant negative correlation with Ammonia (Figure 3.5).

Figure 3.4. Time series of the environmental drivers collected during the *Gelidium corneum* sampling. a-b-c) The black line represents the annual means calculated for the January-June period during the *G. corneum* growing season. d-e-f-g-h-i) Boxplots showing the temporal patterns of the variables including the three sectors for each year. The bottom and top of the box are the lower (Q1) and upper (Q3) quartiles, and the band inside the box is the median. The whiskers extend up to 1.5 times the Interquartile range (Q3 - Q1) of the box. In the plots, the blue line in the plot represents the fitted values of the model with the colour shades showing the 95% confidence interval for each depth. The fit is only drawn in significant cases i.e. when the environmental change over time is significant.

Figure 3.5. a-b-c-d-e-h-i) Scatter plots showing the relationship between *Gelidium corneum* biomass and environmental drivers. j-k) Boxplots showing the relationship of *Gelidium corneum* and human pressures drivers. The bottom and top of the box are the lower (Q1) and upper (Q3) quartiles, and the band inside the box is the median. The whiskers extend up to 1.5 times the Interquartile range (Q3 - Q1) of the box. In the plots, the blue line in the plot represents the fitted values of the model with the color shades showing the 95% confidence interval for each depth. The fit is only drawn in significant cases i.e. when the environmental change over time is significant. SST: Sea Surface Temperature; Hs>5m: significant wave height >5m; Sun: hours of sun; PO₄: phosphate, SS: suspended solids; NTU: turbidity; Dump: wastewater discharge.

Wave energy flux showed high variability across 1993-2024 but increased significantly in the three sampling depths (not shown). As expected, stronger wave energy flux was observed at 5 m depth across the transects, relative to 10 m and 15 m depths (Figure 3.6a). Correlations between observed *G. corneum* biomass and wave energy flux showed high variability across transects and depth, and no clear pattern was observed in their slopes (Figure 3.6a). However, predictions from the mixed model

in Eq. 7 including all transects revealed a significant decrease in *G. corneum* biomass with increasing wave energy flux, which was consistent across depths. We found significant differences in the intercepts across each sampling depth, but no significant differences were observed in the slopes (Figure 3.6b, Table 3.3). Therefore, it appears that the waves energy flux clearly determines the *G. corneum* biomass, more wave energy significantly less biomass, but differences in biomass decrease according to depth are not determined by wave energy flux but by some other factors.

Figure 3.6. a) Relationship between *Gelidium corneum* biomass and wave energy flux for each transect and depth during 1993-2024. b) Linear mixed models (see Eq. 7) showing the relationship of *G. corneum* and wave energy flux across all transects at each depth during 1993-2024. The model shows how biomass decreases with increasing flux at each depth (Eq. 7). The black line in the plot represents the fitted values of the model with the colour shades showing the 95% confidence interval for each depth.

Table 3.3. Linear mixed model output (Eq. 7) to analyse *G. corneum* biomass trends as a function of wave energy flux at each sampling depth. The model includes interaction across Depth and flux model as fixed effects and transect (ID) as random effect. The table includes estimated coefficients, p-values for the terms, and other statistics related to the model fit. * = significant relationship < 0.001.

Parametric coefficients	value	Std. error	t-value	p-value
Flux model	-0.463	0.032	-14.394	<.001
Depth10	-1.036	0.315	-3.289	.001
Depth15	-2.075	0.312	-6.649	<.001
Flux model:Depth10	0.003	0.046	0.069	0.944
Flux model:Depth15	-0.105	0.062	-1.702	0.088

Human activities and pressures drivers

Regarding the human pressures, the model in Eq.6 revealed significant differences in biomass change over time according to Harvest level (Table 3.4, Figure 3.7). In addition, biomass decreased over time significantly in all Harvest levels (Table 3.4, Figure 3.7). One interesting point here is that, although harvest intensity is related to biomass decline over time as expected, it looks like harvesting *G. corneum* at low intensity (Harvest level 1), appears to sustain higher levels of biomass relative to no harvesting (Harvest level 0), mirroring a natural perturbation in the system that can enhance the growth of the algae in Basque waters (Figure 3.7).

Figure 3.7. *Gelidium corneum* biomass change over time for each Harvest level and sampling depth (5 m, 10 m, 15 m) during 1993-2024 based on a linear mixed model (Eq.6) with interaction across Harvest, Year, and Depth. 0 = no direct pressure from harvest; 1 = low pressure; 2 = moderate pressure; 3 = high pressure.

Table 3.4. ANOVA analysis of the linear mixed model (Eq. 4) to analyse *Gelidium corneum* trends over time across depths for each harvest intensity (0,1,2,3). The model included Harvest and Depth specific terms to account for linear trends over time (i.e. interaction of time and depth and sector). Transects were nested within sectors due to the hierarchical patterns of the dataset (Figure 3.1).

Terms	df	F	p-value
Year	31	39.7	<.0001
Depth	2	8.18	0.0008
Harvest	3	1.79	0.1759
Year:Harvest	93	1.97	<.0001
Year:Depth	62	1.88	<.0001

We also analysed if the observed differences in biomass levels according to flux and depth were tied to harvest intensity (Eq. 8). The model in Eq. 8 revealed no significant differences in *G. corneum* biomass across transects with or without harvest, considering the three sampling depths and wave energy flow (Table 3.5). Therefore, it looks like the *G. corneum* biomass decreases with increasing wave energy flux in all transects, regardless of the harvest level, contrary to expectations.

Table 3.5. Linear mixed model output (Eq. 7) to analyse *Gelidium corneum* biomass trends as a function of wave energy flux at each sampling depth including the effect different harvest intensities across transects. The model includes interaction across Depth and flux_model and Harvest level as fixed effects and transect (ID) as random effect. The table includes estimated coefficients, p-values for the terms, and other statistics related to the model fit. * = significant relationship < 0.001.

Parametric coefficients	value	Std. error	t-value	p-value
Flux model	-0.463	0.032	-14.394	<.001
Depth10	-1.036	0.315	-3.289	.001
Depth15	-2.075	0.312	-6.649	<.001
Flux model:Depth10	0.003	0.046	0.069	0.944
Flux model:Depth15	-0.105	0.062	-1.702	0.088
Harvest 1	0.410	0.827	0.496	0.624
Harvest 2	-0.211	0.744	-0.284	0.778
Harvest 3	-0.712	0.744	-0.957	0.347

The variable selection of the model considering annual means of biomass vs annual means of environmental variables (Eq. 5) as well the model using all observations (Eq. 6) between biomass change and environmental variables according to Harvest level (0, 1, 2, 3) is shown in Table 3.6. SST, Sun, SS, Am, flux model and Harvest level were the variables included in models; therefore, we explored potential tipping points in the *G. corneum* time series using some of these selected variables.

We excluded ammonia as potential driver as either there is not limitation or increased levels that could affect *G. corneum* patterns.

Table 3.6. Variable selection using the dredge function in R between environmental drivers and *Gelidium corneum* biomass for (i) one model considering annual means of log biomass vs annual means of environmental variables (Eq. 5), and for (ii) a set of models including all observations (Eq. 6) between biomass and environmental variables according to the level of harvest (0,1,2,3). See methods.

Model	Variables selected
Eq. 5	Am, PO ₄ , SST, flux model
Eq.6	Am, Harvest, NTU, SS, SST, Sun_h, flux model

Figure 3.8 shows the outcome of a GAMM using all observations with biomass as fixed effect and transect and depth as random effects. A gradual decrease in biomass is observed from 1993 to 2010 followed by a sharp decline within the 2010-2015, which is quite consistent with the threshold years observed with the IRA tipping point detection method (see section below). From 2015 onwards, it looks like the biomass levels plateau at minimum levels.

Figure 3.8. Outcome of a mixed model GAM showing the temporal trend in *G. Corneum* biomass in 1993-2024. The model includes the biomass as a response variable, “Year” as a fixed effect with a smoothing term “Year” and two random effects i.e., the transect and the depth, which capture the variability of observations within groups (Eq. 9). The dots depict the residuals of the model, the black solid line is the fit of the model and the grey shadow shows the confidence interval of the fit at 95%.

Tipping point analysis

Breakpoint analysis shows a segmented relationship with the linear predictor “biomass”, that occurs at different times across the time series according to depth (Figure 3.9). The Davies tests revealed

significant changes in the slopes within each time-series in all depths. At 5 m depth the breakpoint occurred in 2006, at 10 m in 2009, and at 15 m in 2010 (Figure 3.9). These findings slightly differ with the pattern observed in the GAM and change in the trend occurring at a later stage (2010-2015) across the time-series. However, the breakpoint analysis seems not to capture the trends in the way one would expect, as it joins two potential regimes without correctly detecting the exact moment of the breakpoint. Nevertheless, both analyses (GAMM and breakpoint) revealed a significant change in the *G. corneum* biomass trend, which justify the analysis of the tipping point methods to dig into the underlying factors underpinning the observed changes in the trends.

Figure 3.9. Breakpoint analysis for each depth showing the outcome of generalized linear models with a segmented relationships in the linear predictor (biomass). The lines represent the fitted values of the model, and the colours show different slopes across the time series. The boxplots show the variability of the data for each year across the transect. The bottom and top of the box are the lower (Q1) and upper (Q3) quartiles, and the band inside the box is the median. The whiskers extend up to 1.5 times the Interquartile range (Q3 - Q1) of the box. the 95% confidence interval for each depth.

In Figure 3.10 top panel a decreasing trend in biomass is observed due to SST and SS. This is because the first derivative of the smoother is greater than zero. On the other hand, an increasing trend in biomass is observed with Sun, as the first derivate of the smoother is lower than zero. Since we observed negative and positive values across the three used drivers (Figure 3.10. bottom panels) as reflected by the rate of change of slope in the second derivative, we conclude that there does not appear to be a point in the time series with significant biomass decrease over time due to SST, nor SS and Sun change (Figure 3.10).

Figure 3.10. Threshold analyses for *Gelidium corneum* biomass as a function of a) Seas Surface Temperature (SST), b) Hours of Sun (Sun_h) and c) Suspended Solids (SS). Top panels: solid lines represent the mean smoothing function $s(x)$; shading indicates the 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles from 1000 bootstrap replicates. Mid panels: The first derivative $S^{\wedge}(x)'$ of $s(x)$ indicates regions where a pressure variable causes a negative [$S^{\wedge}(x)', 0$] or positive [$S^{\wedge}(x)', 0$] response to biomass change over time. Bottom panel: the second derivative $S^{\wedge}(x)''$ denotes regions where $S^{\wedge}(x)'$ changes sign and a threshold is crossed [$0, S^{\wedge}(x)''$]. We estimated the first and second derivatives using finite differences for each bootstrap replicated smoothing term $sbr(x)$.

We also assessed the resilience dynamics with climate driven ecosystem transitions, using the IRA (Figure 3.11.). This method appears to define very well two distinct regimes in our time series related to the drivers (Figure 3.11. a-c-e), with a fold bifurcation and two potential tipping points. The analysis of t-GAMs showed that the cut-off year dividing two potential regimes occurred at 2011 with SST as predictor, in 2012 with Sun, in 2014 with SS and in 2010 with modelled flux. These cut-off years agree relatively well with the patterns observed in the GAMM. Hence, the sharp biomass declines in *G. corneum* observed within 2010-2015 appear to be driven by the cumulative effect of the set or predictors used in this analysis. However, in terms of resilience (Figure 3.11. b-d-f-h), the stability landscape and basins of attraction borders in the response curves do not match with the end and the start of the new regimes, if we look across the years (Scheffer et al. 2001), in any of the used predictors. One might expect that as conditions change and the system approaches a tipping point (F1 or F2) the resilience to erode, and the basins of attraction become narrower and shallower. However, in our analysis the resilience decreases as *G. corneum* biomass levels approach a tipping point in some cases, but in other cases there is not a clear agreement between the decrease in resilience and the start of the tipping point (Figure 3.11. b-d-f-h).

Figure 3.11. Threshold GAM fit showing the discontinuous response of *Gelidium corneum* biomass used as ecosystem state indicator, to fluctuations of a) Sea Surface Temperature (SST), c) Hours of Sun (sun h), e) Suspended Solids (SS) and g) flux model. TGAM represents a system response curve that is folded backwards, forming a fold bifurcation with two tipping points. This method used the ‘genuine’ cross-validation squared prediction error (gCV), which accounts for the estimation of the threshold year across the time series (Ciannelli et al. 2004). b-d-f-h Stability landscapes and estimated relative resilience for the *G. corneum* ecosystem dynamics. Continuous, black lines indicate the attractors, dotted black lines indicate the possible extensions of the attractors, and the points indicate the start of the tipping point.

The SCM allows for modelling the dynamics of a state variable depending on two interactive drivers. Here, to confirm the presence of tipping points, and particularly the presence of hysteresis, we performed the stochastic cusp model with two interacting drivers, including SST, flux model, Sun hours and SS according to different harvest levels (Figure 3.12).

Figure 3.12. Regime shifts and reversibility of *G. corneum* ecosystem in the Bay of Biscay’s Basque coast. Results of the stochastic cusp models using *G. Corneum* biomass as state variable modelled against flux model and Sea Surface Temperature (SST). The point diameter is scaled according to biomass levels. The light blue area represents the cusp area or area below the fold, in which the system can exist in any of three states, two stable and one unstable.

Considering the great influence of model flux on *G. corneum* observed biomass patterns, we have applied the CUSP model using flux as asymmetry parameter and SST, Sun h and SS as bifurcation variable. Here, we only show results of flux model and SST at varying harvest levels. In the way we organise the model, “flux model” is the variable controlling the dimension of the state variable and SST creates the bifurcation. The light blue area (Figure 3.12) represents the cusp area or area below the fold, in which the system can exist in any of three states, two stable and one unstable. When using all data (Figure 3.12), based on these two interacting drivers (SST and flux model), the system seems to have always low resilience (it can be present at 3 different states, so it is highly unstable) across much of the time series. However, the analysis shows that there is not a clear agreement across the

years in and out the CUSP area and starting of the “tipping point”. Since the AIC of the CUSP model is higher relative to the AIC of the linear and logistic model (data not shown), the system appears not to present discontinuous dynamics, but rather a continuous gradual decrease and the presence of a new regime shift is discarded. In particular, the increase of temperature is increasing the instability of the system because it is increasing the area of the CUSP and thus the combination and levels of the drivers for which the system has low resilience (Figure 3.12). In contrast, at maximum harvest levels (Figure 3.12), the system is always within the CUSP area, with discontinuous dynamics that are prone to suffer a regime shift “anytime” within the time-series. At harvest level 1, it looks like the system is quite stable, maybe mirroring a natural perturbation which keeps biomass levels healthy (Figure 3.12). However, more research is needed to understand the patterns observed. The other set of used predictors (SS, Sun h) show similar patterns (not shown).

3.1.4 Discussion and further work

We have shown a significant decrease in *G. corneum* biomass over time, with a stronger decrease in the shallower depth (5 m) consistent with the variation of the energy flux. High wave energy flux clearly determines the decline in *G. corneum* biomass. However, differences in biomass decrease according to depth seems not to be determined by wave energy flux but by some other factors.

The harvest is a major driver explaining *G. corneum* patterns, with significant differences across harvest levels in biomass change. Probably, low harvest levels help the system to stay healthier relative to no harvest, as seen in the model results as well as the CUSP analysis, and also in picking experiments (Borja, 1994b). Flux model, and to a lesser SST, Sun hours and SS appear to be good predictors explaining temporal patterns of *G. corneum* biomass change.

We have shown a sharp decline in biomass according to GAMM within 2010-2015 period, which is consistent with the threshold years observed by the IRA analysis. Hence, this observed decline might be due to the cumulative effect of the predictors used in this analysis, especially the wave flux energy, potentially transitioning the *G. corneum* ecosystem to a new regime. In fact, after several studies, the Bay of Biscay (and especially the Basque coast) has been hit by several exceptional storms around that period, in 2009, 2010, 2013, 2014 and 2016, being the most destructive that of 2014, with the larger wave near 30 m height, while the other years waves were over 10 m (Gatzelumendi et al., 2018; Rivas et al., 2022). This repeated concentration of very large waves, with high energy flux, can explain this new regime for *G. corneum*, since the alga was not able to recover after several consecutive years of storms detaching it from the substrate, and unable to compensate with its slow growth (Borja 1994a). Hence, we speculate that the *G. corneum* ecosystem will hardly recover within the next years even if

the environmental conditions return to the healthier conditions or the human activities are minimized. Further work includes the analysis of the tipping point resolving by depth (5 m, 10 m, 15 m), analysis of cover in the *G. corneum* trends, explore harvest levels with IRA and threshold analysis, as well as the effect of dump and combined pressures (harvest and dump).

3.2 Sardine and Anchovy fisheries of the Ebro Delta

The study was carried out in the Ebro Delta continental shelf area (NW Mediterranean; Figure 3.13), a wide continental shelf of the Mediterranean Iberian Peninsula characterized by large intra-annual changes in environmental variables and productivity (Salat et al., 2002).

Figure 3.13. Map of the studied area (indicated by a black polygon) including the main fisheries harbours and the bathymetry.

Despite being located in an oligotrophic basin, the Ebro Delta coast and continental shelf has a relatively high primary production, whose nutrient enrichment is mainly due to the Liguro-Provençal current, the vertical mixing and the Ebro River runoff (Bosc et al., 2004; Salat et al., 2002). These special oceanographic conditions make the area an important spawning and nursery habitat for sardine and anchovy in the Mediterranean Sea (Giannoulaki et al., 2013; Palomera et al., 2007; Tugores et al., 2011) and a relevant fishing ground for the bottom-trawler and the purse seiner fleet (Merino et al., 2019).

In the late decades significant declines in sardine and anchovies' populations but specially on sardine biomass and sardine catches have been observed. Similarly, important biomass distribution changes have been observed.

3.2.1 Hypothesis

Main: We hypothesise that the observed changes can be explained by a combination of simultaneous ecological, environmental, and human-driven factors, and that these changes have exceeded a tipping point leading to a major change in the socio ecological system.

Specific question 1: Taking into consideration the human-led and ecological changes produced in the last decades in the Ebro Delta, can we identify any tipping point in the socio-ecological system that conditionate current and future **biomass** of sardines and anchovies?

Specific question 2: Taking into consideration the human-led and ecological changes produced in the last decades in the Ebro Delta, can we identify any tipping point in the socio-ecological system that conditionate current and future **biomass landings** of sardines and anchovies?

3.2.2 Data

Table 3.7 shows the key environmental, ecological and fishing effort related variables used in the temporal and the spatio-temporal analysis done to address the specific questions. These data have been completed by an exhaustive legislative review on the management measures applied since 1980 for purse seiners and bottom trawler fleets in the area. For the bottom-trawlers fisheries, only measures with possible effects on the small pelagic fishes' populations were included.

Results have been also discussed with fishers, and potential explanations of the results have been contrasted using their local ecological knowledge.

Data structure and pre-processing:

Temporal coverage:

- All data used in the temporal analysis data have been calculated annually for the period 2000-2020
- Spatio-temporal data, due to data availability limitations constrains was limited to 2004-2017.

Table 3.7. Variables used in temporal statistical models

Variable	Unit	Source
Sardine and anchovy landings	Tons	ICATMAR (Institut Català de Recerca per a la Governança del Mar), and COINCOPESCA (Comisión Interfederativa de Pescadores de la Comunidad Valenciana) database
Sardine and anchovy biomass	kg/km ²	May-July MEDITS yearly campaign
Hake biomass	kg/km ²	May-July MEDITS yearly campaign
Sardinella biomass	kg/km ²	May-July MEDITS yearly campaign
Bluefin tuna feeding habitat	occurrence (%)	JRC
YO hake feeding habitat	occurrence (%)	JRC
Purse seine fishing effort	Hours	General Secretariat of Fisheries of the Spanish Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Environment
Bottom trawling fishing effort	Hours	General Secretariat of Fisheries of the Spanish Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Environment
Sea surface temperature (SST)	°C	Copernicus SST monthly averages were taken from the Mediterranean Sea Physical Reanalysis Product (MEDSEA MULTIYEAR_PHY_006_004, Nigam <i>et al.</i> , 2021) at 0.042° spatial resolution for the study area.
Sea surface salinity (SSS)	Psu	Copernicus SST monthly averages were taken from the Mediterranean Sea Physical Reanalysis Product (MEDSEA MULTIYEAR_PHY_006_004, Nigam <i>et al.</i> , 2021) at 0.042° spatial resolution for the study area.
Net primary production (NPP)	mg/m ³	Copernicus monthly average of NPP was taken from the Mediterranean Sea Biochemical Reanalysis Product MEDSEA_MULTIYEAR_BGC_006_008, Teruzzi <i>et al.</i> , 2021) at 0.042° spatial resolution for the study area.
Ebro Delta Runoff	m ³ /s	Copernicus
Bathymetry	m	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) (https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/products/etopo-global-relief-model)

Pre-processing:

- Biomass data were log-transformed.
- In the spatiotemporal analysis the explanatory variables were standardized. To this end, the scale() function from the standardize package of the R software (Christopher, 2017) was used, and the variables were scaled by subtracting the mean and dividing the result by the variable's standard deviation.
- The occurrence models were fitted under a binomial distribution, while a Gaussian distribution was assumed for the biomass models
- In the temporal analysis bottom trawlers and purse seine fishing pressure were interpolated for the period 2000-2004 based on the number of vessels in the area.

3.2.3 Analyses applied

Variables of interest:

- Temporal analysis: anchovy and sardine biomass and landings.
- Spatiotemporal analysis: anchovy and sardine biomass distribution.

Specific analyses

Temporal analysis:

GENERALIZED LINEAR MODELS

Different models were tested combining interactions between environmental variables, competitors and predators, and the best fitted model was selected with backward stepwise procedure based on Akaike Information Criterion (AIC). Purse seiners' fishing effort was included as an offset, considering the effect of this variable during the model prediction, but without estimating a corresponding regression coefficient. Year was included as a variable to account for the interannual variability. After selecting the best-fitted model, the segmented R package (Muggeo, 2008) was employed to estimate potential breaking points where the relationship between landings or biomass and the variable "year" shows a shift in the temporal trend.

- First model: as explanatory variables, annual averages of SSS, SST and NPP in the study area were included.
- Second model: as explanatory variables, annual averages of SSS, SST, NPP, river runoff, sardinella biomass (competitor) and hake biomass (predator) in the study area from 2000 to 2020 were included.

GRADIENT FOREST MODELS

Different gradient forest model explorations were done to study sardine and anchovy biomass landings evolution using as explanatory variables annual averages of SSS, SST, NPP, sardinella biomass, tuna biomass, hake biomass, riverine water inputs for the period 2000-2020.

Spatiotemporal analysis:

Boosted Regression trees were used to model and predict the distribution (occurrence and biomass) of sardine and anchovy in the study area between 2004-2017. As independent variables, SSS, SST, NPP, purse-seine fishing effort, bottom trawling fishing effort, Bluefin tuna and hake probability of occurrence, and bathymetry in the study area were used.

To address overdispersion and the presence of excess of zeros in the data, a hurdle model was implemented. For this reason, BRTs were performed in two parts: first we modelled the probability of reaching a value of zero (presence or absence, thus quantifying occurrence) and then the probability of non-zero values (thus evaluating biomass) (Julià et al., 2023). The BRT parameters were optimized using the dismo package of the R software (Hijmans et al., 2021). The optimal number of boosting trees was assessed using the `gbm.step()` function through cross-validation, and the tree complexity and the learning rate were fixed at 1 and 0.01, respectively.

To account for the temporal dimension and the spatial autocorrelation, “Year” and the residuals autocovariate “RAC” were included as explanatory variables. For each model, the RAC was implemented to take into account the influence of the neighbour observation on the response variable at a particular location (Barcala et al., 2019; Crase et al., 2012; Escalle et al., 2016). The spatial autocorrelation was calculated using the local () function from the raster package (Hijmans, 2020) and tested using Moran’s index. The goodness of the predicted data (D2) was assessed through the percentage of variance explained by the model, obtained from the difference between the null model deviance and the residual deviance, divided by the null deviance.

The influence of each explanatory variable was calculated by the number of times the variable was selected to ramify the decision tree, weighted by the squared model improvement and divided by the total number of trees using the the gbm.step () function.

Finally, predicted maps of anchovy and sardine occurrence biomass were calculated by the predict() function of the gbm package (Greenwell et al. 2022).

More details on the methodology and data can be found in (Carbonell, 2023).

3.2.4 Results and interpretation

From the different temporal analysis performed, only the landings evolution of sardine seems to be compatible with a potential tipping point that took place in 2007 leading to a continuous decrease of sardine landings (Figure 3.14).

Figure 3.14. Sardine landings time series

None of the temporal generalized temporal models or the gradient forest models were able to provide very good model results, suggesting the need to work with spatiotemporal information or longer temporal periods.

BRTs models developed to explain anchovy and sardine explained a moderate percentage of the total variability for both species (35-43%). The spatiotemporal BRT model in combination with the legislative regulatory review suggest that this landing change may have been triggered not only by changes in the specific conditions on the environmental variables, that are relevant to evaluate the occurrence and biomass of both anchovy and sardine (Table 3.8), but also by consecutive changes (in 2000 and mainly in 2007) on the regulations that allows bottom trawling entrance in shallower areas (20-50 meters) (Figure 3.15). In the sardine occurrence evaluation, the BRT model suggest that bottom trawling is the second factor more relevant after depth in the explanation of sardine occurrence.

Table 3.8. Functional response of the different explanatory variables in the spatiotemporal models of occurrence and biomass for each specie. The response that each independent variable has on the response variable is represented in green for positive effect (+), in red for negative effect (-), and in orange for mixed () or u-shaped (U) effects, and blue for dome effects.

		Variables								
Model	Species	Depth	Year	purse	trawl	SSS	SST	NPP	Tuna	Hake
Occurrence	Anchovy	+	+	+	dome	+	-	+	~	~
	Sardine	+	+	+	dome	~	U	const	const	~
Log-biomass	Anchovy	const	+	+	dome	+	-	+	-	+
	Sardine	+	-	const	+	-	-	+	+	U

Figure 3.15. Main bottom trawling and purse-seine regulation changes in the area

The changes in regulation -specially the one implemented in 2007- lead a continuous increased bottom trawling pressure in important sardine nursery areas since their approval (Figure 3.15). This factor may have contributed to exceed a tipping point in the area through the capture of juveniles. This change is coherent with a recent study on the discards of bottom-trawlers in the area that indicates that sardine and anchovy account for 50% of discards of bottom trawling activity in this area (Blanco et al., 2023), and with the local ecological knowledge of local purse seine fishers that have always though that this interaction is a key explanatory factor on sardine temporal landings evolution (Arego, 2018).

Figure 3.16. Annual bottom trawler’s fishing efforts (hours) in the Ebro continental shelf before and after the implementation of Order APA/1074/2007. After 2007, bottom trawlers in the Ebro Delta continental shelf could work from 3 natural miles independent of the depth.

It is important to note that the bottom trawling regulation in this area is an exception of the Mediterranean Sea regulation where the minimum bottom trawling depth was fixed in general at 50 meters (Regulation (EC) n°1967/2006, Art.13).

3.2.5 Learned lessons

The Ebro Delta case points out to some of the requirements and potentials in order to be able to study potential tipping points.

First it makes clear that the amount of data needed to obtain robust results is important. In our case temporal yearly landing data for almost twenty years of multiple variables were enough to provide important information but not conclusive lessons. The impossibility of getting more detailed

information of this period in this area makes difficult to continue the analysis based only in temporal data.

Nevertheless, this case study also shows the usefulness of combined analytical approaches. In our case it shows that introducing spatio-temporal analysis and using boosted regression trees can be an interesting approach to develop specific analysis. It also points out to the possibility of combining quantitative modelling with other relevant information coming from qualitative research such as historical regulatory data combined with local knowledge. The combination of strategies increases the explanatory potential of quantitative models.

3.3 Identification of tipping points for phytoplankton biomass and alpha diversity in LS3, LS8 and LS9 in relation with time and environmental factors

Phytoplankton accounts for almost 50% of global primary production and enormously affects aquatic food webs and the operation of the global system (Pierella Karlusich et al., 2023). Although phytoplankton is considered as a rather robust organism (Henson et al., 2021), changes in biomass and alpha diversity often occur both at global and local scales when environmental conditions are altered (Spatharis and Tsirtsis, 2010). High alterations of those conditions may lead to abrupt changes of phytoplankton biomass and community composition, which may be persistent if environmental changes also persist. Environmental conditions include direct drivers of phytoplankton growth as nutrients (mainly nitrogen and phosphorus) or indirect drivers as temperature and salinity (Tamvakis et al., 2014). The latter define through the pycnocline the so called compensation depth (Mann and Lazier, 2006). If phytoplankton cells are restricted in a surface layer shallower than this depth, net growth of biomass appears and the opposite occurs when the surface layer is deeper than the compensation depth. The moving barrier defining the depth of the surface layer is the pycnocline, whereas in shallow coastal waters this barrier is often the bottom. Therefore, changes in the pycnocline depth along with the availability of nutrients in the surface layer, originating either from the deeper layer or from terrestrial sources, are the main factors driving the growth of phytoplankton biomass in seawater.

Since phytoplankton comprises a huge number of species with different traits, shapes and sizes, changes in environmental conditions affecting biomass, also affect diversity. Alpha diversity in particular, is related with the distribution of abundance among species and can be expressed through a number of indices, either of simple or more complicated mathematical formulas, showing the diversity, evenness or dominance of the phytoplankton community (Spatharis and Tsirtsis, 2010).

In the current work three databases of phytoplankton at species level were explored aiming to find tipping points of abundance and alpha diversity in relation with time (when applicable) and environmental factors, namely Dissolved Inorganic Nitrogen (DIN), Dissolved Inorganic Phosphorus (DIP), temperature and salinity. The first database is from coastal Danish waters (Learning Site 3, LS3) provided by Aarhus University, Denmark, the second from western Black Sea (Learning Site 9, LS9) provided by the National Institute for Marine Research and Development “Grigore Antipa”, Constanta, Romania and the third from Aegean coastal waters (Learning Site 8, LS8) provided by the Dept of Marine Sciences, University of the Aegean.

3.3.1 Hypothesis

Main: Changes and intensification of human activities in coastal European waters affect phytoplankton abundance and diversity. If those changes persist may lead to tipping points of different ecological states, possibly explained by a number of environmental drivers.

Specific question 1: Taking into consideration recent changes in human activities in coastal areas, can we identify tipping points of phytoplankton abundance, biomass or alpha diversity with time in LS3 and LS9, where long time series are available? When annual values are considered (in LS3 and LS9), that is annual means, annual maxima and annual number of extremes of phytoplankton abundance and alpha diversity, can we identify tipping points?

Specific question 2: Can we associate possible tipping points with environmental drivers (specifically DIN, DIP, temperature and salinity (analyses applied in LS3, LS8 and LS9)?

Specific question 3: When considering all the three investigated areas (LS3, LS8 and LS9) can we arrive in common rules for phytoplankton growth in relation with environmental drivers and possibly establish thresholds above which rapid phytoplankton growth or alterations of alpha diversity occur?

3.3.2 Data

First database from Danish waters (LS3)

Data were compiled for 4 stations in Danish waters, namely ARH170006, VIB3708, NOR5503 and ROS60 (Figure 3.17) sampled from the column of 0-10 m, on a monthly or more frequent basis, each station at different time periods, covering at least three decades. Station ARH170006 was sampled from 1978 to 2021, mostly twice per month, station VIB3708 from 1985 to 2021, mostly twice per

month, station NOR5503 from 1991 to 2021 mostly twice per month or more frequently and station ROS60 from 1987 to 2021, mostly twice per month.

Figure 3.17. Location of the 4 sampling stations in Danish waters (LS3) sampled on a monthly or more frequent basis in different time periods of at least three decades.

The biotic information includes phytoplankton community data at species level, whereas environmental information is available for Dissolved Inorganic Nitrogen (DIN), Dissolved Inorganic Phosphorus (DIP), salinity, temperature and N to P ratio.

Second database from western Black Sea (LS9)

Data were collected from 3 areas, Sulina close to the Danube River outflow, Est-Constanta and Mangalia (Figure 3.18). Five stations with maximum depth of 20 m were sampled in Sulina, a total of 34 samples from 2008-2018, from May to September. In Est-Constanta, 7 stations were sampled with maximum depth of 80 m, a total of 140 samples from 2009-2018, from May to September. Finally at Mangalia, 55 samples were collected from 2008-2018, from May to August, at 6 stations with

maximum depth of 90 m. The sampling was done under national research project and monitoring program and includes simultaneously chemical and biological parameters.

Figure 3.18. Location of sampling stations in western Black Sea in Sulina (5 stations) close to the Danube river outflow, Est-Constanta (7 stations) and Mangalia (6 stations).

The biotic information includes phytoplankton data at species level, both abundance and wet biomass, and environmental information includes PO₄, NO₃, NO₂, NH₄, temperature and salinity. Dissolved Inorganic Nitrogen was calculated by adding NO₃, NO₂ and NH₄ and N to P ratio by dividing DIN to DIP (PO₄).

Third database from Aegean coastal waters (LS8)

The dataset employed in this study includes 701 field samples from coastal areas of the Aegean Sea in Eastern Mediterranean (Figure 3.19), representing a wide range of productivity. At each station, repetitive sampling was carried out covering at least a full annual cycle mostly on a monthly basis. Detailed information about the sampling sites and data collection are provided in Spatharis et al.

(2008). Inner Saronikos Gulf (S, 2 stations), near Athens is characteristic of eutrophic conditions (Simboura et al., 2005). Outer Saronikos Gulf (S, 7 stations), Gera Gulf (G, 8 stations) and Rhodes coastal (R1, 10 stations) are more typical of mesotrophic conditions (Arhonditsis et al., 2000), while offshore stations in Rhodes Island (R2, 5 stations) have been characterized as oligotrophic (Kitsiou et al., 2002). Finally, the 2 stations in the Strait of Mytilene (M) fall in the range from eutrophication to mesotrophy. A detailed account on the eutrophication level and ecological status of these areas is provided in Spatharis and Tsirtsis (2010).

The available biotic information includes phytoplankton abundance at species level identified in an inverted microscope and environmental information includes DIP and DIN concentrations, N to P ratio, temperature and salinity.

Figure 3.19. Location of sampling stations in Aegean Sea, W. Mediterranean, in Saronikos (9 stations) close to the Metropolitan area of Athens, Gera Gulf (8 stations) and Strait of Mytilene (2 stations) in the island of Lesbos, Rhodes offshore waters (5 stations) and Rhodes coastal waters (10 stations) in the island of Rhodes.

3.3.3 Analyses applied

Calculation of phytoplankton alpha diversity

Phytoplankton alpha diversity was calculated by a number of indices, expressing diversity, evenness and dominance. For diversity Menhinick's and Shannon's indices were used, for evenness the index of

Pielou and for dominance the McNaughton's index. The mathematical formulas for the calculation of these indices are the following:

1. Menhinick's index of diversity: $d = \frac{S}{\sqrt{N}}$, where S species richness and N the total abundance.
2. Shannon's index: $H = -\sum p_i \times \ln p_i$, where $p_i = \frac{N_i}{N}$, N_i the abundance of the i species.
3. Pielou's evenness index: $J = \frac{H}{\ln S}$.
4. McNaughton dominance index: $D = \frac{N_1 + N_2}{N}$, where N_1 and N_2 the abundance of the 2 most dominant species.

Methods for the identification of tipping points for phytoplankton (abundance and alpha diversity)

Various methods were applied for the identification of tipping points of phytoplankton data for means and variances, namely binary segmentation method, segmented neighbour method, PELT algorithm and SiZer method (Carstensen and Weydmann, 2012; Sonderegger et al., 2009). All those methods were applied aiming to arrive in more robust results. As already mentioned above in the specific questions of the current study, identification of tipping points for phytoplankton with time was attempted for LS3 and LS8, where long time series were available. For those areas identification of tipping points was also attempted for annual values, namely annual means, annual maxima and annual number of extremes, the latter calculated as the number of values exceeding the median of the corresponding dataset. Since phytoplankton identification at species level may be biased due to classification by different taxonomists, all analyses were also applied by aggregating data at genus level.

For all LSs, identification of tipping points for phytoplankton were also attempted in relation with environmental drivers, namely DIN, DIP, temperature and salinity. All analyses were performed within R Statistical Software (R Core Team, 2024) using changepoint (Killick et al., 2022) and SiZer (Sonderegger, 2022) packages.

Preprocessing-Transformations-Standardization

Phytoplankton variables (abundance, wet biomass and alpha diversity) were standardized by applying z-score standardization. Since normality is required to apply this standardization method, it was checked by observing q-q plots and histograms with overlaid normal curves. For variables showing strong departure from normality, logarithmic transformation was applied.

3.3.4 Results and interpretation

Summary statistics for the variables under consideration in the three LSs

Summary statistics for the variables under consideration, both biotic and environmental, in the 3 LSs are shown in Table 3.9.

Table 3.9. Summary statistics for biotic and environmental variables in Danish waters (LS3), Aegean Sea (LS8) and Black Sea (LS9): N phytoplankton abundance in cells/L, S species richness, Menh Menhinick's diversity, H Shannon's diversity, D McNaughton's dominance, temp temperature in °C, sal salinity in ‰, DIN Dissolved Inorganic Nitrogen in µM, DIP Dissolved Inorganic Phosphorus in µM.

Statistic	N	S	Menh	H	J	D	temp	sal	DIN	DIP
<u>LS3. Danish waters</u>										
min	100	1	0.00	0.00	0.00	23.9	-1.4	9.42	0.12	0.00
max	1618398979	64	0.22	2.97	1.00	100.0	24.9	30.74	252.50	34.19
mean	15332320	17	0.01	1.09	0.42	80.6	11.0	19.55	22.68	2.05
<u>LS8. Aegean Sea</u>										
min	960	4	0.01	0.07	0.03	20.0	9.9	27.98	0.12	0.01
max	6398960	43	0.34	3.10	0.98	99.6	27.6	40.28	37.95	6.00
mean	126976	16	0.13	1.80	0.67	59.7	19.3	38.67	1.93	0.14
<u>LS9. Black Sea</u>										
min	3220	3	0.01	0.31	0.09	26.0	7.2	0.11	1.39	0.01
max	9350280	52	0.13	2.98	0.93	97.1	27.3	20.30	82.75	4.00
mean	752448	25	0.06	1.75	0.57	64.6	19.5	15.11	12.01	0.31

Considering phytoplankton, Danish waters (LS3) show rather higher eutrophication compared to the other sites, with highest abundances, lowest diversity and evenness and highest dominance in phytoplankton assemblages. Comparing Black Sea (LS9) and Aegean waters (LS8), the former show relatively higher abundances, lower diversity and evenness and higher dominance. The above trends can be possibly related with the nutrient availabilities (nitrogen and phosphorus), their mean concentrations being rather higher in LS3, compared to LS9 and LS8.

Regarding the physical parameters, mean temperature is higher in Black Sea and Aegean waters compared to Danish waters. Salinity in the Aegean is typical of Eastern Mediterranean seawater, whereas in the other sites salinity is low, characteristic of coastal systems influenced by freshwater inputs. The Black Sea is a natural brackish water body with a surface salinity of around 16 and bottom salinity of approximately 22. However, salinity levels can sometimes be lower due to freshwater inputs from the Danube River and other coastal sources

Identification of tipping points for phytoplankton in Danish waters (LS3)

Tipping points were not identified for phytoplankton abundance with time in the four stations under consideration. However, tipping points were identified for species richness by all applied methods in stations ARH170006 (Figure 3.20), NOR5503 and VIB3708. In station ARH170006, the change of richness with time shows a humpback behaviour with two points of discontinuity, a shift in 2000 and a decline after 2007. Those changes are of the order of a decade in untransformed values. In NOR5503 and VIB3708, a similar humpback trend is observed, however the time points of discontinuities are different, being for NOR5503 in 2006 the shift and 2016 the decline and for VIB3708 in 2007 the shift and 2014 the decline. In order to remove possible effects of misclassification at species level due to classification by different taxonomists, the analyses were also applied at genus level, however the main findings were similar. The discontinuities observed for species richness also affected alpha diversity, with tipping points observed for a number of indices. However, the shifts or declines of richness did not always affect consistently diversity, as expressed by the various indices. For example, in station ARH170006 the decline of richness was associated with lower diversity and higher dominance, whereas in VIB3708 the opposite was observed.

Figure 3.20. Identification of tipping points for phytoplankton species richness in station ARH170006.

Interesting results were obtained when tipping points were identified for annual values, namely means, maxima and number of extremes (number of values during a year, higher than the median of the whole dataset). In station ARH170006, all annual values of species richness decrease sharply after 2010, identified as tipping points by most methods (annual means in Figure 3.21, left). Tipping points were also identified for the number of extremes of total abundance (Figure 3.21, right). In NOR5503 annual maxima of species richness decrease sharply after 2017, and the same was observed for the number of extremes of total abundance after 2010 and richness after 2015. Finally in station VIB3708,

the number of annual extremes shows tipping points (decrease) for total abundance after 2010 and for richness after 2015.

Figure 3.21. Identification of tipping points for (a) annual means of phytoplankton species richness (top) and (b) annual number of extremes of total abundance (bottom), in station ARH170006.

Identification of tipping points in Danish waters was also attempted for phytoplankton variables in relation with environmental factors (DIN, DIP, temperature and salinity). Based on the N:P ratio, station ARH170006 seems to be nitrogen limited most of the time, whereas the rest stations are mainly phosphorus limited. In all stations consistent identification of tipping points of decline was observed for total abundance, when DIN concentration was increasing (Figure 3.22, for station ARH170006). In stations ARH170006 and NOR5503, species richness also decreased with increasing DIN, whereas increasing DIP only affected both total abundance and species richness in station ARH170006. The above changes in total abundance and species richness also affected alpha diversity which showed some tipping points, however consistent trends across all stations were not observed.

Figure 3.22. Tipping points of phytoplankton total abundance related with DIN concentration for station ARH170006.

Identification of tipping points for phytoplankton in Black Sea waters (LS9)

All methods for the identification of tipping points of phytoplankton variables, both abundance, wet biomass, and alpha diversity were applied separately for each sampling site (Sulina, Mangalia and Est-Constanta) and for the whole dataset. For the latter, a tipping point of decrease was identified for total abundance after 2015 (Figure 3.23). A similar trend was observed for wet biomass, although the discontinuity appeared earlier, in 2012. The composition of phytoplankton assemblages also changed after 2015, showing higher diversity and evenness and lower dominance. Almost similar trends as of the whole dataset were observed when separate analyses were conducted for each sampling site (Sulina, Mangalia and Est-Constanta).

Figure 3.23. Identification of tipping points for phytoplankton total abundance of the Black Sea dataset.

Considering annual values, tipping points were only observed for the number of extremes for both abundance and species richness (Figure 3.24). A humpback behaviour was observed with two tipping points for both variables of shift and decline in 2012 and 2015, respectively.

Figure 3.24. Identification of tipping points of annual number of extremes for total abundance (top) and species richness (bottom) for Black Sea waters.

Identification of tipping points in Black Sea waters was also attempted for phytoplankton variables in relation with environmental drivers (DIN, DIP, temperature and salinity). Based on the N:P ratio, Black Sea waters are almost always phosphorus limited during the sampling period, which was from May to September. Interesting results were obtained for the identification of tipping points for both total abundance and species richness in relation with all environmental variables. More abundant, speciose and diverse phytoplankton assemblages are observed when temperature is increasing. However, increasing salinity has the opposite effect on total abundance and richness, although supports increased diversity and evenness.

Nutrients (DIN and DIP) also affect phytoplankton and tipping points are identified in a rather consistent manner. Total abundance and species richness are increasing with DIN and DIP (Figure 3.25), however diversity and evenness decrease. The use of wet biomass instead of abundance does not change the observed patterns.

Figure 3.25. Tipping points identified for (a) total abundance in relation with DIN (top) and (b) species richness in relation with DIP (bottom).

Identification of tipping points for phytoplankton in Aegean waters (LS8)

For Aegean coastal waters (LS8) long databases in regular time intervals were not available. Therefore, attempt was made to identify tipping points in relation to environmental factors by aggregating the available information from different sites and time periods.

Consistent results (observed with all applied methods) were obtained when identifying tipping points in relation to salinity for phytoplankton abundance, species richness, Menhinick’s and Shannon’s diversities, Pielou’s evenness and McNaughton’s dominance. As an example, the result for total abundance is shown in Figure 3.26. It can be seen that abundance is increasing at low salinities and the opposite holds for high salinities. Those changes with salinity may reflect the different areas from which the samples were taken being coastal waters, open sea or enclosed bays.

Figure 3.26. Tipping points of total abundance in relation with salinity in Aegean coastal waters.

Both nutrients considered (nitrogen and phosphorus) have similar effects on phytoplankton variables and consistent results are obtained in the identification of tipping points. Total abundance and species richness increase with increasing DIN and DIP, whereas diversity and evenness consistently decrease. Tipping points of total abundance in relation with DIN and species richness in relation with DIP are shown in Figure 3.27.

Figure 3.27. Tipping points of (a) total abundance in relation with DIN (top) and (b) species richness in relation with DIP (bottom).

The equivalent role of DIN and DIP for the shaping of phytoplankton assemblages may be related with the N:P ratio in the Aegean sites used in the current study which does not show clearly which is the prevailing limiting factor (Figure 3.28).

Figure 3.28. Nitrogen to Phosphorus ratio in the samples from Aegean coastal waters used in the current study.

3.3.5 Discussion and future work

Although tipping points identified for phytoplankton variables with time in LS2 and LS9 may be related with changes in local conditions, including either human activities or meteorology, more general ecological considerations can be made for the tipping points in relation with environmental drivers. Based on the results of the analyses for the three Learning Sites, DIN seems to be a common factor defining tipping points for phytoplankton abundance, species richness and alpha diversity. Aiming to further study this role of DIN and possibly arrive to some common rules for all LSs and establish thresholds, the analysis for tipping points was applied on a ‘typical dataset’ covering the whole range of values of DIN observed in the three LSs. This ‘typical dataset’ was formed comprising all available data from LS8 and LS9 and data from station NOR5503 from LS2. DIN values in LS8 and LS9 cover the lower part of the range, being up to 37.95 and 82.75 μM in LS8 and LS9, respectively. Station NOR5503 was selected from LS2 due to its high range of DIN values, being up to 252.50 μM .

Consistent identification of tipping points was observed for phytoplankton abundance and alpha diversity in relation with DIN for the ‘typical dataset’. Abundance is continuously increasing with DIN showing four tipping points, species richness shows a humpback behaviour with higher values in the middle of the DIN range (Figure 3.29), Menhinick’s and Shannon’s diversities and Pielou’s evenness decrease with increasing DIN, whereas McNaughton’s dominance shows the opposite trend.

Figure 3.29. Tipping points identified for species richness along the whole range of DIN values observed in the three Learning Sites.

Aiming to further synthesize the findings of the current study, the location of tipping points along the DIN range for the untransformed values of phytoplankton variables is shown and discussed below. For phytoplankton abundance (Figure 3.30), tipping points are identified in rather low concentrations, below 14 μM , resulting to the increase of abundance up to 6 million cells/L. The most important tipping points seem to be close to 4 and 13 μM , in which abundance shows an almost sixfold increase.

Figure 3.30. Location of tipping points of phytoplankton abundance along the DIN range in the three Learning Sites. Circles in the end of lines show the direction of change in the specific tipping points.

Location of tipping points for species richness along the DIN range is shown in Figure 3.31. Species richness does not change as rapidly as the abundance, the range of change being up to 90 μM . At low concentrations, below 4 μM , an increase of richness is observed, followed by a rapid decrease from above 16 to about 8 species at a DIN concentration of about 30 μM . The observed tipping points above this concentration are almost equally spaced in the DIN range, each one causing a decrease of about 2 species.

Figure 3.31. Location of tipping points of species richness along the DIN range in the three Learning Sites. Circles in the end of lines show the direction of change in the specific tipping points.

Alpha diversity was expressed with Shannon’s and Menhinick’s indices. The location of tipping points of Shannon’s diversity along the DIN range is shown in Figure 3.32. Diversity is decreasing when DIN is increasing with two tipping points identified below 40 μM . A rapid decrease is observed just below 15 μM and a second just below 40 μM . For Menhinick’s diversity the critical range of DIN concentration for the decrease of diversity is from 4 to 10 μM , possibly due to the strong dependence of the Menhinick’s index on total abundance. The important role of low concentrations of DIN can be also seen in the corresponding graph for McNaughton’s dominance (Figure 3.33). A rapid increase of dominance from below 60 to almost 70% is observed for concentrations just above 4 μM .

Figure 3.32. Location of tipping points of Shannon’ diversity along the DIN range in the three Learning Sites. Circles in the end of lines show the direction of change in the specific tipping points.

Figure 3.33. Location of tipping points of McNaughton’s dominance along the DIN range in the three Learning Sites. Circles in the end of lines show the direction of change in the specific tipping points.

In conclusion, DIN seems to be the most important nutrient for phytoplankton growth in all the three Learning Sites. Tipping points for abundance, species richness and alpha diversity are observed at relatively low concentrations, mostly below 10 μM . A critical point seems to be the concentration of 4 μM above which abundance is rapidly increasing, species richness is decreasing and dominance is also increasing, affecting alpha diversity. Therefore, measures for the reduction of DIN concentrations below those values can be essential for the conservation of the good ecological state of coastal marine environments. Future work may include the further testing of the applied methods in more European sites, for the evaluation of the general applicability of the defined thresholds and the possible integration of those thresholds into assessment tools for the good ecological state of European waters.

3.4 From Macroalgal Forests to Barrens: High Grazing Pressure Drives Regime Shifts in Eastern Mediterranean Rocky Reef Ecosystems

Macroalgal forests are key structural components of Mediterranean rocky reefs (Bevilacqua et al., 2021). Under pristine conditions, these forests form extensive three-dimensional structures comprising various macroalgal species, mainly from the genera *Ericaria*, *Gongolaria*, *Cystoseira* (hereafter referred as *Cystoseira* sensu lato; Novoa and Guiry, 2019) and *Sargassum*. These structures provide valuable habitats for marine organisms supporting high biodiversity, ecosystem functioning and ecosystem services (Cheminée et al., 2013, 2017; De La Fuente et al., 2019; Manusco et al., 2021).

In the Eastern Mediterranean, a bio-invasion and climate change hotspot (Katsanevakis et al., 2024), extensive loss of macroalgal forests is evident (Nikolaou et al., 2023). Historically, the primary herbivores grazing on these forests were the native sea urchins *Paracentrotus lividus* and *Arbacia lixula* (Bulleri et al., 1999; Guidetti and Dulčić, 2007; Tsirintanis et al., 2018), alongside with the fish *Sarpa salpa* (Vergés et al., 2009; Gianni et al., 2017; Tsirintanis et al., 2018).

However, in the easternmost parts of the basin (e.g. Levantine Sea), rising temperatures have decimated *P. lividus* populations (Yeruham et al., 2015, 2020). These areas are now dominated by two invasive herbivorous rabbitfish species, *Siganus luridus* and *S. rivulatus*, which first entered the Mediterranean through the Suez Canal around late 1920. These invasive species graze intensively on macroalgal forests, confining their distribution to a narrow, shallow band in the lower midlittoral and upper infralittoral zone (Sala et al., 2011; Vergés et al., 2014; Nikolaou et al., 2023).

In contrast, in the colder Aegean Sea, *P. lividus* and native *S. salpa* remain the dominant grazers, as *Siganus* species have not yet established significant populations, while retaining a generally impoverished state of macroalgal forests (Giakoumi et al., 2012; Savin et al., 2023).

The Eastern Mediterranean is a data-poor region, lacking extensive temporal datasets on the state of macroalgal forests, as well as fish and sea urchin communities. Consequently, pinpointing the exact timing of regime shifts — from macroalgal forests to turf or barren formations — remains challenging. Nevertheless, regime shift dynamics of rocky reefs can be investigated using a dense network of sampling stations in space (Figure 3.34).

Figure 3.34: Map of the study area and study sites numbered. Sea Surface Temperature (SST) data are for the 2016-2020 period and were retrieved from Copernicus Marine Service – Data Store (data product identifier: SST_MEDSST_L4_REP_OBSERVATIONS_010_021; <https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/products>)

3.4.1 Hypothesis

Main: The primary hypothesis suggests that macroalgal forests in the Eastern Mediterranean may undergo an abrupt transition to a turf or barren state once the overall grazing pressure surpasses a critical threshold.

Specific question 1: What is the status of macroalgal forests in the Eastern Mediterranean, and which herbivores affect their status?

Specific question 2: Can these regime shifts be explained by cumulative grazing pressure?

3.4.2 Data source

The data were collected from various projects (PROTOMEDEA, MARISCA and ALAS) and span from 2016 to 2021. The spatial coverage extends from the warmer Levantine Sea to the colder North Aegean Sea (Figure 3.34).

For each site, the data include canopy coverage (%) at depths of 0 and 5 m, sea urchin density (individuals/m²), and herbivorous fish biomass (g/m²) at 5 m depth (Table 3.10).

Table 3.10: Data details on sea urchin, fish, and algae distribution.

Variable	Species	Depth zone
Canopy coverage (%)	<i>Cystoseira s.l.</i> , <i>Sargassum</i> spp.	0 and 5 m
Sea urchin density (individuals/m ²)	<i>Paracentrotus lividus</i> , <i>Arabcia lixula</i>	5 m
Fish biomass (g/m ²)	Natives: <i>Sarpa salpa</i> , <i>Sparisoma cretense</i> Aliens: <i>Siganus luridus</i> , <i>Siganus rivulatus</i>	5m

Pre-processing

For the analysis, the average canopy cover at depths of 0 and 5 m was used.

To investigate potential tipping points, a cumulative grazing index pressure was developed. Herbivore values were normalized using min-max normalization then multiplied by specific weights (Table 3.11) based on their relative significance in grazing pressure, as reported in the literature.

In the colder regions of the Mediterranean, where *Siganus* spp. have not established significant populations, sea urchins are the primary grazers of macroalgal forests, which under specific circumstances can cause a shift towards a barren state (Hereu et al., 2006; Tsirintanis et al., 2018). While other native herbivores also affect macroalgal communities (Vergés et al., 2014; Giani et al., 2017), they do not lead to extensive barren formations as sea urchins do.

In the warmer regions invaded by *Siganus* species, *S. luridus* and *S. rivulatus* are considered the primary consumers of macroalgal forests and the main drivers towards an alternative barren state (Sala et al., 2011; Vergés et al., 2014). These species have also been reported as more significant grazers than sea urchins, exerting competitive stress on the native *P. lividus* (Yeruham et al., 2019).

The two *Siganus* species have similar diets, but they have different feeding preferences (Shakman et al., 2009). Studies have reported that *S. luridus* prefers to feed on adult brown canopy-forming macroalgae, such as *Cystoseira s.l.* spp, and *Sargassum* spp., while *S. rivulatus* prefers to feed on turf and epilithic algal matrix which includes early life-history stages of macroalgae (Stergiou et al., 1988;

Lundberg and Golani, 1995; Shakman et al., 2009). Similarly, *S. cretense* is considered EAM consumer (Vergés et al., 2014).

The grazing index was calculated as the sum of the weighted abundance values for all herbivores.

Table 3.11: Weights given to herbivores based on the literature.

Species	Weight
<i>Siganus luridus</i>	5
<i>Sea urchins</i>	4
<i>Sarpa salpa</i>	3
<i>Siganus rivulatus</i>	2
<i>Sparisoma cretense</i>	1

Analyses applied

To examine the relationship between canopy coverage and grazing pressure and investigate for potential critical points, the R package *strucchange* (Zeileis et al., 2001; 2003) was used. The algorithm in *strucchange* package considers all possible ways to split the dataset into contiguous segments and fits a linear regression for each segment, allowing each to have its own coefficient. It identifies the optimal change points (if any exist) by minimizing the total Residual Sum of Squares (RSS) across the dataset. The significance of the change point is assessed by estimating an F-statistic (Chow test).

As input to the algorithm, the average and maximum canopy coverage were estimated at different grazing pressure index values. These were calculated as single values for each observation as required for the analysis. For the same datasets, GAMs were fitted using the *mgcv* package (Wood, 2017), and the first derivative of the smooth curve was estimated using the *gratia* package (Simpson et al., 2024). Additionally, areas of significant change were highlighted using the *gratia* package. Finally, herbivore density and biomass were standardized, and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) scores were calculated. The PCA1 scores were then plotted against the canopy coverage.

3.4.3 Results and interpretation

The combined dataset clearly illustrates the different patterns of herbivores between the colder North Aegean and South Aegean & Levantine Sea. In the North Aegean, the main herbivores are the native sea urchins and *S. salpa*. In contrast, in the South Aegean & Levantine Sea, thermophilic invasive

Siganus and native parrotfish *S. cretense* prevail, while native sea urchin populations are decimated (Figure 3.35).

Figure 3.35: Bar plots display the average canopy cover of the 0 and 5 depth zones (%), sea urchin densities (individuals/m²) and the biomass (g/m²) of *Sarpa salpa*, *Sparisoma cretense*, *Siganus rivulatus*, and *Siganus luridus* at each study site. Bars are depicted with different colours; navy blue represents North Aegean sites and light blue represents South Aegean & Levantine Sea sites.

The abundance of herbivores is negatively correlated with the canopy cover, as shown by LOESS smooths (Figure 3.36). Additionally, when comparing canopy cover at 0 and 5 m depths, the 0 m depth zone generally exhibits higher macroalgal forest coverage (Figure 3.36).

Figure 3.36: Scatter plots displaying herbivore abundance in relation to canopy coverage at the different depth zones. For display purposes, herbivores data from the 5 m zone were used to plot canopy coverage at 0 m. LOESS curves are fitted to the data for different depth zones.

The change point analysis indicates an abrupt shift from macroalgal forest to turf or barren formations when a critical threshold of cumulative grazing pressure is exceeded. Using both average and maximum canopy values along the grazing pressure, a significant breakpoint was identified at a grazing index value of 3 [95% confidence intervals: 2.5-3.5] (Figure 3.37a,b).

Additionally, the results from the GAMs were consistent with these findings (Figure 3.37c,d). The first derivative of the GAM smooth for average canopy values peaked at 2.6, with a significant area of change (range where the estimated first derivative is significantly different from zero) occurring between 0.4 and 5.25 of the grazing index values. The GAM results using maximum canopy coverage aligned with the results obtained from the *strucchange* package, showing the highest rate of change at an index value of 3 and significant change between 2.1 and 3.96.

Figure 3.37: Canopy coverage as a function of cumulative grazing pressure. Canopy coverage at each grazing index step is shown as (a) the average or (b) maximum value. The presence of breakpoint at value 3 of the grazing index value is indicated by the dashed line, with 95% confidence intervals represented by the grey shading around the breakpoint. Smooth curves representing the fit derived from generalized additive models (GAMs) for (c) average and (d) maximum values of canopy coverage across the grazing index. The dashed line marks the point where the first derivative reaches its maximum value (highest rate of change), and the grey area indicates the region of significant change (where the estimated first derivative is significantly different from zero).

Although specific thresholds for species abundance combinations cannot be determined using the cumulative grazing index (this would need a larger dataset) the trajectory towards a barren state in the North Aegean is primarily driven by sea urchins and *Sarpa salpa*. In contrast, in the South Aegean & Levantine Sea, *Siganus* spp. are the main drivers pushing macroalgal forests toward a barren state (Figure 3.38).

Figure 3.38: Canopy cover plotted against PC1 values estimated from the standardized herbivores abundance. Forest state (green overlay) and barren state (red overlay) are separated at the 10% canopy coverage threshold for visualizing the paradigm. There is a slight differentiation between sites in the macroalgal forest state: Northern Aegean sites (NAS) are more concentrated on the left side of the plot, while South Aegean & Levantine sites (SAL) are more clustered on the right.

Once a barren state is established, species such as *S. rivulatus* and *S. cretense*, which feed on epilithic algal matrix that include the juvenile phases of macroalgal, may prevent natural recovery, thereby maintaining the degraded state (Vergés et al., 2014). Notably the high abundance of both species in the warmer sites, as observed in other studies (Vergés et al., 2014), may further reduce recovery potential compared to the colder North Aegean sites. However, experimental work is needed to confirm this. Additionally, the reverse shift toward a macroalgal-dominated state may be hindered by meso-grazers, such as *Idotea balthica*, which feed on juvenile *Cystoseira s.l.* (Montserrat et al., 2023).

These findings have important implications for conservation efforts. To successfully conserve Mediterranean macroalgal forests, it is essential to mitigate the cumulative grazing pressure while also facilitating recovery through restoration projects to shorten the reverse shift period. The latter is essential, as many *Cystoseira s.l.* species have limited dispersal capacity, making natural recovery after complete depletion challenging (Fehér et al., 2023).

For sea urchins-dominated barrens, mitigation measures could include establishing marine protected areas (MPAs) to allow populations of sea urchins predators (e.g. *Diplodus sargus*), to recover from overfishing and subsequently regulate sea urchin grazing (Micheli et al., 2005; Peleg et al., 2023). Another option is targeted sea urchin removals (Miller et al., 2022).

However, MPAs may have the opposite effects (Reis et al., 2024) especially in *Siganus* dominated regions. Studies have shown that *Siganus* population within MPAs can increase in abundance, significantly impacting macroalgal communities (Dimitriadis et al., 2024). In these areas, targeted fishing (even within MPAs) may be the only viable method to mitigate their grazing pressure. This consideration is crucial for future conservation planning, as *Siganus* spp. are thermophilic species expected to expand into the western Mediterranean as sea temperatures continue to rise.

Evidence suggests greater ecological resilience in shallower zones, likely due to higher hydrodynamism (Vergés et al., 2009). This is particularly significant as efforts to restore macroalgal forests in the Mediterranean are currently ongoing (Cebrian et al., 2021; Fabbrizzi et al., 2023). The present and future impacts of invasive *Siganus* spp. on macroalgal forests must be carefully considered in conservation planning. Pristine sites with a healthy macroalgal forest should be preserved and protected from additional pressures, such as pollution or habitat destruction. In the future, these areas could serve as critical refugia for restoration initiatives as well as natural recovery.

3.5 Oceanographic tipping points in the Northern Baltic Sea

The Baltic Sea is known to be heavily influenced by human activities eutrophication being a major problem, while also other human activities and climate change are inducing major additional stress for the ecosystem. The LS1, the Gulf of Bothnia in the northern part of the Baltic Sea has been until recently and partly still is a more oligotrophic area compared to the other large basins of the Baltic Sea. Anyhow, symptoms of eutrophication have become more apparent even there, especially during the last two decades. For example, extensive blooms of cyanobacteria occur annually during summer. It is important to understand the dynamics, trends and tipping points more profoundly in the ecosystem to support the recovery, management, and sustainable use of the marine ecosystem.

3.5.1 Hypothesis

The marine environment is at change due to global change and pressures from human activity. Changes in stratification of the water column, and in nutrient loads from land could influence the dynamics of the ecosystem. In specific, we aim to find out (1) if tipping points can be found in the time series of environmental variables and (2) how could trends in environmental factors influence the cyanobacterial blooms, and could there be tipping points in mechanisms contributing to the blooms?

3.5.2 Data

For the trend analyses, the compiled dataset included both Finnish data from the VESLA database maintained by the Finnish Environment Institute and the Swedish Sharkweb database. For the cyanobacterial bloom model development and sensitivity analysis in addition to monitoring data, information was extracted from the Copernicus Climate Change Services and from data acquired with automated sampling devices installed on commercial ships (Alg@line Ferry box) described in detail in the GES4SEAS Deliverable 5.2.

Pressures

Climatic variations and trends influence the hydrography of the water column including changes in the vertical temperature and salinity stratification. Human activities have increased the nutrient loads to the sea. Even if substantial efforts have been made to decrease loading, especially loads from agriculture continue to be a challenge for the management of the marine environment.

Data structure

The area covered by the current study encompasses the basins known as the northern Baltic Proper, the Åland Sea and the Bothnian Sea (Figure 3.39).

Figure 3.39. The locations of the target areas in the northern Baltic proper (BP1), the Åland Sea (ÅS2), and the Bothnian Sea (BS1, BS2, BS3).

From this area, since about 1980 monitoring data on water quality has been sampled with several monitoring cruises annually. Two seasonal (January to March, and June to August) datasets both

above the halocline 0-40 m and below halocline (70-120 m) were included. So, from each variable (Table 3.12) four timeseries were produced covering 44-year (1980-2023).

Table 3.12. The analysed water quality variables.

Variable	Abbreviation	Unit
Temperature	TEMP	°C
Secchi depth	SECHHI	m
Salinity	SAL	PSU
Total phosphorus concentration	PTOT	mmol m ⁻³
Total nitrogen concentration	NTOT	mmol m ⁻³
Phosphate concentration	PO4P	mmol m ⁻³
Nitrite and nitrate nitrogen concentration	NO23N	mmol m ⁻³
Ammonium concentration	NH4N	mmol m ⁻³
Dissolved oxygen concentration	O2D	Concentration compared to the 100% saturation
pH	pH	
Silicon dioxide concentration	SiO2	mmol m ⁻³
Chlorophyll a concentration	CP	mg m ⁻³

Analyses applied

Variables of interest

The wintertime and summertime deep layer analyses included ten variables: salinity, temperature, phosphate, nitrate and nitrite, ammonium, oxygen, pH, total nitrogen, total phosphorus, and silica. The summertime shallow water layer variables included additionally water transparency and chlorophyll-a (Table 3.12). All the variables were analysed in five areas from 1980 to 2023 (Figure 3.39).

Trends and tipping points in water quality

The time series were analyzed with the R package EnvChp version 1.1.3 (Killick et al. Detection of Structural Changes in Climate and Environment Time Series, <https://github.com/rkillick/EnvCpt/>). In EnvChp, there are 12 different methods to analyse a single-variable time series. To find the best model, BIC (Bayesian information criterion) or AIC (Akaike information criterion) can be applied. For purposes of detection of regime changes and tipping points, all 12 methods were not considered applicable, but for consistency as well as to support comparison and interpretation of trends the change point

method was applied. This method aims to find the time instances when significant changes in the trends in time series take place. After the change point estimates were extracted, a linear regression was fitted between each pair of change point years and the 95% confidence bands of the regression segments were computed. Figures were produced to show the time series data with the segmented regression models, including 95% confidence bands for the slopes.

Tipping points in cyanobacterial blooms

We applied machine learning to find out how different environmental factors could influence the cyanobacterial biomass during summer (June, July, August) and to explore if there could be tipping points in the variables controlling the bloom development. The methods applied for cyanobacterial bloom forecasting in the LS1 have been explained in more detail the *GES4SEAS Deliverable 5.2*. Therefore, only a brief description of the methodologies is given here.

Spatial composites of annual satellite datasets on phytoplankton surface blooms have been made in the Finnish Environment Institute in the years 2003-2024 (<https://tarkka.syke.fi/eo-tarkka/?ver=0&lang=en>). In these the phytoplankton biomass is represented in four categories. The material from 2003-2023 was used as learning data in bloom model development. The explanatory variables in this study included longitude, latitude, concentrations of dissolved nitrogen and phosphorus, average air temperature in May, and year. The water quality data was composed from monitoring data and from Ferry box material collected with automatic instruments installed on commercial cargo and passenger ships. Air temperature data consisting of reanalysis data for spring and summer 2003-2023 and forecast data for summer 2024 were obtained from the Copernicus Climate Change Services (<https://climate.copernicus.eu/>).

It was reasoned that decision-tree methods which are in principle well suited for categorical data, would be applicable in this classification modelling study as the response data for in four bloom biomass categories, whereby we selected random forest (RF) for this task. The RF model was fitted with the R package caret (<https://topepo.github.io/caret/>). Sensitivity of the developed random forest bloom model was tested by exploring the responses in bloom risk forecasts produced by inducing changes in nutrient concentrations. Model forecasts were run by inducing gradual changes in both nutrients in the range of -50 to +50% (a square matrix with dimension 21*21) compared with the concentrations in winter 2024. The results of the sensitivity analysis were visualized with response surface type plots. In this deliverable the sensitivity analysis is represented for the central Bothnian Sea where a substantial increase in phytoplankton biomass has taken place since the year 2003.

3.5.2 Results and interpretation

Most remarkable changes occurred in deeper water layer (70-120 m) **temperatures** in all subareas with a consistent rising trend of c. 2 °C during the four decades (Figure 3.40). Also winter temperatures in the 0-40 m layer increased consistently being close to 0 °C in the beginning of the time series when the basins were ice-covered while summertime temperature changes in the 0-40 m layer were not as consistent but still rising in general.

Oxygen concentrations were decreasing in deep water even if first some increasing trends were apparent during 1980's. The concentrations in the deeper layer in the Baltic proper are approaching zero whereby concomitant changes are taking place in nutrient concentrations (see below). In the deeper layer in other areas oxygen saturation is still mostly > 50%, but concentrations are decreasing.

Salinity is an important factor influencing e.g., the vertical mixing and further on the dynamics of several water quality variables. In all subareas, salinity was steadily decreasing until early 1990's when a clear turn in the trend occurred in all subareas and seasons. Thereafter a clearly increasing trend prevailed in deep water and slightly increasing or stable level in the shallow layer.

In **pH** the general pattern was a slightly decreasing trend around 0.2 pH units in 44 years.

The **nutrient** concentration time series exhibited trends and tipping points. The time series of PO4P and PTOT were very similar in winter, but they were on different level in summer even if showing coherent trends. The tipping points in the phosphorus were found mostly in different years of 1990's and thereafter a steep increase in concentrations occurred.

Total nitrogen concentration indicates mixed trends: in most areas they first increased in 1980-1990's and then declined after a tipping point, while elsewhere they indicate a long decline in 1990-2000. All the areas indicate either a stable situation or a slight increase after decline (i.e. a tipping point).

Nitrate/nitrite (NO₂3N) has a clear tipping point only in the Baltic Proper, where a steep decline took place after 1999-2000. Elsewhere the concentration has either been stable or slightly increased.

NH₄N concentration was almost always very low and often approaching the detection threshold. This nutrient species has had 2-4 tipping points since 1980's in the Bothnian Sea and Archipelago Sea. In the Baltic Proper, passing a tipping point in 2000 leads to increasing concentration the trend being opposite than with the oxidized forms of nitrogen, caused by the wide hypoxia of the area.

The trends in **SiO₂** resemble those of the phosphorus species.

Figure 3.40. Time series of the oceanographic variables in the five target areas BP1, AA2 and BS1,2,3. The data are from the winter months (January, February, March) from 70-120 m depth. Linear regression segments with their 95% confidence bands are shown with blue lines and vertical dashed lines indicate the instances when significant changes in trends occurred.

Water transparency (Secchi depth) slightly improved in the Bothnian Sea but steeply decreased in the Baltic Proper. The latter is easy to understand as a result of the wide cyanobacterial blooms, but surprisingly the in situ-observations of the Secchi depth in the other areas do not show the increased blooms, which are visible in satellite-based monitoring.

Phytoplankton **chlorophyll-a** (CP) concentrations indicated quite large variability within the in situ-data series in the study areas. The Baltic Proper trend is increasing, negatively correlating with the water transparency. Elsewhere the analysis is less reliable.

Predicting tipping points in the cyanobacterial bloom intensity

The bloom model predicted intensity of the cyanobacterial blooms in the selected area in the study period 2003-2024. Figure 3.41 shows how the model estimates on bloom intensities depend on dissolved phosphorus and dissolved nitrogen in the winter samples in surface waters. However, the bloom risks are instead becoming larger which is indicated by the annual averages in Figure 3.41 as most of the recent years are on the right-hand side of the graph in the red area where the bloom risk is on the highest level. Ordering the model forecasts along a phosphorus gradient (phosphorus being the limiting nutrient), gives a sigmoid response curve clearly indicating the threshold of total phosphorus concentration where the blooms start to intensify. Figure 3.41 could be used to estimate how much (%) total phosphorus should be reduced from the surface waters to have weaker blooms. Circa 20% reduction would be sufficient to have low-moderate blooms. It is good to note that this response function depends on the area, and it is likely that a less clear threshold could be found in the Baltic Proper, where the sediment-bound phosphorus reserves maintain the blooms.

Figure 3.41. Forecasts of average risk level of cyanobacterial blooms as a function of DIN and DIP concentrations in a selected area in the southern Bothnian Sea (insert map). RF model forecasts were run by inducing changes in both nutrients in the range of -50 to +50% compared with the concentrations in winter 2024 (the white dashed lines at 100% level). The numbers in the white rectangles show the average concentrations of nutrients in the selected area in the years 2003-2024 in relative scale compared to concentrations in winter 2024. The panel on the right shows the bloom level forecast as a function of phosphate concentration compared to the winter 2024 level.

3.5.3 Discussion and further work

The Baltic Sea is a large brackish water basin with substantial spatial gradients and seasonal variations in biogeochemical characteristics. Salinity of the basin is influenced by variations in saline water inflow through the Danish straits connecting the Baltic Sea to the North Sea. Saline water inflow events into the Baltic Sea take place sporadically, but there have been multiannual fluctuations (data in Major Baltic Inflow statistics – IOW, Mohrholz 2018). The inflowing saline water usually flows under the less saline Baltic Sea water inducing a permanent halocline which delimits mixing of the whole water column. Thus, oxygen is soon depleted from the deeper layer leading to large anoxic areas and anoxic conditions will prevail in deep water until new sufficiently large saline water inflow event occurs.

The LS1, the Gulf of Bothnia, is connected to the Baltic main basin in the south. In the middle of this connection is the main island of Åland. To the east of Åland is the Archipelago Sea with a mean depth of 19 m. On the western side is the deeper Åland Sea, but even there a shallow sill with 45 m depth delimiting saline water inflow in deep water layer to the north. As a result of delimited inflow of saline water and substantial freshwater input from rivers, the salinity is lower and vertical stratification of the water column is weaker in the Bothnian Sea than in the Baltic main basin.

The analyses in this study indicate clear trends and tipping points in salinity data. The salinity tipping points in the early 1990's coincided with the dynamics of saline water inflow to the Baltic Sea via the Danish straits. During the 1980's the time series of anomalies of inflows were below average for 1970-2023 (Figure 3.42., data from Major Baltic Inflow statistics - IOW) which was likely to contribute to the decreasing salinity in the northern Baltic Sea including the Gulf of Bothnia until from the year 1980 to early 1990's. Thereafter, until about 2017 the smoothed timeseries indicates inflows on average or above average level. There were also variations in the annual river discharge and nutrient loads to the Gulf of Bothnia during the evaluated period of over four decades (unpublished data). But there was not any specific trend in river discharge during e.g., 1980's when the drop in salinity occurred.

Figure 3.42. Anomaly time series (relying on information from Major Baltic Inflow statistics – IOW) of the saline water inflow to the Baltic Sea (dark bars) and a smoothed time series with a loess regression (blue) showing the periods of lower and higher inflows.

3.6 Understanding tipping points in data-poor regions: example from the Deep Sea

3.6.1 Hypothesis

Environmental changes caused by climate change and human activities might impact the stability of methane gas hydrates in the deep sea, potentially resulting in changes to the diversity and abundance of deep-sea chemosynthetic fauna.

The Leaning Site 5 (Deep Atlantic-Mediterranean transition) hosts numerous mud volcanoes (Figure 3.43) inhabited by chemosynthetic-based communities, including bivalves and tubeworms (Génio et al., 2013; Vanreusel et al., 2009). Mud volcanoes are geological features where over pressurized sediment seeps through the seafloor of mud and fluids. This process often results in the gradual releases gas, such as methane, which serves as a source for chemosynthesis (Rodrigues et al., 2013). These gases can originate from either the biological decomposition of organic matter in shallow sediments or the migration of thermogenic gas from deeper hydrocarbon reservoirs (gas hydrates).

The high pressure and low temperature conditions in the deep sea maintain gases such as methane in their solid form as gas hydrates. Changes in these conditions due to climate change are likely to destabilize gas hydrates (Magalhaes et al., 2019), potentially releasing large quantities of fossil carbon into the ocean and disrupting chemosynthetic communities. Additionally, human activities, such as deep-sea trawling, may impact the seafloor and enhance methane release. The extent of these activities remains unclear but might pose a substantial threat to deep-sea biodiversity.

Figure 3.43. Location of Learning Site 5 (Deep Atlantic-Mediterranean transition, black polygon), in the Gulf of Cadiz, and the mud volcanoes recorded in the area (red dots).

This case study proposed to identify and predict early warning signs of potential tipping points in deep-sea chemosynthetic communities resulting from an increase in gas release, namely by assessing:

- **Specific Question 1:** How raising sea bottom temperature will affect the amount of gas release and consequently impact the chemosynthetic communities
- **Specific Question 2:** To what extent does bottom trawling fishing impact deeper gas hydrate reservoirs, increase gas releases, and consequently affect chemosynthetic communities?

3.6.2 Data

Data on biodiversity, climate change, and methane gas hydrate stability were compiled from available sources. However, the information is limited, particularly regarding biological data (Table 3.13).

Data structure

The original spatial datasets consist of point shapefiles (mud volcanoes) and raster files (human activities, pressures). The data regarding chemosynthetic communities is presented in a taxonomic list, with information on the species presence for some mud volcanoes.

Data on sea bottom temperature change was readily available for analysis from the original source.

Table 3.13. Data source for deep sea case study

	Ecosystem components	MSFD descriptor	MSFD Criteria	Pressure	Human Activity
1	Mud Volcanoes - EMODnet: https://www.emodnet-geology.eu/products/wp6/events_and_probabilities.zip			Climate change: https://www.bio-oracle.org/	Global Fishing Watch: https://globalfishingwatch.org
2	Mud Volcanoes – Data provided by Vitor Magalhães – Instituto Português do Mar e da Atmosfera (IPMA): vitor.magalhaes@ipma.pt				
	Biological Chemosynthetic communities - Species list: https://ria.ua.pt/handle/10773/981				

The data extracted from Global Fishing Watch was provided in a .csv text file format, with spatial information (longitude, latitude, fishing effort expressed as number of hours on fishing). These files required pre-processing to generate the raster file representing intensity of trawling fishing (number of fishing hours within a grid cell) along the LS5.

Analyses applied

It was not possible to conduct an analysis on tipping points for LS5 due to the lack of suitable data. More details are provided in the next section.

3.6.3 Results and interpretation

The lack of biological information on the tolerance limits of chemosynthetic communities to increasing levels of dissolved gases like methane in water and their impact on organism's metabolism prevents further analysis. Most of the species identified in mud volcano communities are relatively new discoveries, and only taxonomic studies have been conducted. Moreover, the absence of baseline data and time series on faunal composition and gas release rates from mud volcanoes hinders the identification of temporal trends and potential tipping points. Regarding the occurrence of gas hydrates, currently, only information on the location of mud volcanoes (point data) is available. No information is available on the spatial extent of gas hydrate reservoirs to assess the potential impact of bottom trawling.

Data limitations and a poor understanding of ecological processes in most deep-sea ecosystems present a significant obstacle to assessing tipping points within these communities. Consequently,

continuous and comprehensive studies are essential to define reference conditions, monitor ecosystem changes, and develop effective management and conservation actions that aim to prevent or mitigate ecosystem tipping points.

3.7 Contamination on benthos around oil platforms in the North Sea

The North Sea hosts a particularly high density of oil and gas platforms (> 500 platforms) and with many structures nearing end of life and potential decommissioning operations commencing, there is an urgent need to understand past and on-going effects of associated contamination on the environment. Here, in a North Sea wide study, we use benthic fauna and chemical data from industry-based monitoring surveys to address this need using a range of benthic functional groups associated with an existing widely accepted food web model of the North Sea (Ecopath).

3.7.1 Hypothesis

Main: the biomass of marine benthic fauna is reduced due to pollution from multiple contaminants around oil and gas infrastructure.

Specific question 1. Are differing functional groups of benthic fauna impacted to a different extent by the cumulative impact of multiple contaminants?

Specific question 2. Does the biomass of specific benthic faunal groups increase with distance from polluted sites up to the level seen in reference sites beyond the impact zone.

3.7.2 Data

Oil and gas platform, chemical and fauna data preparation

The data for chemicals and biota were sourced from the UK Oil and Gas industry from the online database (Table 3.14). The UKbenthos database contains entries from >700 surveys between 1975 and 2015 and data were extracted for 236 man-made structures. Benthic species data were retained for quantitative gears from which density estimates could be made, i.e. mini Hamon, Day and Van Veen grabs and box corers - data from trawls, scuba and dredge approaches were excluded. Specifically, survey metadata, environmental parameters and faunal information were extracted from the dataset. As part of the quality control step, the data were checked for consistent spelling and revised to accommodate taxonomic changes. Furthermore, empty records or those without metadata

were removed. Data were retained from samples taken up to 1,500 m from the structures only to minimize the potential changes in environment along gradients within sample transects.

Table 3.14. Data source for benthos contamination case study

	Ecosystem components	MSFD descriptor	MSFD Criteria	Pressure	Human Activity
1	Benthic infauna and epifauna	D8 Contamination	D8C2	Contamination	Energy extraction: The Offshore Oil & Gas U.K. Database of Offshore Environmental Survey (UKbenthos Version 5.18; Available at: https://oeuk.org.uk/publications-resources/).

The faunal abundance values were standardized at sampling station level by taking an average of replicates where multiple existed (typically 3-5 replicates). As this study focuses on benthic invertebrates, data entries on fish, plants and pelagic species were removed. Data for species with names that had no match within WoRMS (<https://www.marinespecies.org/>) were removed, as were all records labelled “juvenile” to avoid possible noise due to recruitment events. Since the biological data contained abundance measurements only, data on average individual-body mass were used to derive species-level biomass estimates [g m^{-2}] for each sampling station.

Hydrocarbon and metal concentrations were extracted from the UKBenthos database, retaining records of normal alkane concentration (n-alkanes), high molecular-weight (mw) polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs with four or more aromatic rings and with mw of 202, 228, 252 and 276) and low molecular-weight (mw) polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (naphthalenes, mw 128), phenanthrenes (mw 178) and dibenzothiophenes (mw 184) from ultrasonication were retained along with Barium, (Ba), Cadmium (Cd), Chromium (Cr), Iron (Fe), Nickel (Ni), Lead (Pb), Vanadium (VA) and Zinc (Zn). Any negative records (indicating low values less than the minimum detectable) were set to half the minimum non-zero record for the specific hydrocarbon or metal. All records were subsequently log-transformed to normalize the distribution of values and a visual inspection confirmed typically higher values within 250 m of structures relative to values from 250-1500 m distant.

From the selected chemical sample dataset (1,759 records), Total hydrocarbon (THC) concentration in sediment, determined by gas chromatography, was most frequently reported (72% of records from 199 platforms). THC values of ≤ 0.01 ($\mu\text{g/g}$) are at the limit of detection of many instruments so these values were set to 0 in subsequent analysis and samples with missing THC records were excluded from further analysis, following Chen et al. (2024). For other aromatic hydrocarbon compounds, there was a lower quantity of data (62 to 69% of records), but data on metals were more frequently recorded for some elements i.e. chromium, nickel, lead and zinc (76 to 79%).

THC concentrations in the sediment correlate with a range of specific petroleum products (here the correlation coefficients (R) between THC and other metrics range from R=0.2 for PAH with mw 276, R=0.3 for PAH with mw 252 and zinc, R=0.4 for PAH with mw 202 and mw 228, R=0.5 for naphthalenes, phenanthrenes and dibenzothiophenes) and, as THC is considered a screening tool for presence of petroleum products, we use THC values as a simple proxy for the total loading on sediments. THC is more frequently reported in the dataset than any other chemical measure, so we model the depletion of THC levels with distance from platforms within clusters and investigate the relationship between THC and the biomass of benthic groups

Environment data and clustering of structures

Environmental information relating to sediment type per platform was available within the database (MD0: median grain size in phi units; Mud: Silt/Clay content, percentage by weight of the sub 63 μm fraction of the sediment; OM: percentage of organic content of the sediment by weight) for each study were extracted from the database. Water depth, average bottom current and distance to coast were estimated from available GIS models (Mitchell et al., 2019). Environmental data were scaled (z-transformation) before performing a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to characterize the physico-chemical context of each platform for which biological information is available. K-means partitioning (Oksanen et al., 2022) was then performed on the PCA outputs to create clusters of platforms within which we can consider environmental contexts consistent. The maximum of “Simple Structure Index” (Oksanen et al., 2022) was used to identify the best number of clusters. Finally, sampling stations relating to each platform and containing the biological information and chemical values were aggregated per cluster and ordered according to distance (in m) from the structure.

Functional grouping of fauna

Mackinson and Daskalov (2007) defined functional groupings for benthic fauna whose component species are considered to have similar body sizes and share similar habitat and dietary requirements (See supplementary material). These groupings were subsequently used in the “key-run” of the North Sea Ecopath with Ecosim model (ICES, 2016) and subsequently by Mackinson et al. (2018). The infaunal groups consist of the following (Mackinson and Daskalov, 2007): “Infaunal macrobenthos”, “Small infauna”. Infaunal macrobenthos are generally composed of burrowing brittle stars such as *Amphiura filiformis*, bivalves (e.g., *Arctica islandica*) and gastropods larger than 2 mm (such as cockles (*Cardium* sp.) and whelks (*Buccinum* sp.). Small infauna are mostly comprised of polychaetes (such as *Capitella capitata*, *Myriochele* spp. and *Nephtys cirrosa*) and small crustaceans that live in the sediment. The epifaunal groups (Mackinson and Daskalov, 2007) consist of “Epifaunal macrobenthos” (e.g., sea snails such as *Euspira* spp., sea urchins, small crabs, gastropods, scallops) and “sessile epifauna” (including

Sabellidae, anemones, sponges, tunicates, bryozoans, barnacles (e.g., *Balanus* spp.), and attached bivalves such as mussels and oysters), “small mobile epifaunal” (including mysids, gammarids and amphipods). Meiofauna, *Nephrops* sp., shrimps and large crabs (including European lobsters and edible crabs) are grouped separately given their particular importance in fisheries in the North Sea, but the sample data used here are considered not reliable for these groups and they are not analysed further.

The estimated biomass for each functional group (small infauna, small mobile epifauna, infaunal macrobenthos, epifaunal macrobenthos, sessile epifauna) was summed for each station and by functional group. Any taxa not identified within these functional group were classed as “other”, and not considered further. Biomass estimates by functional group were then averaged across samples per sampling station retaining distance from nearest platform and year of sampling. Benthic biomass data by functional group were non-normally distributed, so data were transformed prior to statistical modelling using 4th root transformations for each group other than sessile epifauna for which an 8th root transformation was used.

Analyses applied

All analyses were conducted in the ‘R’ software (R Core Team, 2022) ver. 4.3.1. Initial analyses were conducted to determine if the biomass of each functional group and the concentration of each chemical differed between the clusters of platforms using an analysis of variance model with “cluster” as a factor and a Gaussian error term (cluster was a significant effect for each, not shown). For the cluster to the west of the Northern Isles (Orkney and Shetland Isles), the maximum sampled level of each chemical measure was low, with background values of hydrocarbons recorded only, so this cluster was excluded from further statistical analysis.

Initial analyses investigated whether data on chemical contaminants differed by distance from structures, through a comparison of the average of samples values within <250m of the structure and between 250m and 1500m, using Welch’s 2-sample *t*-tests to identify significant differences and through graphing of the data. Non-linear patterns of change with distance from platforms that differed between clusters were evident in the data on the concentrations of each chemical and on the biomass of benthic groups. So, data were modelled using Generalized Additive Models and Generalized Additive Mixed Models (Wood, 2004) fitted to the response data using R functions “gam” and “gamm” in package “mgcv” (Wood, 2017). In the mixed models, random intercepts were included per cluster and site grouping alongside the fixed effects. For chemical concentrations, the fixed effects were modelled with a two-dimensional non-linear penalized tensor product spline of distance and sample

year. For biomass data, the fixed effects were modelled with a one-dimensional spline, of total hydrocarbon concentration, with year as a factor. AIC scores were used to compare the performance of GAMMs with simpler GAMs.

From these models, we also identify general thresholds by estimating levels of contamination associated with a decline in biomass. To do so, we estimate the fixed effects of total hydrocarbon concentration (with standard error) on the biomass of each group, with random effects of cluster and site set to zero. The level of biomass depletion is determined relative to the modelled estimate of biomass at a low total hydrocarbon concentration level (10 ppm, Chen et al 2024) in which biomass is expected to be unimpacted (the estimates at 0 ppm were not used due to the increased uncertainty at the extreme values of fitted GAMs and GAMMs). We set the impact-onset threshold per functional group to be the minimum value of contaminant at which the upper estimate of biomass (from the 95% CI) is found to be equal to the minimum estimate of unimpacted biomass (from the 95% CI of biomass at 10 ppm THC). In addition, we identify total hydrocarbon concentration levels associated with a modelled 50% biomass depletion per functional group and cluster.

3.7.3 Results and interpretation

Five clusters of platforms were distinguished based on the common environmental conditions (e.g., depth, sediment grain size but not contaminant data) surrounding them (Figure 3.44). Platforms in Cluster 1 are in a geographically small area in the northern North Sea characterized by low current flow, high mud and carbon content, but with a high median grain size. The environment of Cluster 2 has no features with particularly high or low values and is thus considered the base cluster and platforms in this cluster are distributed throughout the North Sea. Platforms in Cluster 3 are located west of the Northern Isles and this cluster is sited in the greatest water depth. Cluster 4 is intermediate between clusters 1 and 2 with platforms in the northern North Sea. Cluster 5 in the southern North Sea and platforms are sited in shallow waters with high current flow. The biomasses of each functional group and the chemical concentrations in sediments were found to be significantly different (all $p < 0.001$) between the five clusters based on an analysis of variance. Furthermore, the chemical concentrations in sediments (all measures) were significantly different from samples taken within 250 m of the platforms versus those samples between 250 and 1500 m distant in each cluster.

Figure 3.44. a) spatial location of clusters of platforms used in this study shown spatially. b) scatterplot of data coloured by clusters showing the main variables that discriminate between them split across the first two Principal Components (PC1 and PC2). c) the environmental variables that define the clusters, where the labels on the x-axes are: Current velocity of surrounding seawater, Depth of the seabed at the structure location, Distance of structure from nearest coast, MD0 is the median grain size, phi units, Mud is the percentage Silt/Clay content by weight of the sub 63 μm fraction of the sediment; OM: percentage organic content of the sediment.

The biomass of each functional group decreased as total hydrocarbon concentrations in the sediment increased (Figure 3.45). The model smooths were significant ($p < 0.001$) in each model for each functional group investigated. Normality plots of residuals and plots of the response vs fitted values were satisfactory. The decrease in biomasses of small mobile epifauna and small infauna begins at lower concentration values (at $< 100 \mu\text{g/g}$ total hydrocarbon concentration) than for other groups suggesting that these groups are most sensitive to contamination. In contrast, decreases in the biomass of epifaunal macrobenthos occurs at levels $> 1000 \mu\text{g/g}$ only and can be considered least sensitive to effects of contamination. Impact thresholds were established for each group relative to the expected biomass of each at a level of $10 \mu\text{g/g}$ total hydrocarbon concentration (Figure 3.45). For small infauna, small mobile infauna and sessile epifauna the impact thresholds were $< 100 \mu\text{g/g}$, while for Infaunal macrobenthos the threshold was $120 \mu\text{g/g}$ and for epifaunal macrobenthos $1395 \mu\text{g/g}$.

Figure 3.45 Modelled effects on the biomass [$g\ m^{-2}$] of functional groups of benthos due to cumulative effects of contaminants as measured by the total hydrocarbon concentration in the sediment. Fitted lines are coloured according to the clusters shown in Figure 3.44. Vertical lines are drawn at 10 µg/g (dotted grey) along with the impact-onset threshold (dashed black) and 50% impacted levels per group (coloured lines).

3.7.4 Discussion and further work

The benthic functional groupings were considered by Mackinson and Daskalov (2007) as relevant prey groupings for benthivorous predators given that their feeding modes are adapted to exploiting particular sized prey in particular habitats. Lynam et al. (2007) and Püts et al. (2023) used these groupings within Ecopath and Ecosim to model spatial responses to platforms. This means that the relationships between biomass and contaminant detected within the present work can more easily relate to a change in the wider food-web compared to a more conventional species-based approach. Prior expectation on changes in the affinity of benthic functional groups to platforms was assumed to be positive for epifaunal groups since they can benefit from additional hard substrate at and above the surface and this could outweigh the impact on biodiversity of construction and potential contamination during operation (Lynam et al., 2017; Püts et al., 2023). The results presented here challenge those assumptions and suggest there can be an impact at the seabed due to contamination on both infauna and epifauna, that may differ between body sizes, which extends beyond the immediate physical impact of the structure to an extent that depends on the environmental conditions. Our results for epifauna near oil and gas platforms do not exclude the possibility of higher biomass on the structure above the seabed, since the data investigated were from grab and core samples at the base and in the vicinity of the platforms and so are biased towards soft-bottom benthic fauna. Overall, our results suggest that smaller organisms of both infauna and epifauna are more sensitive to cumulative impacts of contamination from hydrocarbons than larger organisms. Our pooled dataset includes platforms that have been decommissioned and platforms that are still operating, but our results link benthic biomass levels to contamination in sediments measured concurrently.

It is widely accepted that while grab/core sampling methods suitably estimate the abundances of the smaller, sediment infaunal organisms (e.g., Rumohr, 2009) but are far less appropriate for estimating densities of the less abundant, larger epifaunal taxa. In our study, samples were grouped within the clusters, but temporal changes were not investigated specifically for each structure due to a lack of repeated sampling over time for each site. Therefore, we are not able to know at what stage of operation or macrofaunal recovery the data arise from, which is worthy of further study, so we recommend additional data on time since construction is added to the database. It is possible that the benthic communities are not stable and may continue to change over time, which is likely to contribute to the variability in the data. Nevertheless, our study conducted was able to detect strong patterns of change in biomass and hydrocarbon contamination that were highly significant.

We found THC in sediment samples in the deep waters west of the northern isles (cluster 3), were low at all distances from platforms ($< 100 \mu\text{g/g}$) and no significant impact on the biomass of benthic groups. Lower concentrations of THC in sediments (typically $< 1000 \mu\text{g/g}$) were also found in the south-western North Sea (cluster 5), relative to samples from clusters 1, 2 and 4, which is likely due to high tidal and storm driven current flows in the south-western North Sea that have led to a lack of extensive accumulations of cuttings material (Bakke et al., 2013). Furthermore, the finer particle size of sand in the hydrodynamically active area is likely to disperse any contamination level more rapidly than the muddier sediments of the other clusters (Owens et al., 1994).

Although the biomasses of many benthic groups were lower near to structures ($< 500\text{m}$) and at high contaminant concentrations (in clusters 1, 2 and 4), and contaminant levels were found to increase near to platforms, these depleted biomass levels could also be the result of the physical impacts from drilling and the construction phases. Furthermore, the level of toxicity of the hydrocarbons was not investigated. A potential impact on infauna by benthivorous predators, such as the highly abundant dab *Limanda limanda* (ICES, 2022), can also not be eliminated by this study. This is particularly the case within the safety zone ($< 500 \text{ m}$) in place around the platforms during active operation which prohibits fishing activities and as a de-facto MPA may allow prey species to increase and subsequently attract predators to the area. Fishery exclusion areas around active oil and gas sites will also prevent direct impact on the fauna and sediment. So, a trade-off in pressure from the presences of structures and associated contaminants and the lack of demersal trawling pressure (typically within 500 m) from the structure provides and added complexity to ecosystem responses. Therefore, drawing a simple mechanistic causal link between the observed faunal responses to platforms, is problematic due to several indirect, confounding factors. However, our use of a large, pooled dataset across the North Sea in different environmental conditions has found differences in THC levels that range over four orders of magnitude and greatly above natural levels.

The data contained within the Oil and Gas UK database may be used, as has been demonstrated here, to inform future decisions regarding the most suitable decommissioning options for a given platform. As we have shown, some platforms display elevated sediment THC concentrations in their vicinity and a resulting correlative link with the biomass of infaunal functional groups. However, to determine likely effects of contaminants on fauna it is important to know the amount of toxic hydrocarbon compounds that are present and the differing susceptibility of the various organisms to them (National Research Council, 2003). The decommissioning of these platforms (OSPAR, 2018) should explicitly consider this potential causal link and the potential for decommissioning to lead to the release of sediment-bound contaminants into the wider marine environment.

3.8 Relationships among North Sea ecosystem components, especially with respect to Harbour seals *Phoca vitulina*

3.8.1 Hypothesis

The North Sea has changed considerably over recent centuries (Quante et al., 2016). Human activities in the region have increased, including marine transport, oil and gas extraction, commercial fisheries, and pollution (Quante et al., 2016). For example, Mayk et al. (2022) analysed historical samples of dogwhelks *Nucella lapillus* from the North Sea to show that heavy metal, particularly lead, concentrations had increased proportionally with changes in leaded petrol consumption since the 1950s. Conversely, the environmental and ecological status of the region has decreased, as measured by loss of biodiversity, habitat, and ecosystem stability (Huthnance et al., 2016). For example, Dickey-Collas et al. (2010) estimated that North Sea herring *Clupea harengus* stocks had collapsed to under 95% of their pre-industrial levels between the 1950s and 1980s (although Cushing (1982) has previously described dramatic cyclical dynamics of herring in the English Channel). It is unlikely that these changes are driven primarily by top-down human activities or bottom-up environmental processes, but rather by their complex interplay involving feedback, temporal lags, and non-linear relationships (Lynam et al., 2017). Nevertheless, several studies have suggested that the net result of these changes is to reduce the ecological resilience of the North Sea, thereby increasing the likelihood that these changes lead to larger and more persistent ecosystem-level changes, known variously as ecological regime shifts, threshold changes, or tipping points (Folke et al., 2004).

As large and persistent changes to natural systems, and with potentially far-reaching implications for our use and understanding of them, tipping points have attracted considerable attention among scientists, managers, policymakers, and the public (Folke et al., 2004). For example, a special issue in the peer-reviewed scientific journal *Progress in Oceanography* was published in 2004 to present the theory and evidence for tipping points in oceans (deYoung et al., 2004; Steele, 2004). Among the themes emerging from that special issue, and many studies published since (Spencer et al., 2011; Dudley and Suding, 2020; Ban et al., 2022; Hillebrand et al., 2023; Selden et al., 2024; Haines et al., 2024), is that the theory underpinning the existence of tipping points is better developed than the empirical evidence to support it (deYoung et al., 2004; Steele, 2004). In other words, there are many issues associated with the detection of tipping points from noisy and incomplete data, and even more issues associated with understanding the causes of any detected tipping points. As is usually the case, in situ controlled experimental studies provide the best empirical evidence for the existence of tipping points. For example, Carrier-Belleau et al. (2023) studied the effects of manipulated levels of nutrient

enrichment and salinity on zebra mussel *Dreissena polymorpha* mortality and found evidence for a threshold in mortality with increasing stressor concentration, which was exacerbated by the second stressor. Unfortunately, extrapolating from such in situ experiments to real-World situations is complicated by interactions with myriad other stressors (Carrier-Belleau et al., 2022). Taken together with the logistical constraints associated with collecting consistent and high-quality data suitable to detect tipping points in situ, it is perhaps unsurprising that real-World examples of tipping points are few and uncertain.

According to Wooster and Zhang (2004), a founding empirical case of an oceanic tipping point was from the North Pacific where a marked shift in the Pacific Decadal Oscillation in the mid-1970s was associated with marked and sustained changes in ocean temperature and zooplankton abundance, which were later related to Pacific salmon *Oncorhynchus* spp. abundances. Since then, there have been many empirical studies seeking evidence of regime shifts in time-series data (see Hillebrand et al., 2023; Haines et al., 2024). Several studies have sought to provide evidence of a regime shift in the North Sea. Reid et al. (2001) provided evidence of a regime shift in fish stocks, specifically mackerel *Trachurus trachurus*, in 1988 driven by plankton dynamics in the North Sea, although they did not provide a formal statistical analysis. Solow and Beet (2005) presented a method for statistically assessing the existence of a regime shift and found weak but persuasive evidence of a regime shift in the same system around 1987. About the same time, Clark and Frid (2001) reviewed long-term data representing the ecology of the North Sea, from environmental variables through fish to seabirds, and concluded that the data showed evidence of both “bottom-up” and “top-down” regulations by different ecosystem components. A few years later, Beaugrand (2004) also reviewed evidence for regime shifts, especially in plankton, in the North Sea and suggested they occurred and were caused by environmental changes, as did Deschamps et al. (2024) more recently.

In this study, we seek to quantify empirical relationships driving changes in variables representing a wide range of ecosystem components in the North Sea. In doing this, we hope to identify variables that are associated with recent observed changes in the southern North Sea, especially increases in the number of Harbour seals *Phoca vitulina* described by Carter et al. (2022). We gather available data to derive variables representing major ecosystem components and propose hypothesised relationships between them in a graph. We explore these hypothesised relationships visually and statistically, considering each relationship in isolation, as well as part of a holistic set of simultaneous equations. We conclude with a discussion of the findings and perspectives on future work.

3.8.2 Data

For the purpose of our analysis, we split the Greater North Sea (OSPAR Region II) into “northern North Sea” and “southern North Sea” using the Level 2 definitions of the OSPAR 2017 Intermediate Assessment reporting units at <https://www.ospar.org/work-areas/cross-cutting-issues/intermediate-assessment-2017-resources> (Figure 3.46).

Figure 3.46: Map showing the division of the Great North Sea into “southern” and “northern” regions, as used in the OSPAR 2017 Intermediate Assessment.

The purpose of this work was to explore relationships between time-series of key components of the North Sea ecosystem, especially with regard to sudden and sustained changes in those relationships. The key components of the North Sea ecosystem considered were restricted to those for which we could find suitable time-series data or data-derived products and are listed along with their details and sources in Table 3.15.

Table 3.15: Ecosystem components represented in this analysis, along with their descriptions and sources.

Name	Ecosystem component	Functional group	Description	Source
Surface temperature	temperature	environment	Sea temperature at the surface ¹	https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.dcc9295c
Bottom oxygen	oxygen	environment	Dissolved oxygen concentration at the bottom ¹	https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.dcc9295c
Winter nutrients	nutrients	biochemistry	Ratio of dissolved inorganic nitrogen to phosphorus concentrations	Heyden and Leujak (2022)
Coldwater zooplankton	plankton	primary production	Abundance of cold-water zooplankton ²	https://doi.org/10.17031/65796de33e68d
Warmwater zooplankton	plankton	primary production	Abundance of warm-water zooplankton ²	https://doi.org/10.17031/65796de33e68d
Phytoplankton	plankton	primary production	Ratio of diatom to dinoflagellate abundances	https://doi.org/10.17031/65796de33e68d
Benthos	benthic	primary consumer	Shannon Weiner measure of benthic organism diversity	OneBenthic database (2025). Accessed via https://rconnect.cefas.co.uk/onebenthic_data_extractionrawl/ in January 2025
Small fishes	fishes	secondary consumer	Catches (kg/km ²) of fish <= 50 cms length ^{3,4}	https://doi.org/10.14466/CefasDataHub.126
Large fishes	fishes	tertiary consumer	Catches (kg/km ²) of fish > 50 cms length ^{3,4}	https://doi.org/10.14466/CefasDataHub.126
Diving seabirds	birds	tertiary consumer	Chicks recruited per diving adult seabird ²	European Seabirds At Sea (ESAS). Accessed via https://esas.ices.dk in January 2025
Seals	seals	tertiary consumer	Harbour seal abundance	Carter et al. (2022)
Fishers	fishers	tertiary consumer	Fishing effort	https://doi.org/10.14466/CefasDataHub.61

1 Modelled under the intermediate greenhouse gas emission (RCP 4.5) scenario.

2 Derived from species given in Table 3.17.

3 50cm cut-off chosen to match the OSPAR Large Fish Index for the Greater North Sea at <https://oap.ospar.org/en/ospar-assessments/quality-status-reports/qsr-2023/indicator-assessments/proportion-lfi/>.

4 Derived from the FutureMares project.

For each ecosystem component, we accessed the latest version of the data from the source identified, converted it to spatial vector where needed, partitioned it between the two North Sea subregions, visualised it, and then aggregated it to a representative time-series. An example of this process is provided in the Annex. These individual time-series were then aggregated into a final dataset Figure 3.47.

Figure 3.47: Time-series data extracted and collated to represent ecosystem components, and later used to derive variables for the statistical analysis. Points represent mean values and error bars are standard errors. Derived variables used only the means, i.e., the variations around the means were disregarded.

Before analysis, each time-series was explored visually and using summary statistics, and where needed they were transformed using appropriate mathematical functions to better approximate a Gaussian distributed variable (Figure 3.48). Specifically, the time-series for “diving birds” was natural log transformed. Although there were some values in some time-series that appeared outlying, i.e., of a value regarded as substantially different from other values in the time-series, they were not removed because we sought evidence of sudden and sustained ecosystem changes that could be characterised by such values. Finally, we z-standardised all variables prior to analysis in the dynamic structural equation models (DSEM) to encourage stable and identifiable parameter estimates, i.e., by ensuring that their variances were similar.

We use DSEM to estimate the strength and statistical significance of relationships between our chosen North Sea ecosystem components (Thorson et al., 2024) (Table 3.15). A structural equation model (SEM) can be defined as a set of causal equations representing linear relationships between variables in the same time-step (Grace 2006). An extension to SEM, known as dynamic SEM (DSEM), allows variables to affect others in a different time-step, i.e., with a temporal lag (Asparouhov et al., 2018). We chose to use DSEM as implemented in the R package dsem (Thorson et al., 2024) because (1) it estimates direct, indirect, and total effects among variables, including simultaneous and lagged effects and recursive (cyclic) dependencies; (2) it fits rapidly as a Gaussian Markov random field in a Generalized Linear Mixed Model; and (3) it allows granular control over the number of parameters

(and restrictions on parameters) used to structure the covariance among variables and over time (Thorson et al., 2024).

Figure 3.48: Histograms of each untransformed variable to show the distribution of their values relative to the overlaid Gaussian density (red line). Note that “diving seabirds” was considered improved by natural log transformation; all other variables remained untransformed.

Our interest was primarily to explore whether changes in the southern North Sea ecosystem, as measured by our ecosystem components (Table 3.15), might be associated with changes in Harbour seal abundance indices in the southern North Sea described by Carter et al. (2022). To represent our hypothesised relationships, we present our DSEM as a graph (also known as a path diagram or causal map) with variables (also known as nodes) representing ecosystem components and paths (also known as edges) representing hypothesised relationships between them, as shown in Figure 3.49. Although most of the hypothesised relationships were between variables in the same year, known as a “simultaneous” effect (or lag 0 effects), others were hypothesised between a variable in year t and another in year $t+\Delta$, known as a “lagged” effect where $\Delta > 0$ is a number of years chosen to match the hypothesised relationship. For example, “small fishes” were hypothesised to affect “diving seabirds” productivity in year $t+1$, i.e., recruitment, whereas “fishers” were hypothesised to affect “small fishes” and “large fishes” in the same year, i.e., fishing mortality. Further, we classified our hypothesised relationships as either “bottom-up” regulation, representing environmental forcing or food availability, or “top-down” regulation, representing predation or density dependence.

Figure 3.49: Graph showing the hypothesised relationships (shown as paths) between ecosystem components (shown as variables). Dashed and solid paths represent “bottom-up” and “top-down” regulation, respectively, and black and blue paths represent simultaneous and lagged effects, respectively.

To explore the direction and strength for each hypothesised relationship in isolation, we plotted data representing the first ecosystem component against data representing the (possibly lagged) second ecosystem component and added a linear regression fit of the form $y \sim \alpha + \beta x$. We then estimated the path coefficients representing the same hypothesised relationships simultaneously using DSEM, in which hypothesised relationships affect one another, and that could be considered a more realistic approach than considering them in isolation.

Aside from estimating the path coefficients representing the hypothesised relationships between our ecosystem components, we also use the fitted DSEM to estimate the time-series for each ecosystem component. This allowed us to speculate about changes in those ecosystem components in periods when we do not have observations, such as for fish catches prior to 1998.

3.8.3 Results and interpretation

Estimation in isolation using linear regressions

Scatter plots of the first and (possibly lagged) second variables for each hypothesised relationship (or path) in the southern North Sea ecosystem revealed sometimes high variation in one or both variables (Figure 3.50).

Figure 3.50: Scatter plots with linear regression fits (blue lines) showing direction and strength of hypothesised relationships for ecosystem components when considering each relationship in isolation, i.e., not simultaneously as is done in DSEM.

For example, the “surface_temperature” and “coldwater_zooplankton” plot revealed two points measures of “coldwater_zooplankton” above 2.5 z-standardised units that were not well captured by a linear regression (shown as a blue line; Figure 3.49). The linear regressions showed that - when considered in isolation of other hypothesised relationships - relationships between the variables were often in line with expectations, albeit with variable strength. For example, “winter_nutrients” had an expected positive, albeit weak, relationship with “phytoplankton”. In some cases, however, the direction and strength of the hypothesised relationship suggested by the linear regression was unexpected. For example, “phytoplankton” had a strong negative relationship with “small_fishes” that was expected to be positive. For most hypothesised relationships, the variation explained by the linear regression was less than 20%; the most notable exception was the relationship between “large_fishes” and “seals” that was strong and positive and explained over 40% of the variation between those variables (Figure 3.50).

Simultaneous estimation using DSEM

Compared to estimates in isolation using linear regression, our DSEM estimates revealed similar results when considering all of the relationships simultaneously (Figure 3.51 and Table 3.16). Specifically, most of the strong hypothesised relationships found in isolation were also considered as strong relationships in the DSEM results. For example, the DSEM estimated a strong and positive relationship between “large_fishes” and “seals”, as had been found in the isolated linear regression and was expected. Some relationships estimated in isolation were not, however, estimated the same in the DSEM. For example, the hypothesised relationship between “small_fishes” and “seals” was weak and positive when estimated in isolation, as expected, but was strong and negative when estimated simultaneously (compare Figure 3.50 and Figure 3.51).

Overall, the DSEM estimates seemed to capture most of the hypothesised relationship in line with expectations. The DSEM estimated a variety of weak positive and negative “bottom-up” regulating relationships between environmental variables, biochemistry, and primary producers and consumers (Figure 3.51 and Table 3.16). For the most part, these were in line with expectations, except the strong negative relationships between “surface_temperature” and “warmwater_zooplankton” and “phytoplankton” and “small_fishes”, both of which were similar when estimated in isolation. Similarly, many of the “bottom-up” regulating relationships between secondary and tertiary consumers were in line with expectations, albeit that they were generally estimated as stronger relationships (Figure 3.51 and Table 3.16). The main exception here was the strong negative relationship estimated between “small_fishes” and “seals”, which was contrary to expectation and different from the relationship estimated in isolation. The only “top-down” regulating relationships were between “fishers” and

“small_fishes” and “large_fishes”, and these were estimated to be strong and negative, in line with expectations and the estimates in isolation.

Figure 3.51: Graph showing the estimated relationships between ecosystem components. Bold coefficient estimates are statistically significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

The variances for each variable were estimated to be approximately 1, as expected, with the exception of “seals” and “diving_seabirds”, which were estimated lower than expected at approximately 0.6 (Table 3.16).

Table 3.16: Path details with coefficient estimates, variable variances and their statistical significance.

Path	Type	Regulation	Lag	Estimate (s.e.)	z value	p value
surface temperature -> phytoplankton	Coefficient	bottom-up	0	0.018 (0.168)	0.105	0.916
surface temperature -> coldwater zooplankton	Coefficient	bottom-up	0	0.127 (0.166)	0.769	0.442
surface temperature -> warmwater zooplankton	Coefficient	bottom-up	0	-0.334 (0.153)	-2.193	0.028
bottom oxygen -> small fishes	Coefficient	bottom-up	0	-0.119 (0.201)	-0.594	0.553
bottom oxygen -> large fishes	Coefficient	bottom-up	0	-0.236 (0.167)	-1.412	0.158
winter nutrients -> phytoplankton	Coefficient	bottom-up	0	0.144 (0.180)	0.799	0.424
phytoplankton -> benthos	Coefficient	bottom-up	0	0.649 (0.210)	3.087	0.002
phytoplankton -> coldwater zooplankton	Coefficient	bottom-up	0	-0.077 (0.161)	-0.480	0.631
phytoplankton -> warmwater zooplankton	Coefficient	bottom-up	0	-0.242 (0.148)	-1.639	0.101
phytoplankton -> small fishes	Coefficient	bottom-up	0	-0.882 (0.246)	-3.581	0.000
coldwater zooplankton -> small fishes	Coefficient	bottom-up	0	0.086 (0.172)	0.500	0.617
warmwater zooplankton -> small fishes	Coefficient	bottom-up	0	0.915 (0.348)	2.631	0.009
small fishes -> large fishes	Coefficient	bottom-up	0	0.192 (0.151)	1.266	0.206
fishers -> small fishes	Coefficient	top-down	0	-0.384 (0.229)	-1.674	0.094
fishers -> large fishes	Coefficient	top-down	0	-0.657 (0.165)	-3.970	0.000
benthos -> small fishes	Coefficient	bottom-up	1	0.572 (0.292)	1.955	0.051
small fishes -> diving seabirds	Coefficient	bottom-up	1	0.528 (0.120)	4.393	0.000
small fishes -> seals	Coefficient	bottom-up	1	-0.371 (0.126)	-2.948	0.003
large fishes -> seals	Coefficient	bottom-up	1	0.726 (0.117)	6.195	0.000
surface temperature <-> surface temperature	Variance	—	0	0.988 (0.108)	9.165	0.000
phytoplankton <-> phytoplankton	Variance	—	0	0.976 (0.112)	8.681	0.000
coldwater zooplankton <-> coldwater zooplankton	Variance	—	0	0.977 (0.112)	8.718	0.000
warmwater zooplankton <-> warmwater zooplankton	Variance	—	0	0.899 (0.103)	8.718	0.000
bottom oxygen <-> bottom oxygen	Variance	—	0	0.988 (0.108)	9.165	0.000
small fishes <-> small fishes	Variance	—	0	0.862 (0.156)	5.534	0.000
large fishes <-> large fishes	Variance	—	0	0.709 (0.119)	5.975	0.000

Path	Type	Regulation	Lag	Estimate (s.e.)	z value	p value
winter nutrients <-> winter nutrients	Variance	—	0	0.989 (0.112)	8.802	0.000
benthos <-> benthos	Variance	—	0	0.849 (0.121)	7.012	0.000
fishers <-> fishers	Variance	—	0	0.967 (0.119)	8.122	0.000
diving seabirds <-> diving seabirds	Variance	—	0	0.563 (0.131)	4.308	0.000
seals <-> seals	Variance	—	0	0.580 (0.086)	6.712	0.000

Ecosystem component time-series in-filled with predictions from the DSEM suggested higher values of “benthos” and especially “small_fishes” and “seals” during the early part of the time-series, i.e., pre-2000 (Figure 3.52). Since the estimated relationships between these variables were not always in line with expectations, these suggestions warrant more consideration of these time-series in future work.

Figure 3.52: Time-series of the southern North Sea ecosystem components, including predicted values (with standard deviation bands) for missing years as estimated by the DSEM.

3.8.4 Discussion and further work

In this study, we explored the empirical evidence for hypothesised relationships between dynamics of ecosystem components of the southern North Sea. We were especially interested in recent changes

in the abundance of Harbour seals in the southern North Sea and whether they could be explained by combinations of “bottom-up” and “top-down” regulation of ecosystem components representing available foods, namely “small_fishes” and “large_fishes”, while allowing for possible temporally lagged effects. We explored our hypothesised relationships by estimating them in a dynamic structural equation model that allows for their simultaneous estimation while allowing for temporal lags (Thorson et al., 2024).

Our analyses suggest that an index of large fish abundance has a strong and positive “bottom-up” regulated relationship with an index of Harbour seals abundance, both of which seem to have increased since 2000. Interestingly, these changes since 2000 seem to correspond to a decrease of fishing effort since 2000, which was modelled as a “top-down” regulation on “large_fishes”. Other “bottom-up” regulating ecosystem components, from environmental variables to benthic organisms, are estimated to have indirect influences on large fish abundances, mainly through their influence on abundance of smaller fishes. Some of the estimated direct relationships among these variables were, however, in directions contrary to our expectations, as was the relationship between indices of small fish and seal abundances. The reason for these counter-intuitive results requires further work and could include misspecification of the relationship(s) or missing node(s) in the graph (see below), both of which could represent a shortcoming in our understanding of this system. Until the relationships are better understood and captured by our modelling, the reconstructed time series in Figure 3.52 should be interpreted with caution, and should we checked against other data sources (where possible) and other published exploring historical dynamics of these ecosystem components.

Although these analyses capture some of our understanding in southern North Sea ecosystem changes, particularly with respect to Harbour seal abundances, they also leave many questions unanswered. As with many such analyses, we tend to be restricted to explore relationships among variables for which representative data are available (Munch et al., 2022). To some extent, DSEMs can overcome this constraint by allowing inclusion of unobserved variables (represented by latent nodes) (Thorson et al., 2023). In this work, we can imagine several variables that were omitted, but that could be included as latent variables to provide a more complete understanding of the ecosystem. For example, Carter et al. (2022) speculated that grey seals *Halichoerus grypus* population changes might explain changes in Harbour seal populations as the two species are thought to be interspecific resource competitors. Furthermore, we made some strong simplifying assumptions about the lower trophic levels of the southern North Sea ecosystem, such as using a diatom:dinoflagellates ratio to represent phytoplankton (Table 3.17).

It is our opinion that DSEM has several advantages over alternative statistical models for ecosystem-level studies. Most notably, DSEM allows all hypothesised relationships between observed (and to a lesser extent unobserved) variables representing ecosystem components to be evaluated simultaneously thereby finding a holistic solution to the system of equations, rather than considering each equation in isolation (Grace, 2006). Our empirical investigation of isolated hypothesised relationships revealed some quantitative, and even qualitative, different estimates to those from DSEM. While the former estimates were sometimes more in line with expectations, we are inclined to promote the DSEM approach and consider any unexpected estimates to be an artifact of an incomplete specification of the system of equations (Thorson et al., 2024). Nevertheless, our current implementation of DSEM is somewhat restricted, most notably by only allowing hypothesised relationships to be linear: several authors have used approaches that better allow for non-linear relationships, including Lynam et al. (2017) who used threshold Generalised Additive Models (tGAMs) and Ban et al. (2022) who used machine-learning models, for example. Another potentially promising approach could be dynamic GAMs (dGAMs).

Perhaps due to its restriction to only linear relationships, our DSEM analysis does not provide unequivocal evidence of a tipping point or regime shift in the southern North Sea ecosystem over the period 1983-2024. Rather, it suggests that there has likely been a sustained increase in the abundance of Harbour seas in the region, which could be due to changes in stocks of large fishes, themselves caused by both “bottom-up” and “top-down” regulating processes, including environmental forcing, such as ocean warming, and anthropogenic activities, such as fishing effort, respectively (Spencer et al., 2011). For example, Capuzzo et al. (2018) described evidence of a sustained change in primary production in the North Sea over 25 years and speculated that it was associated with reductions in zooplankton and fish over the same period. Similarly, Devlin et al. (2023) described gradual changes in nutrient enrichment of the Greater North Sea (among other OSPAR areas) due, in part, to changes in the levels of phosphorus and nitrogen inputs.

Perspectives

While this study has provided some insights into southern North Sea ecosystem dynamics, there are several ways we feel that it could be improved. We list them here.

1. *Further consideration of the hypothesised relationships* A more exhaustive review of the published scientific literature on the North Sea ecosystem, together with a survey of experts, could lead to a more complete understanding of the (southern) North Sea ecosystem, and

lead to revised hypothesised relationships, including with different temporal lags and unobserved/unobservable variables.

2. *Improved data sources* Similarly, a more careful consideration of the data sources available to represent important North Sea ecosystem components. For example, Clare et al. (2017) modelled benthic organism distributions and abundances from survey data in this region, whereas we used the same data to create an index of their diversity through time; a better approach would be to update the work of Clare et al. (2017)] and use those data.
3. *Improved data treatment* We made minimal changes to the data used in these analyses, including admitting outlying values, assuming that they were realistic values of extraordinary events. A more careful treatment of such values could lead to quantitative, or even qualitative, differences in our results. Moreover, the variances estimated for some of the variables, notably birds and seals, was less than expected, perhaps highlighting the need to consider the data representing them more carefully, i.e., accounting for possible trends in their dynamics through time.
4. *Incorporating non-linear responses* Whether extending this implementation of DSEM of finding an alternative, more flexible alternative, it would be interesting - and potentially enlightening - to allow non-linear relationships between variables representing ecosystem components. This could be especially interesting when seeking evidence of tipping points or regime shifts.

Notwithstanding the above list of possible improvements, another consideration is the sensitivity of the system of equations to particular variables. Specifically, we suspect that the variable representing small fish abundances had a strong influence on the solutions of other equations in the system. This possibility should be investigated further.

3.8.5 Annex

Species table used to derive variables

Table 3.17: Table showing the species used in the derivation of some of the variables representing different components of the North Sea ecosystem.

Ecosystem component	Variable	Species name	Common name
plankton	Coldwater zooplankton	Calanus finmarchicus	Calanus finmarchicus

Ecosystem component	Variable	Species name	Common name
plankton	Warmwater zooplankton	Calanus helgolandicus	Calanus helgolandicus
plankton	Warmwater zooplankton	Acartia spp. (unidentified)	Acartia spp. (unidentified)
plankton	Warmwater zooplankton	Para-Pseudocalanus spp.	Para-Pseudocalanus spp.
plankton	Warmwater zooplankton	Temora longicornis	Temora longicornis
plankton	Phytoplankton	Total Diatoms	Diatoms
plankton	Phytoplankton	Total Dinoflagellates	Dinoflagellates
fishes	Small fishes	Gadus morhua	Atlantic cod
fishes	Small fishes	Melanogrammus aeglefinus	Haddock
fishes	Small fishes	Merlangius merlangus	Whiting
fishes	Small fishes	Pollachius virens	Pollock
fishes	Small fishes	Eutrigla gurnardus	Grey gurnard
fishes	Small fishes	Scyliorhinus canicula	Small-spotted catshark
fishes	Small fishes	Trisopterus esmarkii	Norway pout
fishes	Small fishes	Clupea harengus	Atlantic herring
fishes	Small fishes	Sprattus sprattus	European sprat
fishes	Small fishes	Trachurus trachurus	Horse mackerel
fishes	Small fishes	Scomber scombrus	Atlantic mackerel
fishes	Small fishes	Pleuronectes platessa	European plaice
fishes	Small fishes	Ammodytes marinus	Lesser sand eel
fishes	Small fishes	Micromesistius poutassou	Blue whiting
fishes	Small fishes	Limanda limanda	Common dab
fishes	Small fishes	Hippoglossoides platessoides	American plaice
fishes	Small fishes	Microstomus kitt	Lemon sole

Ecosystem component	Variable	Species name	Common name
fishes	Large fishes	Gadus morhua	Atlantic cod
fishes	Large fishes	Melanogrammus aeglefinus	Haddock
fishes	Large fishes	Merlangius merlangus	Whiting
fishes	Large fishes	Pollachius virens	Pollock
fishes	Large fishes	Eutrigla gurnardus	Grey gurnard
fishes	Large fishes	Scyliorhinus canicula	Small-spotted catshark
fishes	Large fishes	Trisopterus esmarkii	Norway pout
fishes	Large fishes	Clupea harengus	Atlantic herring
fishes	Large fishes	Sprattus sprattus	European sprat
fishes	Large fishes	Trachurus trachurus	Horse mackerel
fishes	Large fishes	Scomber scombrus	Atlantic mackerel
fishes	Large fishes	Pleuronectes platessa	European plaice
fishes	Large fishes	Ammodytes marinus	Lesser sand eel
fishes	Large fishes	Micromesistius poutassou	Blue whiting
fishes	Large fishes	Limanda limanda	Common dab
fishes	Large fishes	Hippoglossoides platessoides	American plaice
fishes	Large fishes	Microstomus kitt	Lemon sole
birds	Diving seabirds	Fratercula arctica	Atlantic puffin
birds	Diving seabirds	Morus bassanus	Northern gannet
birds	Diving seabirds	Uria aalge	Common guillemot
birds	Diving seabirds	Alca torda	Razorbill
birds	Diving seabirds	Phalacrocorax carbo	Great cormorant

Plots showing the data preparation

These plots show the data preparation process the chosen example of oxygen on the sea floor (denoted "bottom_oxygen").

3.9 Temporal shifts in open sea trophic guilds in the Bothnian Bay, Baltic Sea

3.9.1 Hypothesis

Main: Changes in the food web of the Bay of Bothnia food web are correlated with abiotic factors such as increased temperature.

Specific question 1. Has there been tipping points in abiotic or biotic variables in the Bay of Bothnia within the past decades?

Specific question 2. Has the food web dynamics changed within the Bay of Bothnia due to these changes?

Integrated ecosystem analyses are crucial for understanding changes in aquatic food webs and how their components interact under various pressures such as climate change and eutrophication. These analyses help manage environments and fisheries, which are essential to ensure continued ecosystem services from marine environments, such as food supply, ecosystem regulation, and carbon sequestration (Eero et al., 2021; Essington et al., 2014; Palumbi et al., 2009). Assessing food web status is challenging due to the complexity of marine systems (Nordström et al., 2020; Reusch et al., 2018; Eero et al., 2021) and limited monitoring capabilities (Tam et al., 2017).

The Baltic Sea is one of the world's most impacted seas. The semi-enclosed nature of the Baltic Sea, characterized by its lower salinity and nutrient-rich waters, creates a distinct environment that influences the structure and function of its food webs. Eutrophication (Carstensen et al., 2019), overfishing (Eero et al., 2023), and maritime activities pose significant threats, impacting food web dynamics and resilience. While a formal assessment of Baltic Sea food webs is lacking, qualitative assessments highlight the pervasive effects of these pressures (HELCOM, 2023; ICES, 2024).

The Bothnian Bay is the northernmost basin of the Baltic Sea separated from the Bothnian Sea by the shallow Quark area. It has a unique ecosystem influenced by freshwater and organic matter inflow from several rivers (Rolff and Elmgren, 2000; Kiljunen et al., 2020) and long ice-covered season (Vihma and Haapala, 2009). It is estimated that the effects of the climate change are first taken place in the north as both the temperatures and the river outflows are increasing. Understanding how trophic interactions within the Bothnian Bay respond to these challenges is crucial for effective conservation and management efforts in this sensitive region.

3.9.2 Data

Data structure: We collected environmental and biological data from offshore stations in the Bay of Bothnia, the northernmost basin of the Baltic Sea, from 1966 to 2023. The area was defined according to HELCOM offshore zone maps excluding coastal and transitional zones. This approach minimized the spatial variability found in coastal areas, influenced by varying nutrient inputs from terrestrial sources, wastewater, and industry (Kiljunen et al., 2020; Rolff and Elmgren, 2000; Vähätalo et al., 2011; Woodland and Secor, 2013). Only stations with a minimum of 10 years of data between 1966 and 2023 were included to ensure measurement consistency over time. Our analysis focused on biotic and chemical variables with the longest continuous records available under national monitoring schemes (Table 3.18). The study covered a total of 109 variables, focusing on food web dynamics. We analysed a 35-year time-series (1986-2020) due to consistent availability of trophic group data.

Table 3.18. Data source for open sea trophic guild case study

	Ecosystem components	MSFD descriptor	MSFD Criteria	Pressure	Human Activity
1	Trophic guilds: Phytoplankton Zooplankton, Benthic Predator Benthic Deposit Feeders, Planktivorous Fish, and Apex Predators	Descriptor 4: Food webs	D4C2 – Primary: The balance of total abundance between the trophic guilds is not adversely affected due to anthropogenic pressures.	Eutrophication, Climate change	

Data sources included databases from the Finnish Environmental Institute (SYKE), Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI), International Council for Exploration of the Sea (ICES), Leibniz Institute for Baltic Sea Research (IOWDB), and Helsinki Commission (HELCOM). Additional zooplankton data was sourced from the NOAA Copepod database. All data underwent quality control, involving expert consultation and verification against established datasets used in the third holistic assessment of the Baltic Sea (HELCOM, 2023).

Any pre-processing Missing data points were filled using mean values from data from two years prior and two years preceding the missing data point. All data was $\ln(y+1)$ transformed and normalized after transformation.

Analyses applied

Variables of interest (Table 3.19): We were interested in the changes within the food web and the abiotic factors influencing the change. Therefore, we gathered species level information of the trophic

levels. Grouping of the organisms was done based on MSFD trophic guilds (ref) and more relevant functional grouping based on documented ecological relationships. The used trophic guilds were phytoplankton (Chlorophyta, Diatoms, Cyanophyta, Dinophyta), Zooplankton (*Limnocalanus + Pseudocalanus+Temora + Eurytemora + Acartia+Bosmina +Eubosmina + Pleopis + Podon, Cercopagis*), Benthic Filterers (*Monoporeia affinis*), Benthic Predators (*Saduria entomon* and *Bylgides sarsi*), Benthic Deposit Feeders (*Macoma balthica, Marenzelleria* and Mysidae), Planktivorous Fish (Herring and Vendace) and Apex Predators (ringed seal and grey seal).

Table 3.19. List of variables used for analysing drivers of changes in trophic interactions.

General	Description	Months	Depth	Unit	Source
DIP	Winter means, nov-mars	Nov-Mar	0-10m	umol/l	sharkweb
Silicate	Winter means, nov-mars	Nov-Mar	0-10m	umol/l	sharkweb
DIN	Winter means, nov-mars sum of NH ₄ , NO ₃ , NO ₂	Nov-Mar	0-10m	umol/l	sharkweb
Ptot	data from Barbel			Kt P	
Ntot	data from Barbel			Kt N	
Benthos	Spring-summer	Apr-Jun		ind/m ²	Ices
Phytoplankton	Summer, jun-aug	Jun-Aug		biomass mg/l	ICES + Hertta
Zooplankton_bm	jun-aug	Jun-Sep	all depths	biomass mg/lm ³	Hertta, sharkweb
Secchi	jun-aug	Jun-Aug	NA	m	Hertta
SpSST	April-may sea-surface temperature	Apr-May	0-10m	degC	sharkweb
SuSST	Jun-aug SST	Jun-Aug	0-10m	degC	Hertta
SuSHT	Jun-aug hypolimnion temp	Dec-Feb	>100m	degC	Hertta
WSAL	Winter surface salinity	Dec-Feb	0-10m	psu	Hertta
WBSAL	Winter bottom salinity	Dec-Feb	>100 m	psu	Hertta
Oxygen	Bottom oxygen dec-feb	Dec-Feb	>100 m	ml/l	sharkweb
pH	Summer surface	Jun-Aug	0-10m	-	Hertta
WBSI	Winter Baltic Index			-	WIBIX19
WBSI3	Winter Baltic Index with 3-yr lag			-	WIBIX20
ICEKM	Whole Baltic extent of ice			1000 km ²	FMI
ICEKM3	Whole Baltic extent of ice with 3-yr lag			1000 km ²	FMI
Herr.SSB	herring spawning biomass			tonnes	ICES WGBFAS 2022
Vendace.SSB	Vendace spawning biomass			tonnes	ICES WGBFAS 2022
Seals	Mean of station counts may-jun then sum of stations			numbers	Shark
New_GreySeal	data by basin from Riikka			numbers	

For explanatory variables, we used a combination of data series to represent nutrient loading and climate change. Abiotic factors representing eutrophication were winter means (Dec-Feb) of surface

(0-10 m) silicate (Si), dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN) and phosphorus (DIP), bottom water (> 100 m) oxygen (Ox), and the DIN:DIP relationship to represent the Redfield ratio. Explanatory variables representing climatology and climate change were surface (0-10 m) spring (April-may) and summer (jun-aug) temperature (SpSST and SuSST, respectively), bottom (> 100 m) summer temperature (SuSHT), winter surface (0-10 m) and bottom (> 100 m) salinity (WSAL and WBSAL, respectively), summer surface pH and summer Secchi depth. The winter Baltic Sea climate index (WBSI) and the maximum extent of ice coverage (Ice) for the whole Baltic were used to indicate larger changes in climate over time (Hagen and Feistel, 2005).

Data transformation

Specific analyses We carried out the integrated trend analysis (ITA) using a combination of multivariate analyses, generalized additive models (GAMs) and segmented breakpoint analyses with the aim to assess how the diversity within, and balance between trophic guilds has changed over time in the BB in response to environmental and anthropogenic pressures.

3.9.3 Results and interpretation

The highest summer surface and bottom temperatures were measured 2011-2016 but the warming trend was not significant (Figure 3.53). For both, the standard deviation increased towards the end of the time series and break point analysis identified a breakpoint in 2010 for surface temperature and year after, 2011, for bottom temperature. For spring surface temperature, the trend was opposite, the temperature was decreasing at the beginning of the timeseries for period 1986-1999, where break point analysis identified a breakpoint. SpSST remain statistically stable for the two remaining decades, 2020-2020.

Winter salinities had both decreasing trends (Figure 3.53). The bottom salinity decreased between 1986-1990 at the rate of -0,8 psu/decade and had no trend thereafter whereas the surface salinity had first stable period 1986-1998 and decreased afterwards at the rate of -0.1 psu/decade. Both dissolved inorganic nutrients, phosphorus (DIP) and nitrogen (DIN) as well as silicate had breakpoints. For DIP they were in 1990 and 2012 since the period 1990-2012 was stable and concentrations increased before and after that period. For DIN, the breakpoints were a year after DIP breakpoints, in 1991 and. The DIN had decreasing trend over the whole period, but the variation increased significantly during each breakpoint. pH had a breakpoint in 1996, when standard deviation increased, and the increase eased.

Figure 3.53. Timeseries and segmented trend analysis of the explanatory variables. The red vertical lines mark the identified break points within the time series. Black crosses are annual values, blue line the segmented trend and green dashed lines the standard error of the indicated time segment. The red vertical lines mark the identified break points within the time series.

For explanatory variables Silicate, OX, Secchi, ICEKM, WBSI, Ntot and Ptot, there were no breaking points within the time series (Figure 3.53). Besides Ptot and OX with decreasing trend and Secchi and silicate with increasing trend they had no statistically significant trend during the study period. For trophic guilds, the analysis revealed several breakpoints (Figure 3.54). Both Phytoplankton and zooplankton had a breakpoint in 1992, when the variation in phytoplankton decreased and for zooplankton the increasing trend slowed down. For phytoplankton, there was decreasing trend for period 1986-2013 after which the trend was close to 0. For benthic deposit feeders, the analysis did not find a breakpoint, but the trend was increasing. Benthic filterers had a very varying behaviour over the study period. The break point analysis identified three breakpoints in 1995, in 2003 and in 2009. First, their amount was increasing until 1995 and then it decreased a lot until 2003 after which the decreasing trend slowed down, but the standard deviation increased and after 2009, the number of benthic filterers increased again with small variation. Benthic predator had increasing trend with one breakpoint in 2014, when both the trend and the standard deviation increased significantly. Planktivorous fish had highest numbers before year 1993 after which their number has fluctuated so

that the break point analysis identified three breakpoints in 1999, 2005 and 2011, where the trend has changed significantly. The seal number has increased throughout the study period. and the rate of change has doubled between the period before 1994 and after 2013.

Figure 3.54. Timeseries and segmented trend analysis of the trophic guilds. Black crosses are annual values, blue line the segmented trend and green dashed lines the standard error of the indicated time segment. The red vertical lines mark the identified break points within the time series.

The time trajectory for the PCO axes (Figure 3.55) shows changes in the relative abundances of guilds over time and suggests that until a relatively stable period until the year 1995 with a high abundance of planktivorous fish, benthic filtered zooplankton and phytoplankton total biomass, the abundances started to vary. The decade between 1996 and 2006 is a transition period. After 2007 the guild composition was again more stable with dominance of benthos and zooplankton. Since 2017, benthic predators, deposit feeders and apex predators (seals) are the dominant species.

Together, PCO1 and PCO2 axes explained c. 84.51% of the total variance in the data about trophic guilds (Figure 3.55). The PCO1 shows an almost monotonic increase during the four decades. Break points were detected in 1995, 2007 and 2017. The planktivorous fish aligned with PCO2, whereas total zooplankton, apex predator and benthic filterers aligned with PCO1 axis. The most influential explanatory variables include Secchi, pH, winter salinity (WSAL), winter bottom salinity (WBSAL), spring surface temperature (SpSST) and summer bottom temperature (SuSHT). Patterns of Secchi aligned with dynamics of benthic deposit feeders, and opposite to the benthic filterers. These two benthic groups showed opposite dynamics with each other, the deposit feeders increasing and the filterers decreasing. Increasing Secchi depth apparently is linked to decreasing phytoplankton biomass, which could also manifest itself in decreased sedimentation rate and decrease internal

loading, influence the resources for benthic filterers. The dynamics of benthic predators is perpendicular to benthic deposit feeders. The analyses support that SuSHT emerges as a factor influencing benthic predators. pH, SpSST and WBSAL align with the total phytoplankton and benthic filterers, but also with planktivorous fish. The WSAL aligns with zooplankton.

Figure 3.55. PCO analysis of trophic guilds and explanatory variables.

3.9.4 Discussion and further work

The Bothnian Bay has experienced a significant shift in its trophic structure over the past four decades. Early dominance by planktivorous fish was followed by a transition period (1996-2006) and then a resurgence of benthic communities, particularly deposit feeders and predators. Concurrently, seals have consistently increased in abundance.

Several environmental factors appear to influence these shifts. Decreasing Redfield ratio (DIN: DIP) indicates change from phosphorus limited conditions towards more favourable conditions for phytoplankton. This change is potentially linked to agricultural runoff, wastewater discharge, or

changes in atmospheric deposition. On the other hand, increasing Secchi depth (indicating clearer water) may correlate with reduced phytoplankton biomass, impacting the base of the food web and influencing both filter feeders and deposit feeders. Decreasing winter salinity trends might indicate changes in freshwater inputs from rivers or precipitation patterns. Increasing summer bottom temperatures (SuSHT) seem to favour benthic predators, potentially influencing their food sources and distribution.

Shifts in trophic structure can have cascading effects throughout the entire food web, potentially impacting species interactions and community stability. Understanding these trends is crucial for developing effective management strategies. This includes addressing nutrient pollution, managing freshwater inputs, and mitigating climate change impacts on water temperature.

Continued monitoring of these trends over time is essential to track ecosystem health and evaluate the effectiveness of management interventions. Assessing how different species within each trophic guild respond to environmental changes could reveal vulnerabilities or opportunities for conservation.

3.10 Primary sex ratio estimations of the loggerhead sea turtle *Caretta caretta* in Laganas Bay (Zakynthos) across the 21st century

3.10.1 Introduction

Sea turtles show phenotypic sex determination, meaning that sexual differentiation relies on the incubation temperature, a process known as temperature-dependent sex determination (TSD) (Standora and Spotila, 1985). Female loggerheads lay their eggs primarily on sandy beaches that maintain relatively stable temperature and humidity levels (Ackerman, 1997). The incubation stage is highly sensitive to temperatures, and once laid, the eggs are affected by any change in the local environment, without a chance to escape harmful conditions (Monsinjon et al., 2019).

Although sea turtles have shown resilience in previous climate crises, their survival will depend on their ability to adapt quickly to rising temperatures to avoid extinction (Hays et al., 2017; Blechschmidt et al., 2020). This adaptability might be reflected in any changes in behavior or physiology (Tomillo et al., 2023). Nevertheless, there is a concern that the projected temperature rise will cause a sex ratio skew towards more females, which will impact the long-term survival of the species (Hays et al., 2014). This study aims to explore sex ratio patterns and dynamics of the loggerhead sea turtle in the context of climate change. We use data on loggerhead sea turtles (*Caretta caretta*) collected at Laganas Bay, a critical nesting habitat for the species in the Mediterranean. This particular nesting rookery has the

highest nesting density in the Mediterranean region and has exhibited stable nesting patterns over the past several decades (Margaritoulis et al., 2022). Therefore, understanding potential future changes at this critical site is of utmost importance for conservation and management efforts. Sand temperature data were collected and used for 2019-2023 alongside climate models to project temperatures across the 21st century, infer the resulting sex ratios, and assess any changes at the nesting sites.

3.10.2 Study area

The current study focused on Zakynthos Island, in the Ionian Sea, Western Greece. The southern part of the island, Laganas Bay, is a nesting ground for the sea turtle *Caretta caretta* and is part of the National Marine Park of Zakynthos. The female turtles utilize six beaches of the bay to lay their eggs: Marathonisi, Laganas, Gerakas, Daphni, and Kalamaki. Each nesting site varies significantly in respect to its physical characteristics, development, and human access (Margaritoulis et al., 2022).

More specifically, data from the first three beaches were utilized for this analysis (Figure 3.56). Laganas and Gerakas are part of the main island of Zakynthos, with easy public access. In contrast, Marathonisi is a small island within the bay that is visited daily by boat. Laganas has a south orientation, is highly used by humans, and has build-up areas at the western part of the beach. Gerakas has a west orientation and is highly-used by swimmers, whereas Marathonisi has a north orientation with a darker color of sand than the other two nesting beaches under scrutiny. For the years 2019-2023, continuous field monitoring of the nesting sites by trained personnel was conducted during the nesting season, and data loggers (ONSET HOBO MX2304) were placed in some randomly selected nests to monitor and examine the environmental conditions within the nests. Nests were found during early morning surveys conducted at each nesting beach on a daily basis.

Figure 3.56. Study area: Laganas Bay, Marine protected Area (MPA) of the National Marine Park of Zakynthos. The map shows the southern part of the island of Zakynthos, where Laganas, Gerakas, and Marathonisi act as nesting sites of the loggerhead sea turtle.

Current thermal conditions

In order to obtain the current sand temperatures, data loggers were placed for the years 2019-2023 in the nests across the three beaches. In more detail, 16 data loggers (eight at Gerakas, five at Laganas, and three at Marathonisi nesting beach) were placed during 2019, 16 data loggers were placed at Marathonisi nesting beach during 2020, 15 data loggers were placed at Gerakas (2) and Marathonisi (13) nesting beaches during 2021, while another 10 and five data loggers were placed at Marathonisi nesting beach during 2022 and 2023, respectively. For each nesting site and year, the temperature records were aggregated and averaged daily. During the same period, air temperature data were collected from the nearby weather station at Zakynthos International Airport “Dionysios Solomos” (37.79°N, 20.9°E) and averaged daily. Linear regressions were performed for each beach to examine the relationship between air and sand temperatures. These regression models were used to project sand temperatures throughout the 21st century.

Climate projections

For the projection of the sex ratio across the 21st century, climate data of the 2-m daily air temperature were obtained through the Climate Data Store of Copernicus Database (2019). In detail, the European domain of the Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment (CORDEX) was selected since it offers an array of combinations of Global (GCM) and Regional (RCM) Climate Models. Daily mean air temperatures were used, in a spatial resolution of 0.11 degrees by 0.11 degrees (i.e., 12 kilometres), to extract time series over the three nesting sites under the RCP 8.5 concentration pathway. Three models were averaged, and air temperature projections were extracted for 2019 to 2023 and across the 21st century every 10 years. More specifically to decrease uncertainty in the climate projections the following combinations of GCM and RCM were selected respectively: 1) MPI-M-MPI-ESM- LR (Germany) and ICTP-RegCM4-6 (Italy), 2) MOHC-HadGEM2-ES (UK) and ICTP-RegCM4-6 (Italy), 3) NCC-NorESM1-M (Norway) and ICTP-RegCM4-6 (Italy).

Quantile mapping was employed to bias-correct the climate projections by comparing the modelled data with local air temperature observations from the nearby weather station for 2019–2023. This approach enables empirical adjustments of the modelled variable using non-parametric quantile mapping based on empirical quantiles (Piani et al., 2010). The bias correction was conducted using the qmap package in the statistical software R (Gudmundsson, 2016).

Using the established linear relationships between air and nest temperatures for each beach, sand temperature projections were reconstructed across the 21st century.

Sex ratio estimations

The relationship between incubation temperature and sex ratio is typically defined by the pivotal temperature, where an equal proportion of both sexes is produced (1:1), and the transitional range of temperatures, which produces mixed sex ratios (Abreu-Grobois et al., 2020).

For *Caretta caretta*, Mrosovsky et al. (2002) collected eggs from nests in Kyparissia Bay in 2001 and monitored their incubation under laboratory conditions. Sex was determined through a microscopic examination of the gonads, establishing relationships between temperature, incubation duration, and sex ratios. The study identified a pivotal temperature of 29.3 °C for the species in the area. These data are available in the “embryogrowth” package in R, developed by Girondot (2023), which allows the construction of a logistic model to estimate the parameters that best describe the thermal reaction norm when temperature-dependent sex determination occurs based on the methodology followed in Girondot (1999). Using this model, sex ratios were inferred based on the projected sand temperatures, with the 50th quantile as the reference point.

3.10.3 Results and Interpretations

Linear regressions were established between air temperature and sand temperature for each beach, based on the data collected for the nesting season between 2019 and 2023 (Figures 3.57, 3.58, 3.59). For all studied sites, the regression models show a significant statistical relationship between air temperatures and sand temperatures (p -value < 0.001) (Table 3.20).

Figure 3.57. Linear regression between sand and air temperatures in Marathonisi site, derived from onsite data loggers and measurements from the nearby Weather Station.

Figure 3.58. Linear regression between sand and air temperatures in Laganas site, derived from onsite data loggers and measurements from the nearby Weather Station.

Figure 3.59. Linear regression between sand and air temperatures in Gerakas site, derived from onsite data loggers and measurements from the nearby Weather Station.

Table 3.20. Linear regressions between air and sand temperatures developed for the three nesting sites Laganas, Marathonisi and Gerakas. The intercept, slope and adjusted R-squared are reported for each site. All relationships are statistically significant (p -value < 0.001).

Site	Intercept	Slope	Adjusted R-squared	p-value
Laganas	15.36	0.468	0.759	< 0.001
Marathonisi	13.06	0.546	0.647	< 0.001
Gerakas	11.55	0.661	0.797	< 0.001

Sand temperatures

Sand temperatures were inferred based on the established relationships of air-sand temperatures for Marathonisi, Laganas, and Gerakas separately for the time period 2019-2023 and across the 21st century (Figures 3.57. 3.58. 3.59). For each year, the period from June 1st to October 15th was selected to coincide with the nesting season of the sea turtles.

All three nesting sites show increasing trends in the inferred sand temperatures in the following decades. Gerakas is expected to exhibit the highest temperatures, while Marathonisi and Laganas demonstrate similar patterns.

The logistic model developed using the available data from Mrosovsky et al. (2002) is later used to infer female percentages in regard to future sand temperatures, using the 50th quantile as the reference point (Figure 3.60). The model identified a pivotal temperature of 29.3°C and a transitional range of 1.54°C, with a lower limit of 28.6°C and an upper limit of 30.1°C.

Figure 3.60. Logistic model describing sex ratio with incubation temperatures based on the data obtained by Mrosovsky et al., 2002. The pivotal temperature at 29.3 °C is marked by a vertical dotted line, with its 95% confidence interval (CI) shown in pink. The transitional range, is set at 1.54, with the lower limit at 28.6 °C and the upper limit at 30.1 °C. These limits are outlined by outer vertical dotted lines, with their corresponding 95% CI illustrated in green.

The sand temperature differences between the three sites are reflected in the estimated sex ratios for each site and their projected changes over time (Figures 3.61-3.66). More specifically, estimations of the 100% class are not yet evident in Laganas and Marathonisi but are expected to appear in the

last decades of this century. In contrast, Gerakas showed higher female-to-male ratios starting from 2020, with female presence expected to exceed 60% in the future.

Figure 3.61. Boxplots representing sand temperatures of Marathonisi during June 1st and October 15th across the 21st century, derived from the established air-sand temperature relationships using the corrected climate data.

Figure 3.62. Boxplots representing sand temperatures of Laganas during June 1st and October 15th across the 21st century, derived from the established air-sand temperature relationships using the corrected climate data.

Figure 3.63. Boxplots representing sand temperatures of Gerakas during June 1st and October 15th across the 21st century, derived from the established air-sand temperature relationships using the corrected climate data.

Figure 3.64. Stacked barplots representing the female percentages estimated throughout the 21st century (June 1st – October 15th) in Marathonisi. Each bar represents the proportion of six categorized classes for the respective year (consult legend), with female percentages inferred at the 50th quantile. Classes are calculated based on daily inferred sex across each season. The 100% class is placed at the bottom of the graph to highlight the potential feminization of the population.

Figure 3.65. Stacked barplots representing the female percentages estimated throughout the 21st century (June 1st – October 15th) in Laganas. Each bar represents the proportion of six categorized classes for the respective year (consult legend), with female percentages inferred at the 50th quantile. Classes are calculated based on daily inferred sex across each season. The 100% class is placed at the bottom of the graph to highlight the potential feminization of the population.

Figure 3.66. Stacked barplots representing the female percentages estimated throughout the 21st century (June 1st –October 15th) in Gerakas. Each bar represents the proportion of six categorized classes for the respective year (consult legend), with female percentages inferred at the 50th quantile. Classes are calculated based on daily inferred sex across each season. The 100% class is placed at the bottom of the graph to highlight the potential feminization of the population.

3.10.4 Discussion and future work

The findings of this study provide critical insights into the effect of rising sand temperatures on the sex ratio of loggerhead sea turtles (*Caretta caretta*) in the Mediterranean, focusing specifically on Laganas Bay. The use of linear regression models to establish the relationship between air and sand temperatures, combined with climate projections and sex ratio estimations, has enabled a comprehensive analysis of the potential impacts of climate change on this species.

Our results demonstrate a significant correlation between air and sand temperatures across the three studied nesting sites, with Gerakas exhibiting the steepest slope, indicating higher sensitivity to air temperature fluctuations. This pattern aligns with observed trends, where Gerakas consistently records higher sand temperatures compared to Marathonisi and Laganas. These differences highlight the distinct thermal profiles of nesting beaches, potentially influenced by factors such as sand composition, shading, and proximity to the waterline. The variability in thermal conditions among sites highlights the importance of localized conservation strategies tailored to the specific challenges of each nesting beach (Fadini et al., 2011).

Projections for sand temperatures for the 21st century indicate a clear upward trend, consistent with global climate predictions. These increases are expected to drive significant shifts in the sex ratios of

loggerhead hatchlings, as demonstrated by the logistic model incorporating pivotal and transitional temperatures. For Marathonisi and Laganas, a shift toward predominantly female hatchlings is anticipated later in the century, whereas Gerakas has already surpassed 60% female hatchling rate as early as 2020. These projections emphasize the urgency of mitigating the impacts of climate change on temperature-dependent sex determination (TSD) in sea turtles.

The skewed sex ratios observed in this study raise concerns about the long-term viability of loggerhead populations. While female-biased sex ratios may initially lead to an increase in reproductive females, prolonged imbalances could disrupt mating dynamics, reduce genetic diversity, and ultimately jeopardize population sustainability (Hays et al., 2017). This issue is particularly pressing for a species already vulnerable to habitat degradation and anthropogenic pressures (Margaritoulis et al., 2003).

Despite their historical resilience to past climate shifts, the ability of loggerhead turtles to adapt to rapid, human-induced temperature increases remains uncertain. Potential behavioral or physiological adaptations, such as selecting cooler nesting sites or adjusting nesting timing, may confer some resilience. However, the extent to which these strategies can offset the projected increases in sand temperatures remains unknown (Monsinjon et al., 2019).

From a conservation perspective, our findings emphasize the importance of implementing targeted measures to mitigate the effects of rising temperatures. These could include shading nests, relocating eggs to cooler areas, or enhancing protection for nesting sites with favorable thermal profiles (Esteban et al., 2018). Additionally, long-term monitoring of sand temperatures and hatchling sex ratios is essential to track the effectiveness of conservation strategies and refine management plans over time, following an adaptive approach to management (Katsanevakis et al. 2011).

In summary, this study provides valuable evidence on the interplay between climate change, TSD, and the future of loggerhead sea turtles. By integrating field data, climate projections, and sex ratio modeling, it offers a robust framework for understanding and addressing the challenges posed by a warming climate to this iconic species. The findings emphasize the need for immediate and sustained conservation efforts to ensure the survival of loggerhead populations in the Mediterranean Sea and beyond.

3.11 Regime shift in coral reef ecosystems, French Polynesia (LS11)

3.11.1 Introduction

Coral reefs are among marine ecosystems the most impacted by human activities across the world, by both global and local drivers (Halpern *et al.*, 2019). Resulting from the combined effects of these pressures, large scale loss of corals has been documented since decades, leading to potential regime shifts towards a less desirable algae-dominated state (Pandolfi *et al.*, 2003; Graham *et al.*, 2015; Hughes *et al.*, 2017b, a).

Various anthropogenic pressures and environmental variables can act on the competition between algae and coral, favoring one over the other (Mehdi Adjeroud, 1997; Jouffray *et al.*, 2019). The main mechanism favoring the replacement of algae over corals is the death of corals due to external disturbance (McCook *et al.*, 2001), for example a bleaching event, cyclones or an outbreak of corallivorous crown-of-thorns starfish. However, it has been also shown that local pressures can inhibit the return to a pre-disturbance state, affecting the resilience of coral reef ecosystems to accumulated anthropogenic pressures (Norström *et al.*, 2009; Graham *et al.*, 2015; Zaneveld *et al.*, 2016).

Local anthropogenic pressures responsible of potential regime shifts are mainly driven by human settlements and population density, resulting in nutrient enrichment, change in sedimentation and fishing of herbivorous fishes (Smith *et al.*, 2016; Harborne *et al.*, 2017). These pressures can act in synergy, antagonistically or additively, it is therefore difficult to separate the individual contribution of each individually and their confounding effect (Gil *et al.*, 2016; Lesser, 2021). Among pathways responsible of potential shifts, the removal of the herbivorous fishes – the main consumers of algae – by fishing, even at low level, can favor a large-scale macroalgal colonization especially after extensive coral mortality (Cheal *et al.*, 2010; Holbrook *et al.*, 2016). Nutrient enrichment coming from agricultural activities and sewage can be especially harmful to oligotrophic coral reef ecosystems by favoring coral competitors over corals, especially algae (Adam *et al.*, 2021), and by various mechanisms which decrease coral resilience to heat stress, reduce their calcification rate and promote diseases (Zhao *et al.*, 2021; Nalley *et al.*, 2023). Effects of change in sedimentation rate are also well documented, with negative effect due to an increase in turbidity and so light penetration which affect their algal symbionts, and smothering and burial of coral polyps, leading to tissue necrosis and population explosions of bacteria in coral mucus (Erftemeijer *et al.*, 2012; Tuttle and Donahue, 2022).

The coral reef ecosystem around the island of Moorea, in French Polynesia (LS11) is subject to regime shift, following several large-scale disturbances that lead to spectacular coral cover declines (from 90% to 10% in some areas) and to a non-less spectacular recovery to a pre-disturbance state (Adjeroud *et al.*, 2018), but evenly located around the island with areas not subject to recovery, suggesting differences in the resilience of corals at the patch scale (Schmitt *et al.*, 2019).

Here, we seek to identify which drivers are responsible for the fine-scale shift from coral to algae in the lagoon of Moorea, in French Polynesia (Figure 3.67). Moorea is surrounded by a barrier reef located ~1 km offshore that is interrupted by 11 major reef passes that connect a shallow (generally <3 m depth) lagoon. Moorea has over 17,000 inhabitants, concentrated along the coastline due to the steep topography, and a majority of them are engaged in a fishing activity, for their own subsistence or for a commercial purpose (Rassweiler *et al.*, 2020). Meanwhile, in the last decades, Moorea experienced a substantial economic development, including an increase in the population density and the intensification of commercial agriculture, leading to a generalized exposure to anthropogenic pressures (Loiseau *et al.*, 2021a).

Figure 3.67. Map of the study area in French Polynesia (Moorea lagoon)

3.11.2 Hypothesis

Local shifts from coral to algae in the Moorea's coral reef ecosystem are due to cumulative anthropogenic pressures, global and/or local, facilitating the settlement of algae over corals.

What are the main predictors (among environmental variables and anthropogenic pressures) explaining the current presence of algae and corals in the lagoon of Moorea, and how are they shaping the dominance of one or another state?

How simulated increase or a decrease of anthropogenic pressures act on the occurrence of corals and algae, and are tipping points identifiable to avoid it?

3.11.3 Data

Coral/algae probability of occurrence

A 0.5 meters resolution map of substrate probability for the whole lagoon of Moorea was built using a spaceborne imagery acquired in 2014 (Pléiades-1) combined with 897 geolocated pictures for ground-truthing (Collin and Hench, 2015; Thiault *et al.*, 2017). 4 classes of substrate were extracted, including coral, algae, sediment and deep water (excluded from the analysis). For each cell, the probability to belong to one of the classes was predicted, giving as results a kappa coefficient of 0.91, indicating an "almost perfect" level of agreement between observed and predicted occurrences of substrate (McHugh, 2012).

Then, we assigned to each cell a unique substrate, based on the highest probability in a given cell, and coded the reef regime on a binomial scale (0 for algae, 1 for corals, NA for others, Figure 3.68A), while keeping the initial probability of substrate occurrence to include it later in the statistical analysis as weight (higher probability of a given substrate in a cell gives a higher weight of this cell in the modelling approach, Figure 3.68B). We also calculated the current shift index (S_i) reflecting the proportion of cells occupied by algae as $S_i = P_a / P_a + P_c$, where P_a is the proportion of cells dominated by algae and P_c is the proportion of cells dominated by corals (Figure 3.68C).

Figure 3.68. Map of the occurrence of coral and algae in the lagoon of Moorea (A), distribution of the probability of each cell to belong to coral or algae (B) and current shift index computed as the proportion of cells being occupied by algae compared to the total number of cells classified as coral or algae (C)

Predictors of regime shift

Predictors were selected according to previous work on coral reef regimes (Graham *et al.*, 2015; Gove *et al.*, 2015; Harborne *et al.*, 2017; Jouffray *et al.*, 2019) and data availability. They included 7 environmental predictors (depth, slope, roughness, exposure, mean of the SST, standard deviation (sd) of the SST, exposure, and distance to pass, and 5 anthropogenic predictors: urban runoff, agricultural runoff, sedimentation rate, fishing and protection level (Table 3.21).

Table 3.21. Summary of predictors used to model the occurrence of coral/algae

Process	Predictors	Description	Spatial/temporal resolution / units	Sources
Environmental	Depth	Built from Lidar campaigns	1 x 1 meters / 2015 / meters	Shom-SAU-NSF, 2015
	Slope	Derived from depth layer	5 x 5 meters / 2014 / meters	(Collin and Hench 2015)
	Roughness	Derived from depth layer	5 x 5 meters / 2014 / meters	(Collin and Hench 2015)
	Mean SST	Annual mean obtained from daily SST (GHRSSST Level 4 MUR Global Foundation Sea Surface Temperature Analysis (v4.1))	100 x 100 meters / 2015/ °C	(NASA/JPL 2015)
	Sd SST	Annual mean obtained from daily SST (GHRSSST Level 4 MUR Global Foundation Sea Surface Temperature Analysis (v4.1))	100 x 100 meters / 2015/ °C	(NASA/JPL 2015)

	Exposure	Proxy estimated through mean wind fetch measurement, using wind speed and direction (ERA-interim every 6hrs between 2005-10)	5 x 5 meters / 2010-2019/ Unitless	(C3S 2018)
	Distance to pass	Linear distance from the nearest pass	5 x 5 meters / none / meters	-
Anthropogenic	Urban runoff	Model based on population density and sewage treatment system projected onto the lagoon through a diffusion model	5 x 5 meters / none / 2021	(Loiseau et al. 2021b)
	Agricultural runoff	Model based on agriculture intensity and uses of fertilizers and pesticides at the watershed scale, projected onto the lagoon through a diffusion model	5 x 5 meters / none / 2021	(Loiseau et al. 2021b)
	Sedimentation rate	Model based on changes of land occupation using the Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE)	5 x 5 meters / none / 2021	(Loiseau et al. 2021b)
	Fishing	Model based on fishing capacity around the island, based on population density and dependence on marine resources	5 x 5 meters / none / 2017	(Thiault et al. 2017)
	Protection level	Presence/absence of Marine Protected Area (MPA), no-take or partially protected	None / no protection, partial protection, full protection / 2005	Urban office of French Polynesia

3.11.4 Analysis

Dealing with multicollinearity

Predictors values of each layer were extracted in each cell of the coral/algae map and checked for collinearity and multicollinearity through Spearman correlation test and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) (Figure 3.69).

Figure 3.69. Multicollinearity in the dataset: results of the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) analysis (A), and matrix of pairwise correlation between predictors (B)

Unsurprisingly, slope and roughness were highly correlated, we then selected only slope for the analysis. High level of collinearity and multicollinearity were also detected between all the anthropogenic predictors, inherent to the way they have been built since they mainly rely on distance to coast, population density and watersheds. We therefore combine predictors related to watersheds (agricultural runoff and sedimentation rate) into a new one call “watershed index”, reflecting the intensity of human activities in watersheds and their potential effect into the lagoon through river mouth releases. Despite this, the level of collinearity remained too high to implement any modelling approach. We then decide to build separate models to individually incorporate anthropogenic predictors, because despite the correlation existing at the island scale, local decoupling exists, and the presence of coral or algae could be explained by only one of these predictors. Moreover, we are interested in exploring the responsibility of anthropogenic pressures in potential local regime shift and predicting changes in regime shift along an increase or a decrease of relevant anthropogenic predictors to simulate various management option, then combining them into one single predictor could mislead our interpretation and prediction of local effects of individual pressures.

Modelling the occurrence of algae/coral

We used a generalized boosted regression model (GBM, also known as Boosted Regression Trees – BRT) to examine the occurrence of coral or algae in relation to our predictors using a weighted Bernoulli distribution. GBM is an advanced regression technique that combines large numbers of relatively simple trees by sequentially fitting each new tree to the residuals from the previous ones. It improves predictive performance over more traditional tree fitting techniques such as Random Forest, with the ability to detect complex interactions among predictors and to model non-linear ecological relationships between response and predictor variables (Elith *et al.*, 2008).

Three different GBM models were built, all of them including 6 environmental predictors (depth, slope, mean SST, sd of SST, exposure, distance to pass) and 1 anthropogenic (protection level), plus each of them incorporating only one of urban runoff, fishing and watershed index predictors. To save computational time, we selected 10% of the original dataset (~ 650,000 observations) as the training data, on which models have been trained, and 10% of the remaining dataset as test data, used as “unseen” data during the training process on which models have been evaluated. We introduced as weight the probability associated with the observed regime in each cell, to give more importance to observations with higher probability during the model training. Then, the calibration of the GBM algorithm requires the specification of 3 main parameters through a range of possible value: the shrinkage, which determines the contribution of each new tree to the model; the interaction depth, which controls how many levels of interactions are fitted, and the bag fraction, specifying the proportion of data to be randomly selected while fitting each single decision tree. In order to identify the best set of parameters to be set, we first explored all combinations of the parameters to be set (shrinkage = [0.5,0.1,0.05,0.01;0.005;0.001]; interaction depth = [1,3,5,7,9]; bag fraction = [0.5;0.6;0.7;0.9,1]) using ten-fold cross-validation, and retained the set of parameters maximizing cross-validated Area Under the Curve (AUC). Optimal parameters were as follow for the three models: shrinkage = 0.1, interaction depth = 0.9, bag fraction = 0.9.

3.11.5 Metrics and models interpretation

Model responses, i.e. the probability for each cell to be assigned as coral or algae, was transformed into a binary response (0 for algae, 1 for coral) by testing different values of possible thresholds. The best threshold (from 0.1 to 0.9) was identified based on the highest obtained AUC computed from the predicted probability against the observed, giving a threshold of 0.5. We retained four metrics to assess each model against the training dataset and the testing dataset: the AUC, the accuracy, i.e. the proportion of observed data correctly predicted, the balanced accuracy, indicating if errors in

prediction are balanced into the two classes (coral or algae) or oriented in one or the other class, and the kappa coefficient described above. We calculated the median relative influence of the predictors and 95% confidence intervals from 100 bootstrap replicates on the training dataset. Relative influence of predictors is computed through records of prediction error increase when each predictor is randomly permuted one at a time (Breiman, 2001). Based on the same bootstrap replicates, we obtained partial dependency plots with 95% confidence intervals to visualize the relationships between the predictors and the response (occurrence probability of coral, coded as 1, or algae, coded as 0), while keeping all other predictors constant (Greenwell, 2017).

3.11.6 Predictions along a gradient of changes in anthropogenic pressures

For each model, we simulated changes in the involved anthropogenic predictors, from a 100% decrease to a 100% increase by step of 10% in each cell, without having the possibility to exceed the maximum or the minimum observed value of each predictor to keep predictions inside the range of observed predictors values in the models. Then, we aggregated in each cell the three different predictions of each model by testing which aggregation method between the mean, the median, the minimum or the maximum provided the highest AUC (at zero change, to compare with the observed original data). The mean of the three probabilities was the best, we therefore transformed the mean probability in a binary response using a 0.5 threshold (0 for algae, 1 for coral) in each cell, and we computed the shift index (proportion of cell predicted as algae compared to the total number of cells) for all the combination of anthropogenic pressures changes at the scale of the whole lagoon.

All the analysis were conducted using the R Statistical Software (v4.1.2; R Core Team, 2021). Packages *sf* (Pebesma, 2018), *terra* (Hijmans, 2020), *caret* (Kuhn, 2008), *gbm* (Ridgeway and Developers, 2003) and the tidyverse suite (Wickham *et al.*, 2019) was used for data preparation and analysis, *purrr* (Wickham and Henry, 2025) and *furrr* (Vaughan and Dancho, 2022) to optimize computation time, *tmap* (Tennekes, 2018), *corrplot* (Wei and Simko, 2024) and *ggplot* (Wickham, 2016) to produce map and figures.

3.11.7 Results and interpretation

Model evaluations

All three models gave similar results as assessed by the metrics used (Table 3.22). AUC on training dataset ranged from 0.953 to 0.956, and is 0.958 on the testing dataset, indicating strong predicting performance on seen and unseen data (Hosmer and Lemeshow, 2000). Accuracy on training dataset

showed that less than 5% of the cells are misclassified (i.e. classified as coral although algae was observed, and inversely), reaching a bit more than 10% on the testing dataset which is still a reasonable rate of error in an ecological context. The kappa coefficient, which considers that a correct classification could be guess by chance, indicated also a strong level of agreement, but moderate on testing data (McHugh, 2012). On both training and testing dataset, the balanced accuracy is similar to the accuracy, indicating that errors in prediction are evenly distributed in both classes.

Table 3.22. Summary of the assessment-metrics for the three models

models	Number of trees	On train data				On test data			
		AUC	Accuracy	Balanced accuracy	Kappa	AUC	Accuracy	Balanced accuracy	Kappa
With urban runoff	2500	0.956	0.948	0.945	0.891	0.958	0.893	0.888	0.778
With fishing	2699	0.954	0.951	0.949	0.898	0.958	0.893	0.888	0.777
With watershed index	2456	0.953	0.946	0.944	0.888	0.958	0.893	0.889	0.777

Model interpretations

Across the three models, depth is the main predictors of the presence of coral or algae (median relative influence ranging from 47.0% to 50.2%) with similar patterns in the partial dependence plots, suggesting that algae dominated over coral in very shallow waters, i.e. less than 2 meters deep (Figure 3.70). After depth, urban runoff is the anthropogenic predictor with the highest relative influence (median of 14.3%), while both fishing (relative influence of 10.4%) and the watershed index (9%) are outpaced by the standard deviation of SST in their respective model (Figure 3.70). Protection level has no influence on modelled occurrence of coral or algae.

Partial dependency plots (Figure 3.70, B, E, H) show a negative relationship between the three anthropogenic pressures and coral occurrence probability but not all along the pressure gradient. Since the best threshold to distinguish between algae or coral occurrence was 0.5, we can identify tipping point from a coral-dominated to an algae-dominated state when the relative intensity of urban runoff exceeds 0.4, when fishing relative intensity exceeds 0.37 and when relative intensity of watershed runoff exceeds 0.7 (Figure 3.70, B, E, H).

Figure 3.70. Summary of the three Gradient Boosted Models, showing the relative influence of predictors (A, D, G), the partial-dependency plot for anthropogenic pressures (B, E, G) with 1 coding for coral and 0 for algae, and partial-dependency plots for the 4 others main influential predictors (C, F, I). Confidence intervals were obtained with 100 bootstraps replications on the training dataset. Dashed lines in partial-dependency plots show the loess smooth of the relationship between coral/algae probability and predictors.

However, this negative relationship is reversing after the last decile of the anthropogenic pressure distribution, along with high levels of uncertainty for each model as shown by the large confidence interval starting at this point. This is likely due to a relatively small number of observations for the highest value of pressures compared with the rest of the distribution. Therefore, interpretations beyond the last deciles of pressure are potentially unreliable and should be treated carefully.

Model predictions along gradients of change in anthropogenic pressures

The predicted shift index within current condition (i.e. without changes in anthropogenic pressure) was 0.404 (comparable with the observed regime index of 0.41), and 15% of the different combination of changes in anthropogenic pressures trigger an increase towards a maximum of 0.419 (Figure 3.71), suggesting that the lagoon is already close to a potential maximum of algae cover, even if results about high level of anthropogenic pressures are highly uncertain. The remaining combinations of changes lead to a decrease of the shift index to a minimum of 0.313. The lowest shift indexes (< 0.325) are reached with minimum level of pressure coming from urban runoff and fishing (Figure 3.72A), but levels of watershed runoff pressure have neglectable effect on the shift index at the lagoon scale (Figure 3.72, B, C). Then, shift index is mainly driven by fishing and urban runoff (Figure 3.73).

Figure 3.71. Distribution of scenario (different combination on changes along gradient of anthropogenic pressures) and their associated shift index

Figure 3.72. Heatmaps of regime shift index depending on changes along a gradient of anthropogenic pressures (A: urban runoff and fishing; B: urban runoff and watershed index; C: fishing and watershed index). The color gradient of the shift index is centered on the regime shift index at zero change (0.404), also indicated in the heatmap with the large white contour line.

Figure 3.73. Evolution of the regime shift index along gradient of change in urban runoff and depending on fishing change (A) and fishing depending on urban runoff change (B), for all values in watershed index change (points in transparency). Smooth lines are generated using a loess regression. The horizontal black lines indicate the regime shift index at zero change (0.404)

3.11.8 Discussion and further work

Models are constraint by depth, which is the main influential predictors for the three of them. Thus, despite decrease or increase in anthropogenic pressures, a large quantity of cells will never be subject to a potential regime shift, explaining the relatively narrow variation of the predicted shift index (from 0.313 to 0.419). However, even if a complete shift towards an algae-dominated state at the scale of Moorea seems impossible, local shifts (patches of algae at a dozen of meters scale) in the lagoon can occur and persist, being detrimental to reef-related activities (Schmitt et al., 2019).

It seems that in the current condition, the lagoon is closer to the maximum shift index than the minimum, suggesting a possible persistence of alternative stable state under accumulated anthropogenic pressures, mainly coming from urban runoff and fishing. Even if our predictions along an increasing gradient of change for both pressures do not demonstrate a large increase of the shift index, these results should be taken with caution due to the high uncertainty of the models for these

levels of pressure. Furthermore, when looking at low levels of increase for both pressures, there is an increase as well in the shift index.

Predictions also suggest that a considerable management effort is needed to attain the best possible conditions (i.e. the lowest shift index), and acting solely on one of the considered pressures will not be enough to decrease the potential of regime shift around Moorea. But one of the main limitations of our approach is that pressures are not expressed in a manageable way since their intensity are relative, based on modelling approaches. Then, even if tipping points on these relative levels of intensities are identifiable, we need to translate our results towards a “real world” threshold.

3.12 Summary and lessons learnt

The case studies above have highlighted that many ecosystems across Europe have undergone severe changes, some of which may be described as past a tipping point. In some cases, clear tipping points and thresholds were found. For example, the introduction and invasion of new grazers in the South Aegean Sea has promoted grazing pressure and the persistence of macroalgae barrens through the grazing of recovering macroalgae populations. This, consequently, has caused permanent loss of these macroalgae and their ecological function. Similarly, the Bothnian Sea food web structure has shifted considerably on three occasions due to changing environmental parameters (e.g., nutrients and winter salinity) over a period of four decades, whereby the ecosystem changes in the pelagic and planktonic interactions occurred first and then, over the years, cascaded through to the benthos.

In other cases, tipping points or thresholds in parameters driving tipping points were more difficult to pin-point. For example, the analysis of phytoplankton communities from the Aegean Sea, the Black Sea and the Kattegat, revealed numerous shifts in community structuring on a temporal scale, even if these were not very clear tipping points in the sense where the whole community changed drastically, and that change persisted for a long time period. Nonetheless, this case study also confirmed that the nutrient concentrations in the Kattegat were much more than the other seas examined, and that phytoplankton communities across stations of the Kattegat underwent different shifts pertaining to the nutrient and environmental dynamics at the stations.

To directly evaluate the similarities and differences between case studies, Table 3.23 provides some of the key components and results identified within these case studies. What is clear is that the predominant types of pressures present in an ecosystem is what most likely drive which components within that ecosystem may be more prone to passing a tipping point. In the Baltic Sea, for example, because of shifting environmental parameters due to multiple types of human activities or climate, the biogeochemistry and planktonic communities are highly prone to shifts and, in some area, have shifted drastically. These then cascade into higher trophic levels. Other case studies around Spain show that harvesting, either of fish or macroalgae, is among the primary driver of tipping points in populations. Therefore, our case studies highlight the importance of properly managing pressures in ecosystems, and that in many instances the management of such pressures have been done to a very poor standard. Additionally, one case study pointed out that when data and understanding of an ecosystem is poor (e.g., deep ecosystems), there is a further necessity to extend the protection of such ecosystems rather than allow exploitation (e.g., trawling). This is extremely important because the ecosystem will likely be at risk of being severely impacted or destroyed, even before any valuable monitoring data can provide an understanding of how that ecosystem functions.

Table 3.23: Summary of key components and results from the tipping point analyses undertaken in ecosystems around Europe.

Case study	Country	Area	Ecosystem	Main Ecosystem Component	Main Pressure	Tipping point present	Analysis method	Main findings
Gelidium corneum macroalga biomass decline across the Basque coast	Spain	Basque coast	Bay of Biscay	Gelidium corneum	Wave intensity, Harvest	Yes	Generalized Additive Models, Segmented Regressions, Stochastic cusp Modelling	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A sharp decline in macroalgae biomass in the 2010-2015 period. 2. Decline due to the cumulative effect of increased wave flux energy and harvesting. 3. Potentially transitioning the G. corneum ecosystem to a new regime. 4. The G. corneum ecosystem will likely not recover within the next years even if the environmental conditions return to the healthier conditions or the human activities are minimized.
Sardine and Anchovy fisheries of the Ebro Delta	Spain	NW Mediterranean	Ebro delta	sardine and anchovy	fishing	Yes	Gradient Forest, Boosted Regression Trees	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The changes in regulation implemented in 2007 lead to a continuous increase in bottom trawling in important sardine nursery areas. 2. Study on the discards of bottom-trawlers in the area indicates that sardine and anchovy account for 50% of discards of bottom trawling activity in this area. 3. Therefore, the changed regulations may have caused a cascading effect through the increased capture and discard of sardines including juveniles.
Phytoplankt on community shifts	Denmark, Greece, Romania	Baltic Sea, Black Sea, Aegean Sea	Kattegat, Sulina, Danube, Est-Constanta, Mangalia Saronikos, Gera Gulf, Strait of Mytilene, Rhodes offshore waters	Phytoplankton	Dissolve inorganic nitrogen	Not specifically, but changes in community identified.	segmentation method, segmented neighbour method, PELT algorithm and SiZer method	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Danish waters show rather higher eutrophication compared to the other sites. 2. Danish waters also have highest abundances, highest dominance, and lowest diversity in phytoplankton assemblages. 3. A critical point seems to be the concentration of 4 µM of nitrogen above which abundance is rapidly increasing, species richness is decreasing, and dominance is also increasing.

Macroalgal Forests to Barrens	Greece	Eastern Mediterranean	North Aegean, South Aegean & Levantine Sea	Macro algae cover	sea urchins and <i>Sarpa salpa</i>	Yes	Breakpoint analysis, Generalized Additive Models, Principal Component Analysis	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A barren state in the North Aegean is primarily driven by sea urchins and <i>Sarpa salpa</i>. 2. In contrast, in the South Aegean & Levantine Sea, <i>Siganus</i> spp. are the main drivers pushing macroalgal forests toward a barren state. 3. A high abundance of both invasive fish species in the warmer sites (South). 4. A significant breakpoint was identified at a grazing index value of 3. 5. Invasive species limit the recovery of macroalgae.
Biogeochemical shift	Finland	Northern Baltic Sea	Åland Sea and the Bothnian Sea	geochemical components	Limited inflow of saline water and substantial freshwater input from rivers	Yes	Random Forest	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Due to eliminated inflow of saline water and substantial freshwater input from rivers, the salinity is lower and vertical stratification of the water column is weaker in the Bothnian Sea than in the Baltic main basin. 2. Clear trends and tipping points in salinity were found. 3. The salinity tipping points in the early 1990's coincided with the dynamics of saline water inflow to the Baltic Sea via the Danish straits.
Deep sea ecosystem	Portugal	Deep Atlantic-Mediterranean	Gulf of Cadiz	mud volcanoes	Climate change, bottom trawling	NA	NA	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The lack of biological information on the tolerance limits of chemosynthetic communities to increasing levels of dissolved gases like methane in water and their impact on organism's metabolism prevents further analysis. 2. Data limitations and a poor understanding of ecological processes in most deep-sea ecosystems present a significant obstacle to assessing tipping points within these communities. 3. Consequently, continuous and comprehensive studies are essential to define reference conditions, monitor ecosystem changes, and develop effective management and conservation actions that aim to prevent or mitigate ecosystem tipping points.
Benthic contamination from Oil platforms	United Kingdom	North Sea	NA	Benthos	Hydrocarbons, heavy metals	No	Generalized Additive Models and Generalized Additive Mixed Models	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The biomasses of many benthic groups were lower near to structures and at high contaminant concentrations. 2. Contaminant levels were found to increase near to platforms, but these depleted biomass levels could also be the result of the physical impacts from drilling and the construction phases. 3. Some platforms display elevated sediment THC concentrations in their vicinity and a resulting correlative link with the biomass of infaunal functional groups. 4. To determine likely effects of contaminants on fauna it is important to know the amount of toxic hydrocarbon compounds that are present and the differing susceptibility of the various organisms to them.

Shifting North Sea Harbour seal populations	Multiple (OSPAR region)	North Sea	OSPAR region	Harbour seal population	Shifting lower trophic level and environmental parameters	No	DSEM (linear – based)	An index of large fish abundance has a strong and positive “bottom-up” regulated relationship with an index of Harbour seals abundance, both of which seem to have increased since 2000. Interestingly, these changes since 2000 seem to correspond to a decrease of fishing effort since 2000, which was modelled as a “top-down” regulation on “large_fishes”. Other “bottom-up” regulating ecosystem components, from environmental variables to benthic organisms, are estimated to have indirect influences on large fish abundances, mainly though their influence on abundance of smaller fishes.
Open sea trophic guild	Finland	Baltic sea	Bothnian Bay	trophic guilds	environmental change	Yes	multivariate analyses, generalized additive models (GAMs) and segmented breakpoint analyses	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The Bothnian bay food web has shifted three times over 40 years. 2. These shifts were linked to several environmental parameters. 3. Decreasing Redfield ratio indicates change from phosphorus limited conditions towards more favourable conditions for phytoplankton. 4. Decreasing winter salinity trends might indicate changes in freshwater inputs from rivers or precipitation patterns. 5. Increasing summer bottom temperatures seem to favour benthic predators, potentially influencing their food sources and distribution. 6. Understanding these trends is crucial for developing effective management strategies.
Sea turtle sex ratio	Greece	Mediterranean	Marathonisi, Laganas, Gerakas	loggerhead turtle	increasing sand temperature	Yes	logistic model	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increasing air temperature is drastically increasing the sand temperature. 2. In Marathonisi and Laganas, a shift toward predominantly female hatchlings is anticipated later in the century. 3. Gerakas has already surpassed 60% female hatchling rate as early as 2020.
Regime shift coral/algae	French Polynesia	Lagoon of Moorea	Coral reef ecosystem	Coral / Algae	Urban runoff, agricultural runoff, sedimentation, fishing	Not specifically	Machine learning (GBM)	Urban runoff, fishing and watershed index pressures have a negative relationship with coral versus algae occurrence, until the last decile of their distribution (high uncertainty due to relatively low number of observations), favouring the settlement of algae over coral. Under current conditions, the regime shift index shows that the lagoon is almost under the maximum possible algae cover, and only a sharp decrease in urban runoff and fishing would allow to reduce the algae cover in the lagoon

Regarding the application of methods for identifying thresholds and tipping points in data, at least 10 different methods were used through the case studies. Nonetheless, 55% of case studies used either GAMs or an analysis of breakpoints or segmentation in data, meaning that the latter methods are applicable in different contexts. Nonetheless, they necessitate good understanding of which parameters drive shifts in others and cannot be used through a haphazard combination of parameters within an ecosystem at the risk of identifying patterns or break points that may either be not signify any ecological relevance, or that are artifacts of the data. Hence why many studies that used either GAM or breakpoint regressions also used other methods to help define shifts in their data and potential tipping points in the ecosystem. Finally, 45% of case studies used other methods that were more adapted to the type of data they had and were more useful at pointing out meaningful trends in the ecosystem.

Overall, the case studies presented here show that tipping points may occur in different contexts in ecosystems (e.g., fish, macroalgae, plankton) but it seems that the predominant pressure in that ecosystem is what drives which component is likely to be prone to shifting drastically. Many ecosystems around Europe have undergone major change and, in many instances, the probability of these systems to bounce back seem very low or may require a very long time, if there are no novel pressures that affect the ecosystems. As pointed out by our case study for the deep habitats, is it extremely important to safeguard habitats for which we have low information, while we improve the management of those we use heavily. Importantly, the case studies show that in many instances, although the ecosystem has changed, and a general time period can be associated to that change, identifying a specific tipping point is not always straight-forward.

Implementation of tipping point analyses in toolbox

Regarding the implementation of tipping point analyses into toolbox under development in WP4, there are several factors that require careful considerations.

1. Several methods have been applied in each case study suggesting that one method cannot be applied to identify tipping points or thresholds universally across LSs or even in habitats within one LS. This means that the choice of analysis technique needs to be founded on the type of data and the question of what seems to drive tipping points in that ecosystem.
2. Second, the data used by the analyser needs to be suitably prepared to include pressures that are suspected to cause important shifts in the ecosystem, and ecosystem components that are suspected to be prone to change. This means that careful examination and understanding of the ecosystem prior the analysis of tipping points or thresholds is needed.

3. Third, most data layers imported to the toolbox will likely be of spatial scale while many tipping point analyses are done on a temporal scale. This means that analyses within the toolbox will not simply be able to be carried out on the data currently uploaded, but the upload of specific data sets for tipping point analyses will be required. This should not be a major issue; however, the user needs to be aware of such requirements.

4. Marine Ecosystem Modelling

A range of mechanistic modelling approaches have been developed to study marine ecosystem dynamics, climate change and cumulative effects on good environmental status. The project was able to apply Ecopath with Ecosim foodweb models, EwE (Christensen and Walters, 2004; Christensen et al., 2014), across multiple regional European Seas (North Sea, Baltic Sea, Bay of Biscay and the Western Mediterranean Sea), and sub-regions of these areas (Local Baltic Sea, and the Portuguese Shelf) (Table 4.1). This ability built on the model development within EU project FutureMARES (Coll et al., 2024a) and specifically the spatial implementation of Ecospace through the digital marine laboratories approach. The models were developed to explore the consequences of Climate Change (CC), the implementation of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs), restoration activities for habitat forming species alongside fisheries management for biodiversity, ecosystem function and service provision (Coll et al., 2024b). Here, we demonstrate how these models can be used to investigate cumulative impacts by including offshore wind farms (both fixed and floating) into the marine environment alongside changes in shipping traffic.

The EwE models used in this study were calibrated previously to time-series of biomass and/or abundance, catch and/or landings (Coll et al., 2024b) with changes in temperature, salinity and primary production driving each model with additional data in some case studies (e.g. such as oxygen levels). GES4SEAS Deliverable 2.3 (Franco et al., 2023) Appendix 1 provides additional detail on the use of these models as tools for cumulative effects assessment. An ensemble of statistically downscaled environmental datasets was provided by Kristiansen et al. (2024) and processed within FutureMARES to provide standardized inputs (RCP2.6, RCP8.5, RCP-8.5) for Ecospace to drive climate changes in the model systems spatially (building upon the FutureMARES climate scenarios, Butenschön et al., 2024).

Table 4.1. Summary of Ecosim with Ecopath models used to evaluate cumulative effects on Good Environmental Status.

Models	Surface (km ²)	FGs	Fleets	Hindcast	Forecast	References
1 - North Sea	570,000	65	11	1991-2020	2021-2100	ICES, 2016; Mackinson et al., 2018; Lynam et al., in prep.
2 - Central Baltic Sea	240,669	22	10	2004-2014	2015-2098	Bauer et al., 2019
3 - Bay of Biscay	120,433	53	13	2003-2019	2019-2010	Corrales et al., 2022; Amate et al., in prep.
4 - Western Mediterranean	846,002	93	5	1995-2016	2017-2050	Coll et al., 2019a; Coll et al., in prep; Coll et al., 2019b; Gomei et al., 2021
5 - Archipelago Sea (Local Baltic Sea)	14,962	29	6	2000-2016	2017-2098	Puntilla et al., 2022, Uusitalo et al., 2023
6 - Portuguese shelf	29,847	35	3	1986-2017	2018-2100	Szalaj et al., 2021; Szalaj et al., 2022; Szalaj et al., in prep.

4.1 Scenarios

Scenarios are developed in GES4SEAS building on those proposed in FutureMARES (2021). FutureMARES considered three scenarios: Global Sustainability, National Enterprise and World Market, which considered differing targets for restoration, the implementation of MPAs and Ecosystem Based Fisheries Management (reductions in discarding and bycatch and, for Global Sustainability also reductions in fishing effort) alongside alternative climate projections following RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 to 2100. Ecospace model projections also included management status-quo scenarios that forecast changes due to climate with no further changes to fisheries management, protection through MPAs or restoration to historical conditions (Table 4.2).

Table 4.2 Summary of modelled climate change, effects of turbines, marine traffic and management activities by scenario.

Scenario num.	RCP	Primary production	Offshore wind turbines	Marine traffic	New MPAs	EBFM	Restoration
1	4.5	time-varying	-	-	No	No	No
2	4.5	time-varying	-	L, M and H	No	No	No
3	4.5	time-varying	L, M and H	-	No	No	No
4	4.5	time-varying	M	M	No	No	No
5	4.5	time-varying	M	M	Yes	Yes	No
6	4.5	time-varying	-	-	Yes	Yes	Yes
7	4.5	time-varying	M	M	Yes	Yes	Yes
8	8.5	time-varying	M	M	Yes	Yes	No
9	4.5	constant	-	-	No	No	No
10	4.5	constant	M	M	Yes	Yes	No
11	8.5	constant	M	M	Yes	Yes	No

GES4SEAS extends the Global Sustainability scenario (high protection including meeting the 30 by 30 target and including restoration efforts for key habitat forming species) and National Enterprise scenario (low protection and no restoration) scenarios to include changes in marine traffic (to 2050) and offshore windfarms (to 2050) and reconsiders these with a RCP4.5 climate projection. A variant of Global Sustainability is also run without effective restoration of habitats and termed “GES4SEAS Fisheries Sustainability with Cumulative Effects”. The GES4SEAS Global Sustainability with Cumulative Effects scenario outcomes are contrasted to the “GES4SEAS Status-Quo” scenario that includes current management and existing fisheries closures with climate change modelled following RCP4.5. Furthermore, we introduce intermediate scenarios with one or multiple pressures (traffic and/or wind farms) included to evaluate the separate contribution of each mechanism. Each regional sea study considered scenarios 1 to 11 below:

1. GES4SEAS 'Status Quo' with no change in management following climate RCP4.5
2. GES4SEAS 'Status Quo plus shipping' with sensitivity study (high, medium, low effects)
3. GES4SEAS 'Status Quo plus wind farms' with sensitivity study (high, medium, low effects)
4. GES4SEAS 'Status Quo with Cumulative Effects' (including shipping and wind farms)
5. GES4SEAS 'Fisheries Sustainability with Cumulative Effects' following climate RCP4.5
6. GES4SEAS 'Global Sustainability' following climate RCP4.5
7. GES4SEAS 'Global Sustainability with Cumulative Effects'
8. GES4SEAS 'National Enterprise with Cumulative Effects' following climate RCP8.5
9. GES4SEAS 'Status Quo - constant primary production
10. GES4SEAS 'Fisheries sustainability with Cumulative Effects - constant primary production
11. GES4SEAS 'National Enterprise with Cumulative Effects' - constant primary production

In scenarios 2, 3, 4, 5, 7 and 10,

- Marine traffic density from shipping, expected to trend down to 2040 by 25% of 2019 levels (Crum et al 2019) (not Scenario 3 where shipping is not included)
- Offshore wind farm coverage, with addition of fixed and floating wind turbines, expected to continue to increase to 2050 (not Scenario 2 where wind farms are not included)

In scenarios 8 and 11,

- Marine traffic density, expected to trend up 33% by 2050 based on the EU Reference scenario for delivering the European Green Deal (European Union, 2021; 2023)
- Offshore wind farm coverage expected to increase to 2030 only.

Turbine effect on seabirds: potential collision mortality

Piet et al. (2021) summarize the fraction reduction of survival for four common seabird species in the North Sea (with estimates of 0.005 for Common guillemot; 0.047 for Sandwich tern; 0.120 for Lesser Black-backed Gull and 0.064 for Northern Gannet). Therefore, the expected range of effect on survival is up to 6% of natural mortality, where the percentage increase in mortality = $100 \times (\text{Fraction reduction in survival})$. These data were combined with estimates of additional mortality from Everaert and Stienen (2006): 3.0–4.4% for Common Tern *Sterna hirundo*, 1.8–6.7% for Little Tern *Sterna albifrons* and 0.6–0.7% for Sandwich Tern *Sterna sandvicensis*. While these data are highly informative of impacts of turbines on a few species in the North Sea there remains a wealth of data missing for other species and areas. To bridge this gap and expand to a wider range of species we extracted a relative ranking for risk of mortality from Furness et al. (2013) (excluding their ranking of conservation

importance) and regressed the estimates of mortality increase on this ranking (Figure 4.1). From the regression line, estimates for a suite of surface feeding seabirds and diving feeders were calculated to give expected median risk and the interquartile range for each functional group (Table 4.3).

Figure 4.1. Data points (crosses) are from Piet et al. (2021) and Everaert and Stienen (2006) with relative risk ranking adapted from Furness et al. 2013, where relative risk for mortality = (Flight % at blade height) x (Flight agility + % of time flying + Night flight)/3.

Table 4.3 Estimated increase in potential mortality rate of seabirds due to collision with turbines, where the medium level is based on the median expected mortality risk, low is the 1st quartile and high is the 3rd quartile.

Functional group	Increase in mortality rate due to collision		
	Low (25 th percentile)	Medium (median)	High (75 th percentile)
All seabirds	0.02	0.03	0.05
Surface feeding seabirds ¹	0.03	0.05	0.09
Diving seabirds ²	0.01	0.02	0.03

¹ Surface feeding seabirds considered were: Arctic skua, Arctic tern, Black-headed gull, Black-legged kittiwake, Common gull, Common tern, European storm-petrel, Great black-backed gull, Great skua, Herring gull, Leach's storm-petrel, Lesser black-backed gull, Little tern, Northern fulmar, Roseate tern, Sandwich tern, White-tailed eagle.

² Diving seabird species considered were: Atlantic puffin, Black guillemot, Black-throated diver, Common eider, Common guillemot, Common scoter, Great cormorant, Great northern diver, Great-crested grebe, Little auk, Long-tailed duck, Manx shearwater, Northern gannet, Razorbill, Red-throated diver, Shag, Slavonian grebe, Sooty shearwater, Velvet scoter.

Marine traffic effect on mammals: potential collision mortality

The shipping route effects on mammal other mortality (not bycatch or predation) were estimated for fin whales based on data from the northeast Atlantic from Robbins (2022) and from the western Mediterranean Sea from Sèbe et al. (2023). These data were then combined with data on frequency of occurrence of species to be impacted by vessels (Schoeman et al., 2020) to estimate relative impacts for functional groups of turtles, seals, toothed cetaceans and whales in general to standardise the

approach across regional sea models (Table 4.4). The turtles considered include *Caretta caretta* and *Chelonia mydas*, seals include *Phoca vitulina*, *Halichoerus grypus* and *Monachus monachus*, toothed cetaceans include *Phocoena Phocoena*, *Tursiops truncatus*, *Delphinus delphis*, *Stenella coeruleoalba*, *Globicephala melas*, *Grampus griseus*, *Ziphius cavirostris* and *Physeter macrocephalus*, and whales include *Balaenoptera musculus*, *Balaenoptera physalus* and *Balaenoptera acutorostrata*.

Table 4.4 Estimated increase in potential mortality rate of mammals due to collision with ships, where the medium level is based on the median expected mortality risk, low is the 1st quartile and high is the 3rd quartile.

Functional group	Increase in mortality rate due to collision		
	Low (25 th percentile)	Medium (median)	High (75 th percentile)
Toothed cetaceans	0.02	0.04	0.07
Seals	0.02	0.04	0.07
Turtles	0.03	0.06	0.09
Baleen whales	0.03	0.06	0.09

Foraging impacts due to avoidance

Within Ecospace, functional groups of species distribute themselves of the model grid dependent on the quality of a cell relative to its neighbour in terms of foraging capacity and their response to predators. So, when the foraging capacity of a cell is degraded (through the introduction of shipping noise or a man-made structure) a group is likely to avoid that cell. We model avoidance by mammals of shipping routes and avoidance by seabirds of turbines by reducing the foraging capacity of the impacted cells.

The sensitivity of the level of avoidance of shipping routes by top predators was modelled with three levels of effect on foraging, where the reduction in foraging within a cell (i.e. one completely covered by a shipping route) would be 25%, 50% or 75% (low, medium and high levels, respectively) of the expected value given the prey levels and environmental conditions in the cell. The effect was modelled with a linear decrease from no effect in empty cells to the maximum effect for saturated cells. A similar approach was taken for avoidance of wind farm areas by seabirds with three levels of effects on foraging 25%, 50% or 75% (low, medium and high levels respectively), but with a greater impact on species of birds that dive for their prey 50%, 75% or 90% (low, medium and high levels respectively).

Offshore wind turbine effects on benthic organisms

The impact of turbines on benthic habitat was included in the models with the simple assumption of an area of habitat per turbine dependent on pile diameter or expected anchor area along with expected scour protection area per turbine (Table 4.5). Habitat is considered lost for infauna due to

the construction of the turbines and artificial habitat is considered gained for epifaunal groups through the addition of scour protection at the base of fixed wind turbines and around anchors for floating wind turbines. Standard buffers were used to estimate habitat area lost or gained per grid cell given the number of turbines in each cell with different values for fixed turbines (infaunal habitat lost per turbine = 79 m² assuming a pile diameter of 10m, epifaunal habitat gained per turbine = 1,963m² assuming a scour radius of 25m) and floating turbines (infaunal habitat lost per turbine = 1 m² assuming a pile diameter of 0.8m, epifaunal habitat gained per turbine = 20m² assuming a scour radius of 2.5m).

Table 4.5. Summary of specific human activities, impacts to include and datasets required

Activity	Impact to model	Dataset description	Implementation in Ecospace
Offshore wind farm (all types)	Seabird collision	OWF polygon coverage by cell without buffer	Linear “other mortality” function STF: Environmental driver
Offshore wind farm (all types)	Seabird avoidance	OWF polygon coverage by cell, with 0.5 km buffer (i.e. as fishing restrictions layer)	Linear environmental foraging function STF: Environmental driver
Offshore wind farm (all types)	Permission for all fisheries to fish wherever OWF do not exist (1-defacto.MPA)	1-coverage of OWF polygon (including fixed and floating with 0.5 km buffers)	STF-Habitat. Require check box ticks in table of HabitatFishery for each and every fishery. Requires ‘Habitat layer’ for fishing.
Offshore wind farm (restriction in floating turbine areas, but permission in fixed turbine areas***)	Permission for some fisheries to fish wherever OWF do not exist and also inside fixed turbine areas (1-FPA)	1-coverage of polygon for floating turbines (including 0.5 km buffer).	STF-Habitat. Require check box ticks in table of HabitatFishery to identify specific fisheries. Requires ‘Habitat layer’ for fishing [note if grid cell overlaps with defacto.MPA (above) selected fisheries will now fish in fixed farm area]
Turbine-occupied area per cell	Habitat lost due to pile driving for infaunal groups	Turbines with buffer diameter 10m fixed and 1m floating	Linear environmental foraging function applied to infaunal groups STF: Environmental driver
Turbine-occupied area per cell	Habitat gained though scour protection for epifaunal groups	Turbines with buffer diameter 50m fixed and 5m floating	STF: Habitat ‘Habitat foraging usage’ table: values =1
Shipping routes	Collision risk for marine mammals / turtles	Route density, no buffer	Linear other mortality function applied to key groups STF: Environmental driver
	Avoidance by marine mammals / turtles		Linear environmental foraging function applied to key groups STF: Environmental driver

*Note for windfarm areas (include seabird collision/avoidance and fishing restrictions) and turbine habitat datasets YEAR is annual 1990 to 2023 then 2030, 2040 to 2050, but only provided where there is a change in presence. ASCII files are cumulative, so YEAR includes all turbines from 1990 up to and including YEAR.

**Note for all shipping route datasets. SCENARIO is Sustainability or National Enterprise. First YEAR is 2021 followed by annual projections to 2040 (Sustainability) or 2050 (National Enterprise).

*** Floating turbine areas are considered equal to FuMa Fully Protected Areas (FPA) – no activity zones. Fixed turbine areas are considered equal to FuMa Highly Protected Areas (HPA) allowing some fisheries.

#Alternative datasets for offshore wind.

For the Portuguese shelf, datasets based on IPMA GIS data product Áreas para implantação de parques eólicos marinhos: Revisão 01 — divgmwebgis.ipma.pt. For the North Sea, datasets based on Waldman et al. Data product <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14222865>

Lost habitat impact on foraging suitability of infauna

For infauna, we use the simple linear function from x_1 (no effect) at driver value $X_{min}=0$ (i.e. when no structure is present) to 0 (no suitable habitat) at driver value $X_{max}=1$ (i.e. when cell fully covered by structure). This impact is then altered annually and spatially by the Spatial Temporal Framework given the area of habitat in each model grid cell lost due to construction of the fixed turbines (piling) or addition of anchors.

Additional habitat gained for epifauna

The additional habitat for epibenthic groups was determined through application of a buffer of 50m diameter (25m radius) around all fixed turbines (monopile or pin-pile) (Leen de Vos et al., 2012; Posen et al., 2020). The complexity of the surface in the vertical dimension was not considered.

New artificial habitat was considered as preferred habitat for epifaunal groups through inclusion of values of 1 in 'Habitat foraging usage' table for these groups (following Lynam et al., 2017 and Puets et al., 2023). The effect is then altered annually and spatially by the Spatial Temporal Framework given the area of habitat in each model grid cell due to scour protection at the base of fixed wind turbines and anchors for floating wind turbines.

Fisheries impacts due to restrictions near turbines and avoidance behaviour

Fishing fleets were considered to be effectively excluded from areas with floating wind turbines due to the risk of operating fishing gears near to the anchor lines that present a significant snagging hazard. Around fixed wind turbines, mobile gears were restricted due to expected difficulties operating gears around turbines and service vessels operating in the area. However, small-scale and artisanal fisheries (such as those using pots, traps or fixed nets) were considered unimpacted and able to fish in areas between turbines. For restricted fishing fleets, the available area within a grid square was reduced by the surface coverage of the wind farm area with an additional 500m buffer representing an exclusion area for safety.

Model outputs

Annual average maps (ASCII format) and time-series (CSV format) are provided by each study for: the biomass, catch and discards of each functional group along with fishing effort by fishing fleet and ecological indicators (biomass based, catch based, diversity metrics - Kempton's Q and Shannon diversity, trophic level based for the catch and the community, expected mean length and mean weight of the fish community and of the catch given species traits). The relevant comparisons between scenarios to demonstrate impact of specific activities/climate/management are as follows:

- *Impact of offshore wind*

The difference in the impact of adding offshore wind to the model can be seen in the contrast between scenarios 4 (with medium effects of offshore wind and shipping) and 2 (with medium effect of shipping only). Uncertainty in the effect of the response of impacted functional groups to the installation of offshore wind turbines is demonstrated by the difference between high, medium and low outputs from scenario 3.

- *Impact of shipping traffic*

The difference in the impact of adding shipping to the model can be seen in the contrast between scenarios 4 (with medium effects of offshore wind and shipping) and 3 (with medium effect of offshore wind only). Uncertainty in the effect of the response of impacted functional groups to shipping is demonstrated by the difference between high, medium and low outputs from scenario 2.

- *Impact of shipping and offshore wind combined*

The cumulative impact of both shipping and wind is evident in the contrast between scenario 1 and 4 (each status quo management) and also between scenarios 6 and 7 (each including EBFM).

- *Impact of MPAs/EBFMs combined*

The difference in the impact of MPAs, bycatch and discard mitigation can be seen in the contrast between scenario 4 and scenario 5.

- *Impact of restoration*

The difference in the impact of restoration can be seen in the contrast between scenarios 5 and 7.

- *Impact of MPA/EBFM/restoration combined*

The difference in the impact of restoration can be seen in the contrast between scenarios 4 (not including MPA/EBFM/restoration) and 7 (including MPA/EBFM/restoration).

- *Impact of primary production*

The difference in the impact of change in PP can be seen in the contrast in scenarios 1 and 9 (for RCP4.5 with status quo management) and also between 5 and 10 (for RCP4.5 with EBFM-Fisheries Sustainability) and between 8 and 11 (for RCP8.5 with EBFM-National Enterprise).

- *Impact of climate (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5) combined with MPA/EBFM management*

The difference between Fisheries sustainability and National Enterprise is demonstrated by the contrast between scenarios 5 and 8. Neither of these scenarios include restoration.

4.2 EwE results – North Sea

Fisheries management

In each scenario, the fishing effort (days fishing) of fleets was reduced within MPAs, cod management areas, and, where present, within offshore wind farms (Figure 4.2). Reductions in fishing effort leads to reductions in catch in those areas with fisheries restrictions and potentially increases in catch in unprotected areas due to the displacement of fishing effort (e.g. as shown in the outputs from the status quo scenario, Figure 4.3). In every scenario, all mobile bottom-impacting gears were excluded from the plaice box in the southern North Sea, the Western Dogger Bank closure in the central North Sea and the small UK protected area ‘Northeast of Farnes Deep’. Industrial fisheries for sandeels were also excluded from the ‘Firth of Forth’ closure to the east of Scotland and all gears catching cod were excluded from the small seasonal cod management plan areas in the northern North Sea. In the fisheries sustainability, global sustainability and national enterprise scenarios additional MPAs were added following the FutureMARES project scenarios (Coll et al., 2024) (Figures 4.4 and 4.5). All fishing fleets were excluded from Fully Protected Areas (FPAs), while trawl and seine fleets (including demersal, beam, pelagic, *Nephrops*, dredges, industrial) were excluded from Highly Protected Areas (HPAs) only allowing some fisheries to continue (including pots, shrimpers, drift and fixed nets, gears using hooks and the class of other undefined gears).

Figure 4.2. Fishery restrictions due to proportional coverage of cells by wind farms with fixed turbines impacting selected gears (left), floating turbines impacting all gears (middle) and other restrictions (right) where the areas shown include bottom trawl restrictions near coasts (hatched), the Western Dogger Bank and gears targeting cod in the north.

GES4SEAS S4 SQ cumulative effects

Demersal trawl + dem seine (Effort)

Pelagic trawl (Effort)

Pots (Effort)

Figure 4.3. Fishing effort in scenario 4 with RCP4.5 climate trajectory, additional turbines in 2030 and 2040 (fixed turbines - open polygons, floating turbines - hatched polygons) and 25% reduction in marine traffic by 2040. Maps show average distribution of effort standardised to the 2020s (left, showing percentage of effort in each grid cell of the total over the whole domain) followed by change per grid cell (increases and decreases per cell relative to 2020s) by 2030s, 2050 and 2090s for demersal trawlers and seiners (top), pelagic trawlers (middle) and pots (bottom).

GES4SEAS S7 Global cumulative effects

Demersal trawl + dem seine (Effort)

Pelagic trawl (Effort)

Pots (Effort)

Figure 4.4. The distribution of fishing effort in Scenario 7 with RCP4.5 climate trajectory, new Marine Protected Areas for Global Sustainability (Highly Protected Areas, HPA open polygons, and Fully Protected Areas, FPA hatched polygons) to meet the 30x30 commitment, plus a decrease in fishing effort post-2030 and with new wind turbines in 2030 and 2040 and a reduction in vessel speed by 2050. Maps are shown for demersal trawlers and seiners (top), pelagic trawlers (middle) and pots (bottom). The maps show the average distribution of effort in the 2020s reference period (left) followed by change in effort relative to the 2020s in 2030s, 2050 and 2090s.

GES4SEAS S8 NatEnt cumulative effects

Demersal trawl + dem seine (Effort)

Pelagic trawl (Effort)

Pots (Effort)

Figure 4.5. The distribution of fishing effort for National Enterprise Scenario 8 with RCP4.5 climate trajectory, Marine Protected Areas (Highly Protected Areas, HPA open polygons, and Fully Protected Areas, FPA hatched polygons) and the addition of wind turbines (to 2030 only) and an increase in marine traffic by 2040. Maps are shown for demersal trawlers and seiners (top), pelagic trawlers (middle) and pots (bottom). The maps show the average distribution of effort in the 2020s reference period (left) followed by change in effort relative to the 2020s in 2030s, 2050 and 2090s.

Overall change in the biomass of functional groups by scenario

In each scenario, several functional groups increase by 2050 relative to the 2020s (megrim, skate and cuckoo ray, small sharks and horse mackerel) due to the positive impacts of climate change, while a number are expected to continue to decrease (starry ray, wolf-fish, surface-feeding seabirds, saithe, halibut and cod) due to the negative impacts of climate change (Figure 4.6). By 2090, decreases continue and are exacerbated in the National Enterprise scenario, which uses a more extreme climate

projection (RCP8.5) and differs from the others that include the RCP4.5 projection (Figure 4.7). The biomasses of grey seals and harbour porpoise fall to their lowest levels in the National Enterprise with cumulative effects scenario (S8) due to the climate driven reduction in forage fish biomass (herring, sandeel and sprat) (Figure 4.8) despite higher bycatch levels in S1, S3, S4 and S9 (Figure 4.9). The long-term climate effect on forage fish (sandeel and sprat) is largely due to direct impact of temperature increase on foraging ability of the fish, but for herring the modelled reduction in primary production greatly exacerbates this direct impact (contrast S8, black dotted lines, with S11, green solid lines, in Figure 4.8) through a reduction in the biomass of zooplankton groups (copepods, carnivorous zooplankton and gelatinous zooplankton, Figure 4.10).

Notable increases in biomass between 2020 and 2050 occur for tope, large demersal fish, turbot, sprat and monkfish following reductions in fishing effort and catch (Figure 4.11) and with the implementation of Marine Protected Areas in Scenarios 5, 6, 7 and 10 to meet the 30% protection of sea surface area by 2030. Furthermore, harbour seals, grey seals and harbour porpoise benefit from a decrease in bycatch in scenarios 5, 6, 7 and 10 and to a lesser extent in scenarios 8 and 11. In contrast the decrease in discard tonnage in scenarios 5, 6, 7 and 10 leads to a decrease in the biomass of surface-feeding seabirds.

The overall changes in the ecosystem can be captured through ecosystem indicators as shown in Figure 4.12. Notably the biomass of predators, IUCN listed species and diversity metrics (Shannon index and Kempton's-Q) increase in each scenario. However, the total biomass of the system only increases in scenario 11 in which fishing levels are moderate with a high rate of climate change (RCP8.5), but in which primary production is not allowed to vary demonstrating the importance of this variable for the model. In contrast, scenario 10 within greater protection from fishing, but a lower rate of climate change (RCP4.5) and in which primary production is not allowed to vary does not result in an increase in total biomass of the system. The mean trophic level increases in the status-quo scenario 1 and the cumulative effects scenario 4 demonstrating a high biomass of predators relative to prey, but decreases in each of the other scenarios shown demonstrating changes within the structure of the food web.

Figure 4.6 Heatmap showing change in biomass of functional groups between 2050s and the 2020s for 11 scenarios.

Figure 4.7 Heatmap showing change in biomass of functional groups between 2090s and the 2020s for 11 scenarios.

Figure 4.8 Biomass of key fish species over time for 10 scenarios.

Figure 4.9 Bycatch of marine mammals over time for 10 scenarios.

Figure 4.10 Change in biomass of planktonic groups over time for 10 scenarios

Figure 4.11 Change in total catch of key fish species over time for 10 scenarios.

Figure 4.12 Change in ecosystem indicators relative to 2020s for 6 scenarios.

Impact of offshore wind turbines on functional group biomass

The impact of wind turbines on the biomass of functional groups is evident from the contrast of outcomes from the three variants of scenario 3 with differing level of response to turbines by seabirds (i.e. high, medium and low avoidance response and mortality rate). Furthermore, the contrast in these outcomes to scenario 1 (the climate status-quo without turbines or shipping) standardises these impacts for the effects of climate change. The contrast between the cumulative effects scenario 4 (with medium responses to the impacts of turbines and shipping) and scenario 2 (no wind farms but a medium response to shipping) reveals the synergy between the impact of shipping and wind farms. In each of these scenarios (S1-4), the model is driven by RCP4.5 climate projection with constant fishing effort in the future (equal to the most recent value) and keeping marine protections (fisheries closures and MPAs) that are currently in place constant post-2023. New offshore wind turbines are added in both S3 and S4 between 2023 and 2050 according to the sustainability scenario (i.e. increasing coverage to 2050, with the majority of additions before 2040 by fixed turbines in the southern North Sea followed by additions 2040-2050 by floating turbines in the northern North Sea and more fixed turbines in the southern North Sea). In S4, the impact of shipping on marine mammals

is constant prior to 2021, when a gradual linear decrease begins down to 75% of the 2021 level in 2040.

The biomass of each seabird group decreases with increasing levels of offshore wind coverage due to collisions of birds within the regions despite the avoidance functional response. Relative to the status-quo Scenario 1, there is a decrease in the 2050s due to fixed turbines of between 17% and 46% of seabird functional group biomass in offshore wind farms and a similar impact due to floating turbines of between 11% and 41% of biomass in offshore wind farms (Table 4.6). The greatest impact in the 2050s relative to S1 is modelled on diving seabirds among farms with fixed turbines in the high response scenario and smallest impact on surface-feeding seabirds among farms with floating turbines in the low response scenario.

Table 4.6. Sensitivity of biomass of seabirds to turbine impacts (collision and avoidance) along with key prey species once standardised to Scenario 1 to exclude climate change impacts. Values give the percentage difference in biomass in the 2050s [$100 \times (S3_{bio} - S1_{bio})/S1_{bio}$] between Scenario 1 (Status quo) and three variants of Scenario 3 (with turbines).

Scenario comparison	Windfarm Area	Diving seabirds	Kittiwakes	Surface-Feeding seabirds	Sprat	Sandeel	Herring
S1 vs S3 Low	Fixed turbines	-25	-16	-17	1	0	2
S1 vs S3 Medium		-38	-27	-27	2	0	2
S1 vs S3 High		-46	-40	-38	3	0	2
S1 vs S3 Low	Floating turbines	-19	-12	-11	-5	-2	2
S1 vs S3 Medium		-33	-25	-23	-4	-2	2
S1 vs S3 High		-41	-38	-36	-4	-2	2
S1 vs S3 Low	North Sea	-2	-4	-4	-1	-1	1
S1 vs S3 Medium		-6	-7	-7	-1	-1	1
S1 vs S3 High		-6	-10	-10	-1	-1	1

Due to a reduction in fishing effort within the wind farms and an increase in artificial habitat from scour protection, the modelled simulates increases in the biomasses of large crabs (including edible crabs and European lobster, with biomass 158% higher in fixed turbine areas and 6% higher in the floating turbine areas in the 2050s than expected given projected change in the status-quo scenario, S1) and *Nephrops* (91% higher in fixed turbine areas but only 1% in the floating turbine areas relative to S1 in the 2050s). The impact on benthic infaunal groups due to a loss of physical habitat was found to be <1% of the expected biomass in S1 in 2050s. Larger changes were found due to predator-prey

interactions and the displacement of fisheries, specifically for the biomass of sprat (between 1-3% higher in the fixed turbine areas in the 2050s than expected given the status-quo scenario, S1, but 4-5% lower in the floating turbine areas), plaice (5% lower in fixed turbine areas, but 3% higher in the floating turbine areas), turbot (6% lower in fixed turbine areas but 1% higher in the floating turbine areas). Change over time in the biomasses of seabirds, selected fish and benthic functional groups is shown in Figures 4.13a-c and tabulated in Tables 4.7-4.10. Overall, at the whole North Sea scale, the impact of turbines relative to S1 in the 2050s was found to be negative for sprat (-1%), plaice (-4%) and turbot (-2%) but positive for large crabs (20%), *Nephrops* (9%), oysters (7%), mussels (5%), herring (3%), cod (1%), flounder (1%), skate/cuckoo ray (2%), thornback and spotted ray (1%), starry ray and others (4%).

Table 4.7. Percentage change in biomass of selected fish species through fisheries and foodweb responses to turbine impacts once standardised to Scenario 1 to exclude climate change impacts. Values give the percentage difference in biomass between the scenario in the 2020s $[100 \times (S3_{bio} - S1_{bio})/S1_{bio}]$ between Scenario 1 (Status quo) and the three variants of Scenario 3 (with turbines). Note outputs for S3 with high and low responses of fish are identical for these groups.

Scenario comparison	Windfarm Area	Cod	Plaice	Turbot	Skate and cuckoo ray	Thornback and spotted rays	Starry ray and others
S1 vs S3 medium	Fixed turbines	0	-5	-6	2	5	6
S1 vs S3 medium	Floating turbines	2	3	1	3	4	5
S1 vs S3 medium	North Sea	<1	-4	-2	2	1	4

Figure 4.13a. Time-series of biomass for seabird functional groups resulting from the model driven by RCP4.5 with current fishing effort and marine protection in place and change in offshore wind turbines and shipping route density according to three scenarios: S3 (three levels of impact of turbines), S4 (with medium impacts of turbines and shipping) and S2 (medium impact of shipping and no impact of turbines).

Figure 4.13b. Time-series of biomass for key functional groups of fish resulting from the model driven by RCP4.5 with current fishing effort and marine protection in place and change in offshore wind turbines and shipping route density according to three scenarios: S3 (three levels of impact of turbines), S4 (with medium impacts of turbines and shipping) and S2 (medium impact of shipping and no impact of turbines).

Figure 4.13c. Time-series of biomass for key functional groups of benthic fauna resulting from the model driven by RCP4.5 with current fishing effort and marine protection in place and change in offshore wind turbines and shipping route density according to three scenarios: S3 (three levels of impact of turbines), S4 (with medium impacts of turbines and shipping) and S2 (medium impact of shipping and no impact of turbines).

Table 4.8. Percentage change between 2050s and 2020s in the biomass of seabirds in the status quo scenario 1, three variants of the OWF scenario 3 and in the status quo with cumulative effects scenario 4 with medium response to OWF and shipping by spatial region – where the offshore wind farm extent (for fixed turbines, floating turbines and no turbines) is set at the full modelled coverage in 2050 across all scenarios (including S1 where no turbines are implemented).

Change over time by scenario	Spatial region	Diving seabirds	Kittiwakes	Surface seabirds
S1 status quo (RCP4.5) and no change in human activities	no OWF region	-15.1	-12.9	-21.2
	fixed turbines	-16.8	-15.4	-16.8
	floating turbines	-13.2	-9.0	-29.4
	North Sea	-15.3	-13.3	-20.4
S3 status quo (RCP4.5) with low response to OWF	no OWF region	-13.8	-14.4	-21.8
	fixed turbines	-38.3	-29.1	-31.1
	floating turbines	-31.2	-21.1	-38.1
	North Sea	-19.0	-17.6	-24.3
S3 status quo (RCP4.5) with medium response to OWF	no OWF region	-14.4	-14.7	-21.5
	fixed turbines	-48.9	-38.8	-39.5
	floating turbines	-42.9	-32.9	-46.6
	North Sea	-21.8	-20.2	-26.3
S3 status quo (RCP4.5) with high response to OWF	no OWF region	-14.7	-15.1	-21.4
	fixed turbines	-55.4	-48.9	-48.4
	floating turbines	-50.0	-44.7	-55.4
	North Sea	-23.5	-22.8	-28.5
S4 status quo (RCP4.5) with cumulative effects to OWF and shipping (medium responses)	no OWF region	-14.6	-14.9	-21.7
	fixed turbines	-49.1	-39.0	-39.6
	floating turbines	-43.1	-33.1	-46.8
	North Sea	-22.0	-20.4	-26.5

Table 4.9. Percentage change between 2050s and 2020s in biomass of key benthic fauna in the status quo scenario 1, three variants of the OWF scenario 3 and in the status quo with cumulative effects scenario 4 with medium response to OWF and shipping by spatial region – where the offshore wind farm extent (for fixed turbines, floating turbines and no turbines) is set at the full modelled coverage in 2050 across all scenarios (including S1 where no turbines are implemented).

Change over time by scenario	Spatial region	Large crabs	Nephrops	Epifaunal macro-benthos	Sessile epifauna	Small epifauna	Small infauna	Infaunal macro-benthos
S1 status quo (RCP4.5) and no change in human activities	no OWF region	-3.8	-5.0	-5.0	-6.0	0.2	-0.8	-1.7
	fixed turbines	-0.7	-5.6	-4.4	-5.3	-0.5	-0.9	-2.2
	floating turbines	0.0	-3.4	-5.1	-5.7	0.4	0.0	-1.3
	North Sea	-3.4	-4.9	-5.0	-6.0	0.1	-0.7	-1.8
S3 status quo (RCP4.5) with medium response to OWF	no OWF region	-3.5	-5.3	-4.5	-4.9	-3.2	-3.4	-3.4
	fixed turbines	111.6	66.7	-1.3	2.8	4.4	-2.5	-3.4
	floating turbines	5.8	-3.2	-3.9	-3.4	-3.2	-3.5	-3.7
	North Sea	9.3	1.3	-4.1	-4.1	-2.5	-3.3	-3.4
S4 status quo (RCP4.5) with cumulative effects to OWF and shipping (medium responses)	no OWF region	-3.6	-5.3	-4.6	-4.9	-3.2	-3.4	-3.4
	fixed turbines	111.5	66.7	-1.3	2.8	4.4	-2.5	-3.4
	floating turbines	5.7	-3.2	-3.9	-3.4	-3.2	-3.5	-3.7
	North Sea	9.2	1.3	-4.1	-4.2	-2.5	-3.3	-3.4

Table 4.10. Percentage change between 2050s and 2020s in biomass of key fish species in the status quo scenario 1, three variants of the OWF scenario 3 and in the status quo with cumulative effects scenario 4 with medium response to OWF and shipping by spatial region – where the offshore wind farm extent (for fixed turbines, floating turbines and no turbines) is set at the full modelled coverage in 2050 across all scenarios (including S1 where no turbines are implemented).

Change over time by scenario	Spatial region	Cod	Herring	Plaice	Sandeels	Sprat	Turbot
S1 status quo (RCP4.5) and no change in human activities	no OWF region	-16.7	-7.2	-7.9	-13.8	7.9	-0.3
	fixed turbines	-25.8	-6.2	-9.4	-25.1	12.9	11.3
	floating turbines	-13.0	-8.2	-3.9	-2.8	5.5	-5.3
	North Sea	-17.3	-7.2	-8.2	-15.6	9.1	1.1
S3 status quo (RCP4.5) with medium response to OWF	no OWF region	-17.0	-9.5	-11.9	-16.8	4.4	-3.3
	fixed turbines	-26.6	-7.0	-14.8	-25.9	14.2	3.7
	floating turbines	-12.7	-9.5	-2.6	-7.6	-2.4	-4.9
	North Sea	-17.7	-9.3	-12.4	-18.2	6.7	-2.3
S4 status quo (RCP4.5) with cumulative effects to OWF and shipping (medium responses)	no OWF region	-17.3	-9.6	-12.2	-17.0	4.2	-3.5
	fixed turbines	-27.0	-7.2	-15.1	-26.1	14.0	3.3
	floating turbines	-12.9	-9.6	-3.0	-7.8	-2.5	-5.1
	North Sea	-17.9	-9.4	-12.7	-18.4	6.5	-2.6

Impact of shipping

Change over time in the biomasses of marine mammal functional groups is shown in Figure 4.14. The period until 2021 has a constant level of shipping density and a therefore the difference between the three variants of Scenario 2 demonstrates the differing impacts of assumptions of collision risk and avoidance impacts on foraging. The sensitivity of marine mammals to these impacts are summarised in Table 4.11, where each group is impacted most in the high shipping scenario, and the recovery from reductions in marine traffic are shown in Table 4.12. The greatest impact was evident for harbour porpoise (a 4% decrease in total biomass) followed by the southern population of harbour seals (3% decrease). The impact on the northern population of harbour seals is very small (<0.05% of total biomass) as the population is not directly impacted by most of the shipping activity that takes place in the southern North Sea. Little detrimental change is evident in fish, seabird or benthic functional groups due to shipping as groups generally increased as a result of reductions in mammal predators, with the greatest increases in modelled total biomass (>2%) found for herring, saithe, other large and small demersal fish and the group of miscellaneous filter-feeding pelagic fish. However, a single group (wolf-fish) did decrease in the high shipping scenario by a small amount (0.1%) due to the avoidance behaviour of its predator, grey seals, and spread the core area of wolf-fish.

Table 4.11. Sensitivity of mammal biomass to shipping impacts (collision and avoidance) once standardised to Scenario 1 to exclude climate change impacts. Values give the percentage difference in biomass between the scenario in the 2020s [$100 \times (S2_{bio} - S1_{bio})/S1_{bio}$] between Scenario 1 (Status quo) and the three variants of Scenario 2 (with shipping).

Scenario comparison for North Sea	Minke whale	Grey seals	Harbour porpoise	Harbour seals (N)	Harbour seals (S)
S1 vs S2 SQ Low shipping	-0.6	-0.1	-1.1	0.0	-0.4
S1 vs S2 SQ Med shipping	-1.2	-0.8	-2.4	0.0	-1.5
S1 vs S2 SQ High shipping	-1.8	-1.9	-4.2	0.0	-3.1

Table 4.12. Recovery of mammal biomass from shipping impacts (collision and avoidance) following reduction in shipping impacts by 25% by 2040 and in a warming climate (RCP4.5). Percentage change over time between 2050s and 2020s in the biomass of mammal species in three variants of the shipping S2 in the whole region and in the area impacted by shipping.

Scenario	Spatial region	Minke whale	Grey seals	Harbour porpoise	Harbour seals (N)	Harbour seals (S)
S2 SQ Low shipping with 25% reduction in shipping by 2040	Shipping region	-5.4	31.9	0.0	-27.5	8.4
	North Sea	-7.2	4.2	-2.2	-4.1	6.4
S2 SQ Med shipping with 25% reduction in shipping by 2040	Shipping region	-4.5	34.5	0.9	-26.9	10.7
	North Sea	-7.0	5.3	-2.2	-3.9	8.3
S2 SQ High shipping with 25% reduction in shipping by 2040	Shipping region	-3.3	37.7	1.9	-26.3	13.6
	North Sea	-6.9	6.5	-2.3	-3.6	10.7

Between 2021 and 2040, marine traffic is reduced by 25% in the scenarios (shown in Figure 4.14). The negative effect of high levels of shipping on harbour porpoise and grey seals in the shipping lanes remains evident in the period 2021-2040 despite some recovery of harbour porpoise as traffic is reduced. The population biomass of grey seals and harbour seals (both northern and southern populations) increase which compensates for the local decrease prior to 2021 due to current shipping impacts. The small effect on harbour seal populations become negligible following traffic reduction (Figure 4.14 left). Notably, across the whole North Sea domain, the depletion of harbour porpoise leads to an overall increase in other mammal species as shipping impacts are reduced with the seal populations benefiting from the reduction of competitors (since each species share a >50% overlap of prey in their diets). The effect of the introduction of offshore wind farms without shipping leads (S3, purple lines in Figure 4.14) to a greater decline in the biomass of seals, but a relative increase in harbour porpoise (contrast S3, purple lines, with the three S2 scenarios). Nevertheless, the cumulative impact of offshore wind farms and shipping is negative for harbour porpoise (contrast S4, grey lines, with S3, purple lines in Figure 4.14).

Figure 4.14. Sensitivity of marine mammal biomass to shipping impacts (period before 2021) and reduction of shipping impacts (25% reduction between 2021-2040) under a changing climate (RCP4.5) with current fishing effort and marine protection in place. Change in human activities modelled according to scenario: S2 (three levels of shipping impact and no turbines), S4 (with medium impacts of turbines and shipping) and S3 (medium impact of turbines but no shipping).

Cumulative impact of shipping and offshore wind combined with EBFM measures, MPAs and restoration activities under a changing climate

The impacts of climate change are clear in the scenarios whether new EBFM measures (reduction in bycatch, discards and fishing effort to meet Maximum Sustainable Yield), new MPA or restoration activities are included. The RCP4.5 projection results in higher biomass of marine mammals (Figure 4.15a) than the RCP8.5 projection (used in Scenario 8). For harbour porpoise the addition of MPAs, to meet a 30% coverage of the North Sea by 2030, and EBFM measures with cumulative effects in Scenario 7 leads to an increase in biomass in wind farms with fixed turbines leading to an increase over the whole domain. In contrast, Scenario 4 with an increase in offshore wind farm coverage, a reduction in shipping and a RCP4.5 climate, but no new MPAs or EBFM measures, leads to stable biomass trajectory for harbour porpoise in the fixed wind turbine area in the southern North Sea and a gradual decrease overall. However, the biomass of harbour porpoise continues to decline in the National Enterprise scenario 8 with RCP8.5 projection limited increase in wind farm coverage and an increase in shipping, despite the addition of fully protected areas (no take zones) covering 7% of the North Sea (including 2% from the Western Dogger Bank closure) and highly protected areas (allowing only gears using hooks, pots, drift and fixed nets) covering an additional 5%. The biomass of each seal

population (grey seals, and harbour seals in the north and south) initially does improve in scenario 7, but ultimately the long-term effects of climate on the food web leads to declines in biomass between 2050 and 2100. For seabird functional groups, there is a long-term decline in the biomass of each group when MPAs and EBFM measures are introduced since this leads to a reduction in discards that have historically provided an important source of nutrition to seabirds (Figure 4.15b). Cumulative effects due to collisions with turbines and avoidance of wind farms lead to further declines. The National Enterprise scenario with cumulative effects (S8) leads to a worse outcome for surface-feeding seabirds than the Global Sustainability scenario with or without cumulative effects (S6 and S7), but the reverse is true for kittiwakes and diving seabirds in the long-term. For all fish groups (Figure 4.15c), the global sustainability scenario leads to highest biomass in the long term and cumulative impacts from shipping and offshore wind leads to small decreases that do not alter the benefits from the introduction of MPAs and EBFM measures. The worst outcomes for fish are in the National Enterprise scenario due to reduction in production at the base of the food web due to climate change impacts. There is a generally lower biomass in infaunal groups and epifaunal macrobenthos post-2050 relative to the 2020s, but there is considerable year-to-year variability (Figure 4.15d). A range of outcomes are evident for epifaunal groups with large crabs benefiting from the introduction of turbines and sustaining increases in the long-term despite climate change. Sessile epifauna and *Nephrops* initially increase, but the biomass of each group is reduced by 2100 in each scenario due to climate effects on the system that are not mitigated even by the extensive network of MPAs in Global and Fisheries Sustainability scenarios. Restoration of oysters in the Global Sustainability scenario (S6) leads to a 6% increase in biomass relative to the status quo scenario 1 in the 2050s, but with cumulative effects (S7) the increase in biomass grows to 19%. Similarly, S6 leads to an increase in mussels by 9% which grows to 12% with cumulative effects (S7). However, these increases to very little difference in biomass of groups other than oysters, when contrasted to Fisheries Sustainability with cumulative effects (S5).

Figure 4.15a. Time-series of biomass for key mammal functional groups for six scenarios with additional MPAs in S5-8 but no change in extent of MPAs in S1 & S4. Scenario 8 has a different climate projection to the rest and in this scenario shipping is increased between 2021 and 2050 by 33%.

Figure 4.15b. Time-series of biomass for seabird functional groups for six scenarios with additional MPAs in S5-8 but no change in extent of MPAs in S1 & S4. Scenario 8 has a different climate projection to the rest.

Figure 4.15c. Time-series of biomass for key functional groups of fish for six scenarios with additional MPAs in S5-8 but no change in extent of MPAs in S1 & S4. Scenario 8 has a different climate projection to the rest.

Figure 4.15d. Time-series of biomass for key functional groups of benthic fauna for six scenarios with additional MPAs in S5-8 but no change in extent of MPAs in S1 & S4. Scenario 8 has a different climate projection to the rest.

Impact of primary production and difference between scenarios of climate (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5) combined with MPA/EBFM management

The models of the North Sea ecosystem are driven here by Earth System Model projections that account for changes in temperature, salinity, oxygen and primary production rates of phytoplankton (Butenschön et al., 2024; Coll et al., 2024; Kristiansen et al., 2024). However, there is great uncertainty in the forecast of primary production from these models (Spence et al., 2022) so we also explore three of our scenarios (S1, 5, 8) with primary production constant post-2021 (i.e. S9, 10, 11) (Figure 4.16a-c). For the National Enterprise scenario with RCP8.5 projection and greatest decrease in primary production (S8), the constant primary production scenario (S11) shows generally higher biomass of benthic groups particularly in the northern floating wind turbine regions. In contrast the Fisheries Sustainability scenario (S5) with RCP4.5 climate trajectory is altered when primary production is fixed in the forecast (S10), but to a much lesser degree and in a variable direction. For the status-quo scenario with RCP4.5 projection (S1), the variable level of primary production leads to higher biomass of benthic groups (infauna and epifauna) over the constant primary production scenario (S9), with greatest impact in the northern North Sea, where floating turbines would be added, except in the final decade 2090s when biomass begins to decline.

Figure 4.16a. Time-series of biomass for key benthic groups for six scenarios, including additional MPAs in scenarios 5, 8, 10 and 11 but no change in MPAs in S1 & S9. Scenarios 8 and 11 only use RCP8.5 climate projections.

Figure 4.16b. Time-series of biomass for key fish species for six scenarios with additional MPAs in scenarios 5, 8, 10 and 11 but no change in extent of MPAs in S1 & S9. Scenarios 8 and 11 only use RCP8.5 climate projections.

Figure 4.16c. Time-series of biomass for mammals for six scenarios, including additional MPAs in scenarios 5, 8, 10 and 11 but no change in MPAs in S1 & S9. Scenarios 8 and 11 only use RCP8.5 climate projections.

4.3 EwE results - Central Baltic Sea

Fisheries management

In each scenario, the fishing effort of all fleets was reduced within existing MPAs, cod management area (i.e. cod box), and, where and when present, within offshore wind farms (Figure 4.17). Reductions in fishing effort leads to reductions in catch in the areas with fisheries restrictions (FPA or HPA) and potentially increases in catch in unprotected areas due to the displacement of fishing effort (e.g. as shown in the outputs from the status quo scenario, Figure 4.18). In all scenarios, fishery was guided with a cost layer based on historical effort (data from JRC). In the Fisheries Sustainability, Global Sustainability (GS) and National Enterprise (NE) scenarios, additional MPAs were added following the FutureMARES project scenarios (Coll et al., 2024) (Figures 4.19 and 4.20). All fishing fleets were excluded from Fully Protected Areas (FPAs) and offshore wind farms with floating wind turbines, while only small passive metiers (PAS0012 and PAS1218) were allowed to fish in the Highly Protected Areas (HPAs) and offshore wind farms with fixed wind turbines.

Figure 4.17. Fishery restrictions due to proportional coverage of cells by wind farms with fixed turbines impacting selected gears (left), floating turbines impacting all gears (middle) and other existing fisheries management (right) where the areas shown include restrictions for cod fishery. In the right panel, regions excluded from the Ecospace domain are also visible.

Figure 4.18. Changes in fishing effort in scenario 4 with RCP4.5 climate trajectory, additional turbines in 2030 and 2040 (fixed turbines - open polygons, floating turbines - hatched polygons) and 25% reduction in shipping traffic by 2040 (according to the GS scenario). Maps show average distribution of effort standardised to the 2020s (left, showing percentage of effort in each grid cell of the total effort over the whole domain) followed by change per grid cell (increases and decreases per cell relative to 2020s) by 2030s, 2050 and 2090s for selected fleets (metiers ACT1824 (active fleets 18-24m) (top), PEL1840 (pelagic fleets 18-24m) (middle) and PAS1840 (bottom)).

Figure 4.19. The change in distribution of fishing effort in Scenario 7 with RCP4.5 climate trajectory, new Marine Protected Areas for Global Sustainability (Highly Protected Areas, HPA open polygons, and Fully Protected Areas, FPA hatched polygons) to meet the 30x30 commitment, plus a decrease in fishing effort post-2030 and with new wind turbines in 2030 and 2040 and a reduction in vessel speed by 2050. Maps are shown for metiers ACT1824 (active fleets 18-24m) (top), PEL1840 (pelagic fleets 18-24m) (middle) and PAS1840 (bottom). The maps show the average distribution of effort in the 2020s reference period (left) followed by change in effort relative to the 2020s in 2030s, 2050s and 2090s.

Figure 4.20. The change in distribution of fishing effort for National Enterprise Scenario 8 with RCP4.5 climate trajectory, Marine Protected Areas (Highly Protected Areas, HPA open polygons, and Fully Protected Areas, FPA hatched polygons) and the addition of wind turbines (to 2030 only) and an increase in vessel traffic by 2040. Maps are shown for metiers ACT1824 (active fleets 18-24m) (top), PEL1840 (pelagic fleets 18-24m) (middle) and PAS1840 (passive fleets 18-40m)(bottom). The maps show the average distribution of effort in the 2020s reference period (left) followed by change in effort relative to the 2020s in 2030s, 2050s and 2090s.

Overall change in the biomass of functional groups by scenario

In each scenario, certain functional groups increase by 2050 relative to the 2020s (e.g., both adult and juvenile cod) due to the positive impacts of reduced climate change (RCP 4.5) and assumed reductions in nutrient emissions, while certain groups are expected to continue to decrease (meiobenthos, sprat and fish-feeding birds) due to the negative impacts of climate change as well as trophic interactions

(Figure 4.21). By 2090, the decreases continue for species impacted by climate (Figure 4.22). The National Enterprise scenario (NE), which uses a more extreme climate projection (RCP8.5), assumes reference level (current trajectory) nutrient emissions and an increase in fishing effort, shows opposite patterns than the RCP4.5 scenarios (Figure 4.21 and 4.23). In the NE scenario, sprat and flounder are increasing, conversely to cod, which is experiencing a drastic decline in biomass and catch (Figure 4.24). The decline is due to a combination of reduced reproductive volume in the main reproduction area (Gotland deep) and status-quo fishing effort levels. The biomass of grey seals is forced in the model and therefore it is not impacted by the scenarios.

Figure 4.21 Heatmap showing change in biomass of functional groups between 2050s and the 2020s for 11 scenarios for the Central Baltic Sea

Figure 4.22 Heatmap showing change in biomass of functional groups between 2090s and the 2020s for 11 scenarios for the Central Baltic Sea

Figure 4.23 Change in biomass of benthic groups over time for the 11 scenarios

Figure 4.24 Change in total catch of key fish species over time for 10 scenarios.

The overall changes in the ecosystem can be captured through ecosystem indicators as shown in Figure 4.25.

Figure 4.25 Change in ecosystem indicators relative to 2020s for 6 scenarios.

Notably, the biomass of predators, IUCN listed species and diversity metrics (Shannon index and Kempton’s-Q) increase in each scenario. However, the total biomass of the system decreases least in scenario 11 in which fishing levels are moderate with a high rate of climate change (RCP8.5), but in

which primary production is not allowed to vary, demonstrating the importance of this variable for the model. In the Baltic Sea the changes in primary production due to assumptions of nutrient emissions have important implications to the productivity of the system. In contrast, scenario 10 within greater protection from fishing, but a lower rate of climate change (RCP4.5) and in which primary production is not allowed to vary, does not result in an increase in total biomass of the system.

Impact of offshore wind turbines on functional group biomass

The impact of wind turbines on the biomass of functional groups is evident from the contrast of outcomes from scenario 3 simulations, with three variants of response to turbines by seabirds (high, medium and low avoidance and mortality responses) (Table 4.13). Furthermore, the contrast in these outcomes to scenario 1 (the climate status-quo without turbines or shipping), scenario 2 (medium response to shipping but no wind farms) and the cumulative effects scenario 4 (with medium responses to the impacts of turbines and shipping) can standardise these impacts for the effects of climate and reveal the cumulative impact of shipping and wind farms. In these scenarios, the model is driven by RCP4.5 climate projection with constant fishing effort in the future (equal to the most recent value) and marine protections (fisheries closures and MPAs) that are currently in place are kept post-2023. New offshore wind turbines are added between 2023 and 2040 according to the sustainability scenario in both S3 and S4, in the latter the impact of shipping on marine mammals is constant until a 25% decrease between 2021 to 2040.

Table 4.13. Sensitivity of seabird biomass to turbine impacts (collision and avoidance) along with key prey species biomass once standardised to Scenario 1 to exclude climate change impacts. Values give the percentage difference in biomass in the 2020s $[100 \times (S3_{bio} - S1_{bio})/S1_{bio}]$ between Scenario 1 (Status quo) and the three variants of Scenario 3 (with turbines).

Scenario comparison	Windfarm Area	Fish-feeding birds	Cod	Herring	Sprat	Flounder	Mytilus
S1 vs S3 Low	Fixed turbines	-39	56	31	7	42	-51
S1 vs S3 Medium		-61	29	10	12	29	-28
S1 vs S3 High		-73	19	12	15	24	-29
S1 vs S3 Low	Floating turbines	-41	71	67	1	22	-84
S1 vs S3 Medium		-64	46	60	5	4	-78
S1 vs S3 High		-78	53	61	7	13	-77
S1 vs S3 Low	Central Baltic Sea	-5	22	22	-5	13	-34
S1 vs S3 Medium		-8	5	6	-5	1	-6
S1 vs S3 High		-5	6	7	1	1	-5

The biomass of fish feeding birds decreases with increasing levels of offshore wind coverage due to collisions of birds within the regions despite the avoidance functional response (Figure 4.25). Relative to the status-quo Scenario 1, there is a decrease in the 2050s due to fixed turbines of between 39% and 73% of seabird functional group biomass in offshore wind farms and a similar impact due to floating turbines of between 41% and 78% of biomass in offshore wind farms (Table 4.13). As the extent of predicted wind farms in the Baltic Sea model domain is extensive (see Figure 4.17), the added mortality can also be detected at the whole model domain level.

Due to a reduction in fishing effort within the wind farms and an increase in artificial habitat from scour protection, the model simulates increases in the biomasses of some groups. Especially cod appears to respond to the added protection; the biomass increases in all wind farms areas and scenarios. Furthermore, other macrozoobenthos appears to benefit from the structures. Meiobenthos appears to experience the largest decline. Change over time in the biomasses of seabirds, selected fish and benthic functional groups is shown in Figure 4.25a-c and tabulated in Tables 4.14-4.16.

Figure 4.25a. Time-series of biomass for fish-feeding birds resulting from the model driven by RCP4.5 with current fishing effort and marine protection in place and change in offshore wind turbines and shipping route density according to three scenarios: S3 (three levels of impact of turbines), S4 (with medium impacts of turbines and shipping) and S2 (medium impact of shipping and no impact of turbines).

Figure 4.25b. Time-series of biomass for key functional groups of fish resulting from the model driven by RCP4.5 with current fishing effort and marine protection in place and change in offshore wind turbines and shipping route density according to three scenarios: S3 (three levels of impact of turbines), S4 (with medium impacts of turbines and shipping) and S2 (medium impact of shipping and no impact of turbines).

Figure 4.25c. Time-series of biomass for key functional groups of benthic fauna resulting from the model driven by RCP4.5 with current fishing effort and marine protection in place and change in offshore wind turbines and shipping route density according to three scenarios: S3 (three levels of impact of turbines), S4 (with medium impacts of turbines and shipping) and S2 (medium impact of shipping and no impact of turbines).

Table 4.14. Percentage change between 2050s and 2020s in the biomass of fish-feeding birds in the status quo scenario 1, three variants of the OWF scenario 3 and in the status quo with cumulative effects scenario 4 with medium response to OWF and shipping by spatial region – where the offshore wind farm extent (for fixed turbines, floating turbines and no turbines) is set at the full modelled coverage in 2050 across all scenarios (including S1 where no turbines are implemented).

Change over time by scenario	Spatial region	Fish-eating birds
S1 status quo (RCP4.5) and no change in human activities	no OWF region	-12.4
	fixed turbines	-7.0
	floating turbines	-18.1
	Central Baltic Sea	-12.3
S3 status quo (RCP4.5) with low response to offshore wind farms	no OWF region	-13.6
	fixed turbines	-44.8
	floating turbines	-52.8
	Central Baltic Sea	-17.9
S3 status quo (RCP4.5) with medium response to offshore wind farms	no OWF region	-12.1
	fixed turbines	-63.0
	floating turbines	-70.6
	Central Baltic Sea	-18.8
S3 status quo (RCP4.5) with high response to offshore wind farms	no OWF region	-11.0
	fixed turbines	-75.5
	floating turbines	-81.9
	Central Baltic Sea	-19.3
S4 status quo (RCP4.5) with cumulative impacts of offshore wind farms and shipping (both with medium responses)	no OWF region	-9.4
	fixed turbines	-62.4
	floating turbines	-70.1
	Central Baltic Sea	-16.3

Table 4.15. Percentage change between 2050s and 2020s in biomass of key benthic fauna in the status quo scenario 1, three variants of the offshore wind farm (scenario 3 and in the status quo with cumulative effects scenario 4 with medium response to turbines and shipping by region – where the OWF extent (for fixed turbines, floating turbines and no turbines) is set at the full modelled coverage in 2050 across all scenarios (including S1 where no turbines are implemented).

Change over time by scenario	Spatial region	<i>Saduria entomon</i>	<i>Mytilus</i>	Other macro-benthos	Meiobenthos
S1 status quo (RCP4.5) and no change in human activities	no OWF region	55.8	-8.9	10.0	-69.3
	fixed turbines	4.7	-7.3	0.1	-5.4
	floating turbines	355.2	-5.1	57.6	-84.8
	Central Baltic Sea	55.8	-8.6	11.4	-69.8
S3 status quo (RCP4.5) with medium response to OWF	no OWF region	52.7	-11.9	8.5	-70.4
	fixed turbines	-9.6	-35.0	7.7	-33.1
	floating turbines	15.3	-80.2	98.2	-97.7
	Central Baltic Sea	44.8	-16.3	12.4	-73.0
S4 status quo (RCP4.5) with cumulative effects to OWF and shipping (both medium responses)	no OWF region	57.2	-8.9	10.3	-69.3
	fixed turbines	-8.2	-33.7	8.9	-31.8
	floating turbines	18.1	-79.2	102.0	-97.6
	Central Baltic Sea	48.9	-13.6	14.2	-72.0

Table 4.16. Percentage change between 2050s and 2020s in biomass of key fish species in the status quo scenario 1, three variants of the OWF scenario 3 and in the status quo with cumulative effects scenario 4 with medium response to OWF and shipping by spatial region – where the offshore wind farm extent (for fixed turbines, floating turbines and no turbines) is set at the full modelled coverage in 2050 across all scenarios (including S1 where no turbines are implemented).

Change over time by scenario	Spatial region	Cod	Herring	Sprat	Flounder
S1 status quo (RCP4.5) and no change in human activities	no OWF region	582.3	5.0	-27.0	11.9
	fixed turbines	-32.0	-8.8	-1.8	-1.3
	floating turbines	886.0	20.0	-34.4	110.1
	Central Baltic Sea	530.1	4.8	-26.6	10.7
S3 status quo (RCP4.5) with medium response to OWF	no OWF region	561.6	4.3	-35.6	5.9
	fixed turbines	-16.4	-1.7	7.0	26.3
	floating turbines	1395.5	92.9	-34.3	145.1
	Central Baltic Sea	543.3	8.4	-33.8	9.3
S4 status quo (RCP4.5) with cumulative effects to OWF and shipping (medium responses)	no OWF region	590.3	7.9	-27.6	7.6
	fixed turbines	-14.9	5.9	11.8	27.2
	floating turbines	1396.5	94.6	-29.1	134.7
	Central Baltic Sea	570.9	12.4	-26.2	10.9

Impact of shipping

Change over time in the biomasses of marine mammal functional groups is shown in Figure 4.26. The period until 2021 has a constant level of shipping density and a therefore the difference between the three variants of Scenario 2 demonstrates the differing impacts of assumptions of collision risk and avoidance impacts on foraging. The sensitivity of grey seals, the only mammal group in the model, to these impacts are summarised in Tables 4.17 and 4.18.

Between 2021 and 2040, shipping traffic is reduced by 25% in the scenarios (shown in Figure 4.26). The negative effect of high levels of shipping on grey seals in the shipping lanes remains evident in the period 2021-2040. The population biomass of grey seals is following an increase which compensates for the local added mortality prior to 2021 due to current shipping impacts. Also, grey seal biomass is forced in the model and therefore the responses are likely to be unrealistically low.

Figure 4.26. Sensitivity of grey seal I biomass to shipping impacts (period before 2021) and reduction of shipping impacts (25% reduction between 2021-2040) under a changing climate (RCP4.5) with current fishing effort and marine protection in place. Change in human activities modelled according to scenario: S2 (three levels of shipping impact and no turbines), S4 (with medium impacts of turbines and shipping) and S3 (medium impact of turbines but no shipping). The grey seals are not responding to the shipping related mortality or avoidance since the group is forced.

Table 4.17. Sensitivity of mammal biomass to shipping impacts (collision and avoidance) once standardised to the status-quo scenario to exclude climate change impacts. Values give the percentage difference in biomass between the scenario in the 2020s [$100 \times (S2_{bio} - S1_{bio})/S1_{bio}$] between Scenario 1 (Status quo) and the three variants of Scenario 2 (with shipping).

Scenario comparison for Central Baltic Sea	Grey seals
S1 vs S2 SQ Low shipping	<1
S1 vs S2 SQ Med shipping	<1
S1 vs S2 SQ High shipping	<1

Table 4.18. Recovery of mammal biomass from shipping impacts (collision and avoidance) following reduction in shipping impacts by 25% by 2040 and in a warming climate (RCP4.5). Percentage change over time between 2050s and 2020s in the biomass of mammal species in three variants of the shipping S2 in the whole region and in the area impacted by shipping.

Scenario	Spatial region	Grey seals
S2 SQ Low shipping with 25% reduction in shipping by 2040	Shipping region	73.2
	Central Baltic Sea	75.2
S2 SQ Med shipping with 25% reduction in shipping by 2040	Shipping region	73.1
	Central Baltic Sea	75.2
S2 SQ High shipping with 25% reduction in shipping by 2040	Shipping region	73.4
	Central Baltic Sea	75.2

Cumulative impact of shipping and offshore wind combined with EBFM measures, MPAs and restoration activities under a changing climate

The impacts of climate change are clearly evident in the scenarios whether new EBFM measures (reduction in bycatch, discards and fishing effort to meet Maximum Sustainable Yield), new MPA or restoration activities are included. The RCP4.5 projection results in higher biomass of marine mammals (Figure 4.27a) than the RCP8.5 projection (used in Scenario 8).

Figure 4.27a. Time-series of biomass for grey seals for six scenarios with additional marine protected areas in S5-8 but no change in extent of MPAs in S1 & S4. Scenario 8 has a different climate projection to the rest and in this scenario shipping is increased between 2021 and 2050 by 33%. Note, the grey seal biomass is forced in the scenarios.

For seabird functional groups the results are linked to changes in primary productivity and added mortality due to wind farms and the interactions of these factors. In all scenarios including wind farms fish-feeding birds decrease in the wind farm areas (Figure 4.27b). But in the National Enterprise scenario with cumulative effects (S8) increase in primary production counteracts the impacts at the whole model domain level. The Global Sustainability scenario with or without cumulative effects (S6 and S7) results in a better outcome than SQ scenario.

Figure 4.27b. Time-series of biomass for fish-feeding birds for six scenarios with additional marine protected areas in S5-8 but no change in extent of MPAs in S1 & S4. Scenario 8 has a different climate projection to the rest.

Scenario 7, that includes Global Sustainability assumptions leads to an increase in biomass in wind farms with fixed turbines leading to an increase over the whole domain for cod (Figure 4.27c). In contrast, Scenario 4 with an increase in offshore wind farm coverage, a reduction in shipping and a RCP4.5 climate, but no new MPAs or EBFM measures, leads to much lower biomass trajectory. For all fish groups (Figure 4.27c), the global sustainability scenario leads to highest biomass in the long term and cumulative impacts from shipping and offshore wind leads to small decreases that do not alter the benefits from the introduction of MPAs and EBFM measures.

Figure 4.27c. Time-series of biomass for key functional groups of fish for six scenarios with additional marine protected areas in S5-8 but no change in extent of MPAs in S1 & S4. Scenario 8 has a different climate projection to the rest.

Figure 4.27d. Time-series of biomass for key functional groups of benthic fauna for six scenarios with additional MPAs in S5-8 but no change in extent of MPAs in S1 & S4. Scenario 8 has a different climate projection to the rest.

Impact of primary production and difference between scenarios of climate (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5) combined with MPA/EBFM management

The models driven here are making use of Earth System Model projections that account for changes in temperature, salinity, oxygen and primary production rates of phytoplankton. However, there is greater uncertainty in the forecast of primary production so we also explore three of our scenarios (S1, 5, 8) with constant primary production post-2021 (i.e. S9, 10, 11). For the Central Baltic Sea the interest is in these comparisons of the impacts of eutrophication control. For the National Enterprise scenario with RCP8.5 projection (S8), the outcomes for benthos, fish and mammals for the constant primary production scenario (S9) follows quite closely the trajectories in Scenario 1 (SQ) (Figure 4.28a-c). In contrast, the Fisheries Sustainability scenario (S5) with RCP4.5 climate trajectory is altered when primary production is fixed in the forecast (S10), but to a much lesser degree and in a variable direction. For the scenarios with RCP4.5 projection (S1, S5), the level of primary production leads to lower biomass of meiobenthos (Figure 4.28a) than the higher primary production (following RCP8.5) in the NE scenarios (S8). The corresponding scenarios without the effect of changes in primary production show a slight decrease in meiobenthos biomass. In the other benthic groups impact of primary production is less pronounced.

Figure 4.28a. Time-series of biomass for key benthic groups for six scenarios, including additional marine protected areas in scenarios 5, 8, 10 and 11 but no change in MPAs in S1 & S9. Scenarios 8 and 11 have RCP8.5 climate projections.

Figure 4.28b. Time-series of biomass for key fish species for six scenarios with additional marine protected areas in scenarios 5, 8, 10 and 11 but no change in extent of MPAs in S1 & S9. Scenarios 8 and 11 have RCP8.5 climate projections.

Figure 4.28c. Time-series of biomass for mammals for six scenarios for six scenarios, including additional marine protected areas in scenarios 5, 8, 10 and 11 but no change in MPAs in S1 & S9. Scenarios 8 and 11 have RCP8.5 climate projections.

4.4 EwE results - Finnish Archipelago Sea

Fisheries management

In each scenario, the fishing effort (days fishing) of fleets was reduced within existing MPAs (HPA), and, where present, within offshore wind farms (Figure 4.29). Reductions in fishing effort led to reductions in catch in those areas with fisheries restrictions and potentially increases in catch in unprotected areas due to the displacement of fishing effort (e.g. as shown in the outputs from the status quo scenario, Figure 4.30). In every scenario, all trawling and hunting was banned from existing MPAs (current enforcement). Furthermore, trawling was restricted to open sea areas based on catch and effort data from the area. In the fisheries sustainability, global sustainability (GS) and national enterprise (NE) scenarios, additional MPAs were added following the FutureMARES project scenarios (Coll et al., 2024) (Figures 4.31 and 4.32). All fishing fleets were excluded from Fully Protected Areas (FPAs), while only artisanal fleets (traps, recreational and lines) were allowed in the HPAs.

Current closures (HPA)

Fig 4.29. Fishery restrictions due to proportional coverage of cells by wind farms with fixed turbines impacting selected gears (left), floating turbines impacting all gears (middle) and other fisheries management, current MPAs (right).

Fig 4.30. Fishing effort in scenario 4 with RCP4.5 climate trajectory, additional turbines in 2030 and 2040 (fixed turbines - open polygons, floating turbines - hatched polygons) and 25% reduction in shipping traffic by 2040. Maps show average distribution of effort standardised to the 2020s (left, showing percentage of effort in each grid cell of the total over the whole domain) followed by change per grid cell (increases and decreases per cell relative to 2020s) by 2030s, 2050 and 2090s for pelagic trawlers (the central parts of the model domain do not include trawling)(top), traps (middle) and recreational fishery (bottom).

Fig 4.31. The distribution of fishing effort in Scenario 7 with RCP4.5 climate trajectory, new MPAs for Global Sustainability (Highly Protected Areas, HPA open polygons, and Fully Protected Areas, FPA hatched polygons) to meet the 30x30 commitment, plus a decrease in fishing effort post-2030 and with new wind turbines in 2030 and 2040 and a reduction in vessel speed by 2050. Maps are shown for pelagic trawlers (the central parts of the model domain do not include trawling)(top), traps (middle) and recreational fishery (bottom). The maps show the average distribution of effort in the 2020s reference period (left) followed by change in effort relative to the 2020s in 2030s, 2050 and 2090s.

Fig 4.32. The distribution of fishing effort for National Enterprise Scenario 8 with RCP4.5 climate trajectory, MPAs (Highly Protected Areas, HPA open polygons, and Fully Protected Areas, FPA hatched polygons) and the addition of wind turbines (to 2030 only) and an increase in vessel traffic by 2040. Maps are shown for pelagic trawlers (the central parts of the model domain do not include trawling)(top), traps (middle) and recreational fishery (bottom). The maps show the average distribution of effort in the 2020s reference period (left) followed by change in effort relative to the 2020s in 2030s, 2050 and 2090s.

Overall change in the biomass of functional groups by scenario

In each scenario, several functional groups increase by 2050 relative to the 2020s (*Fucus*, herring and *Mytilus*) due to the positive impacts of reduced climate change and nutrient reductions. Seal biomass keeps recovering towards carrying capacity as the hunting mortality is kept low. Several groups are also decreasing, most notably cod (Figure 4.33). Most scenarios assume a decrease in nutrient emissions, which leads to improved biomasses in the scenarios by 2090s. The differences between Global Sustainability and National Enterprise scenarios are exacerbated. The NE scenario uses a more

extreme climate projection (RCP8.5) and differs from the others that include the RCP4.5 projection (Figure 4.34).

Figure 4.33 Heatmap showing change in biomass of functional groups between 2050s and the 2020s for 11 scenarios for the Archipelago Sea.

Figure 4.34 Heatmap showing change in biomass of functional groups between 2090s and the 2020s for 11 scenarios for the Archipelago Sea.

Species benefiting from increased temperatures and more eutrophication include filamentous algae and sander. Conversely, herring shows the largest increase in GS scenario (Figures 4.35 and 4.37). The biomass of seals increases as a result of Ecosystem Based Management measures and the implementation of MPAs for 30% of surface area by 2030 when combined with cumulative effects, due to the further reduction in fishing effort in the offshore wind farm areas, with or without change in primary production included (Scenarios 5 and 10, Figure 4.36). Fisheries catches (Figure 4.38) largely reflect the fishing effort reductions (especially visible for heavily fished herring) and the amount of MPAs (both spatial protection and increase in OWF).

Figure 4.35 Biomass of key fish species over time for 10 scenarios.

Figure 4.36 Biomass of grey seals over time for 10 scenarios.

Figure 4.37 Change in biomass of benthic groups over time for 10 scenarios

Figure 4.38 Change in total catch of key fish species over time for 10 scenarios.

The overall changes in the ecosystem can be captured through ecosystem indicators as shown in Figure 4.39. Notably the biomass of predators, IUCN listed species and diversity metrics (Shannon index and Kempton’s-Q) remain the similar in each scenario. However, the total biomass of the system decreases in all scenarios, and the pattern is amplified in the GS scenario, probably reflecting the decrease in productivity due to nutrient reductions in all SQ and GS scenarios. This is highlighted with

the comparison to scenario 9 where the impact of primary production is removed. In the scenario 9 the total biomass remains highest.

Figure 4.39. Change in ecosystem indicators relative to 2020s for 6 scenarios.

Impact of offshore wind turbines on functional group biomass

The biomasses of seabird groups decrease within the wind farm areas (Figure 4.40a) due to additional mortality and avoidance, both parameterised in the model. However, in the model domain, the overall wind farm area is low (see Figure 4.29) and the impacts are not visible at the whole model domain scale. Relative to the status-quo Scenario 1, there is a decrease in the 2050s due to fixed turbines of between 33% and 79% of seabird functional groups' biomass in offshore wind farm areas and a similar impact due to floating turbines of between 24% and 57% of biomass in offshore wind farm areas (Table 4.19). Interestingly, the biomass of eider increases in the floating wind farms in the low mortality scenario. The greatest impact in the 2050s, relative to S1, is modelled on cormorants among farms with fixed turbines in the high response scenario and smallest impact on benthivorous birds among farms with floating turbines in the low response scenario. We also modelled a reduction in fishing effort within the wind farms and an increase in artificial habitat from scour protection. The impacts are generally minor (although *Mytilus* and herring benefit) and concentrate on the wind farm areas (Table 4.20 and Figure 4.40b-c). Change over time in the biomasses of seabirds, selected fish and benthic functional groups is shown in Figures 4.40a-c and tabulated in Tables 4.21-4.23.

Table 4.19. Sensitivity of seabird biomass to turbine impacts (collision and avoidance) along with key prey species biomass once standardised to the status-quo scenario to exclude climate change impacts. Values give the percentage difference in biomass between the scenario in the 2050s $[100 \times (S3_{bio} - S1_{bio})/S1_{bio}]$ between Scenario 1 (Status quo) and the three variants of Scenario 3 (with turbines).

Scenario comparison	Windfarm Area	Cormorant	Benthivorous birds	Perch	Sander	Herring	Mytilus
S1 vs S3 Low	Fixed turbines	-42	-33	-20	-2	35	43
S1 vs S3 Medium		-65	-60	-24	-4	35	44
S1 vs S3 High		-79	-77	-26	-5	35	44
S1 vs S3 Low	Floating turbines	-24	21	-23	5	55	26
S1 vs S3 Medium		-42	-15	-21	-2	55	26
S1 vs S3 High		-57	-47	-20	0	55	26
S1 vs S3 Low	Archipelago Sea	<1	<1	-3	0	10	4
S1 vs S3 Medium		<1	<1	-3	0	10	4
S1 vs S3 High		<1	<1	-5	-2	10	5

Table 4.20. Percentage change in biomass of selected fish species through fisheries and foodweb responses to turbine impacts once standardised to the status-quo scenario to exclude climate change impacts. Values give the percentage difference in biomass in the 2020s $[100 \times (S3_{bio} - S1_{bio})/S1_{bio}]$ between Scenario 1 (Status quo) and the three variants of Scenario 3 (with turbines). Note outputs for S3 with high and low responses of fish are identical for these groups.

Scenario comparison	Windfarm Area	Sander	Perch	Herring	Sprat	Benth. fish	Mytilus
S1 vs S3 medium	Fixed turbines	-4	-24	35	-3	-12	44
S1 vs S3 medium	Floating turbines	-2	-21	55	-9	-28	26
S1 vs S3 medium	Archipelago Sea	-1.7	-4	10	-2	-5	4

Figure 4.40a. Time-series of biomass for seabird functional groups resulting from the model driven by RCP4.5 with current fishing effort and marine protection in place and change in offshore wind turbines and shipping route density according to three scenarios: S3 (three levels of impact of turbines), S4 (with medium impacts of turbines and shipping) and S2 (medium impact of shipping and no impact of turbines).

Figure 4.40b. Time-series of biomass for key functional groups of fish resulting from the model driven by RCP4.5 with current fishing effort and marine protection in place and change in offshore wind turbines and shipping route density according to three scenarios: S3 (three levels of impact of turbines), S4 (with medium impacts of turbines and shipping) and S2 (medium impact of shipping and no impact of turbines).

Figure 4.40c. Time-series of biomass for key functional groups of benthic fauna resulting from the model driven by RCP4.5 with current fishing effort and marine protection in place and change in offshore wind turbines and shipping route density according to three scenarios: S3 (three levels of impact of turbines), S4 (with medium impacts of turbines and shipping) and S2 (medium impact of shipping and no impact of turbines).

Table 4.21. Percentage change between 2050s and 2020s in the biomass of seabirds in the status quo scenario 1, three variants of the OWF scenario 3 and in the status quo with cumulative effects scenario 4 with medium response to OWF and shipping by spatial region – where the offshore wind farm extent (for fixed turbines, floating turbines and no turbines) is set at the full modelled coverage in 2050 across all scenarios (including S1 where no turbines are implemented).

Change over time by scenario	Spatial region	Benthivorous birds	Cormorants
S1 status quo (RCP4.5) and no change in human activities	no OWF region	1.0	0.1
	fixed turbines	-3.9	-2.2
	floating turbines	-34.4	-3.2
	Archipelago Sea	0.0	0.0
S3 status quo (RCP4.5) with low response to offshore windfarms	no OWF region	2.4	0.5
	fixed turbines	-43.8	-35.8
	floating turbines	-50.3	15.6
	Archipelago Sea	0.0	0.0
S3 status quo (RCP4.5) with medium response to offshore windfarms	no OWF region	3.3	1.3
	fixed turbines	-66.2	-61.8
	floating turbines	-61.9	-18.5
	Archipelago Sea	0.0	0.0
S3 status quo (RCP4.5) with high response to offshore windfarms	no OWF region	3.9	1.9
	fixed turbines	-79.7	-78.0
	floating turbines	-72.1	-48.9
	Archipelago Sea	0.0	0.0
S4 status quo (RCP4.5) with cumulative effects of offshore windfarms and shipping (both with medium responses)	no OWF region	3.3	1.3
	fixed turbines	-66.1	-61.9
	floating turbines	-61.7	-18.6
	Archipelago Sea	0.0	0.0

Table 4.22. Percentage change between 2050s and 2020s in biomass of key benthic fauna in the status quo scenario 1, three variants of the OWF scenario 3 and in the status quo with cumulative effects scenario 4 with medium response to OWF and shipping by spatial region – where the offshore wind farm extent (for fixed turbines, floating turbines and no turbines) is set at the full modelled coverage in 2050 across all scenarios (including S1 where no turbines are implemented).

Change over time by scenario	Spatial region	Pred. benthos	Mytilus	Benthic bivalves	Other benthos	Filamentous algae	R. harrisi
S1 status quo (RCP4.5) with no change in human activities	no OWF region	-3.8	16.6	19.0	2.3	-14.2	1.0
	fixed turbines	-0.7	11.6	15.7	3.6	-31.1	-31.4
	floating turbines	0.0	22.5	19.8	8.6	-3.6	-31.0
	Archipelago Sea	-3.4	16.7	18.9	2.9	-14.8	0.0
S3 status quo (RCP4.5) with medium response to OWF	no OWF region	-3.5	13.7	19.6	2.3	-16.7	1.2
	fixed turbines	111.6	57.5	-57.5	-64.9	-25.3	-25.0
	floating turbines	5.8	53.0	-77.2	-93.8	-5.4	-23.3
	Archipelago Sea	9.3	19.2	7.1	-9.4	-16.8	0.0
S4 status quo (RCP4.5) with medium response to OWF and shipping	no OWF region	-3.6	14.6	19.9	2.4	-16.8	1.2
	fixed turbines	111.5	57.8	-57.5	-64.9	-25.3	-25.3
	floating turbines	5.7	53.7	-77.2	-93.8	-5.4	-23.7
	Archipelago Sea	9.2	20.1	7.4	-9.4	-16.8	0.0

Table 4.23. Percentage change between 2050s and 2020s in biomass of key fish species in the status quo scenario 1, three variants of the OWF scenario 3 and in the status quo with cumulative effects scenario 4 with medium response to OWF and shipping by spatial region – where the offshore wind farm extent (for fixed turbines, floating turbines and no turbines) is set at the full modelled coverage in 2050 across all scenarios (including S1 where no turbines are implemented).

Change over time by scenario	Spatial region	Cod	Sander	Perch	Benthivorous fish	Herring	Sprat
S1 status quo (RCP4.5) and no change in human activities	no OWF region	-46.0	-22.9	-10.9	11.3	12.6	0.3
	fixed turbines	-49.7	-27.9	-18.4	7.1	19.4	0.7
	floating turbines	-42.5	-8.2	-21.3	12.4	20.4	8.6
	Archipelago Sea	-45.7	-22.5	-12.8	11.1	13.7	1.1
S3 status quo (RCP4.5) with medium response to offshore windfarms	no OWF region	-46.0	-23.5	-13.6	10.1	8.4	0.4
	fixed turbines	-49.7	-31.2	-34.8	-4.6	40.5	-1.7
	floating turbines	-42.5	-10.3	-39.4	-18.4	66.7	0.3
	Archipelago Sea	-45.7	-23.3	-18.4	6.3	16.4	0.2
S4 status quo (RCP4.5) with medium responses to offshore windfarms and shipping	no OWF region	-46.0	-25.3	-10.9	10.3	8.3	0.4
	fixed turbines	-49.7	-27.7	-38.1	-5.9	40.0	-1.7
	floating turbines	-42.5	-5.3	-35.4	-19.5	66.3	0.3
	Archipelago Sea	-45.7	-24.6	-16.1	6.2	16.3	0.3

Impact of shipping

Change over time in the biomass of the grey seals is shown in Figure 4.41. The period until 2021 has a constant level of shipping density and therefore the difference between the three variants of Scenario 2 demonstrates the differing impacts of assumptions of collision risk and avoidance impacts on foraging. The sensitivity of seals to these impacts is summarised in Table 4.24 (and recovery in Table 4.25), where each group is impacted most in the high shipping scenario. The impact was evident for seals (up to 36% decrease in total biomass). Little detrimental change is evident in fish, seabird or benthic functional groups due to shipping as groups generally increased as a result of reductions in seal predation.

Between 2021 and 2040, shipping traffic is reduced by 25% in the scenarios (shown in Figure 4.41). The negative effect of high levels of shipping on seals in the shipping lanes remains evident in the period 2021-2040. The effect of the introduction of offshore wind farms without shipping leads (S3, purple lines in Figure 4.41) to a decline in the biomass of seals (contrast S3, purple lines, with the three S2 scenarios).

Figure 4.41. Sensitivity of marine mammal biomass to shipping impacts (period before 2021) and reduction of shipping impacts (25% reduction between 2021-2040) under a changing climate (RCP4.5) with current fishing effort and marine protection in place. Change in human activities modelled according to scenario: S2 (three levels of shipping impact and no turbines), S4 (with medium impacts of turbines and shipping) and S3 (medium impact of turbines but no shipping).

Table 4.24 Sensitivity of mammal biomass to shipping impacts (collision and avoidance) once standardised to the status-quo scenario to exclude climate change impacts. Values give the percentage difference in biomass between the scenario in the 2020s [$100 \times (S2_{bio} - S1_{bio})/S1_{bio}$] between Scenario 1 (Status quo) and the three variants of Scenario 2 (with shipping).

Scenario comparison for Archipelago Sea	Seals
S1 vs S2 SQ Low shipping	0.5
S1 vs S2 SQ Med shipping	11.5
S1 vs S2 SQ High shipping	-9.1

Table 4.25. Recovery of mammal biomass from shipping impacts (collision and avoidance) following reduction in shipping impacts by 25% by 2040 and in a warming climate (RCP4.5). Percentage change over time between 2050s and 2020s in the biomass of mammal species in three variants of the shipping S2 in the whole region and in the area impacted by shipping.

Scenario	Spatial region	Seals
S2 SQ Low shipping with 25% reduction in shipping by 2040	Shipping region	63.8
	Archipelago Sea	63.3
S2 SQ Med shipping with 25% reduction in shipping by 2040	Shipping region	34.3
	Archipelago Sea	34.4
S2 SQ High shipping with 25% reduction in shipping by 2040	Shipping region	55.7
	Archipelago Sea	56.2

Cumulative impact of shipping and offshore wind combined with EBFM measures, MPAs and restoration activities under a changing climate

The impact of climate change is clear when comparing scenarios where new EBFM measures (reduction in bycatch, discards and fishing effort to meet Maximum Sustainable Yield), new MPA or restoration activities are included in scenarios with RCP4.5. In the Central Baltic Sea, the nutrient reduction scenarios play an important role defining the level of primary production. The RCP4.5 projection results in lower biomass of marine mammals (Figure 4.42a) than the RCP8.5 projection (used in Scenario 8) likely due to a difference in primary productivity that cascades to the top predators. In contrast, Scenario 4 with an increase in offshore wind farm coverage, a reduction in shipping and a RCP4.5 climate, but no new MPAs or EBFM measures, leads to stable biomass trajectory

The National Enterprise scenario with cumulative effects (S8) leads to a worse outcome for cormorants than the Global Sustainability scenario with or without cumulative effects (S6 and S7), but the impacts aren't visible in the whole domain scale (Figure 4.42b). For many fish groups (Figure 4.42c), the global sustainability scenario leads to highest biomass in the long term and cumulative impacts from shipping and offshore wind leads to small decreases that do not alter the benefits from the introduction of MPAs and EBFM measures. The worst outcomes for most fish are in the National Enterprise scenario due to high fishing effort, and low spatial protection. Some fish groups such as sander benefit from the warming. The benthic groups show variable responses that are shaped by climate change, eutrophication, added or removed habitat due to OWF and trophic relationships (Figure 4.42d). Furthermore, the groups that benefit from eutrophication and warming such as annual filamentous algae, show increase in the NE scenario.

Figure 4.42a. Time-series of biomass for seals for six scenarios with additional marine protected areas in S5-8 but no change in extent of MPAs in S1 & S4. Scenario 8 has a different climate projection to the rest and in this scenario shipping is increased between 2021 and 2050 by 33%.

Figure 4.42b. Time-series of biomass for seabird functional groups for six scenarios with additional MPAs in S5-8 but no change in extent of MPAs in S1 & S4. Scenario 8 has a different climate projection than the rest.

Figure 4.42c. Time-series of biomass for key functional groups of fish for six scenarios with additional MPAs in S5-8 but no change in extent of MPAs in S1 & S4. Scenario 8 has a different climate projection to the rest.

Figure 4.42d. Time-series of biomass for key functional groups of benthic fauna for six scenarios with additional MPAs in S5-8 but no change in extent of MPAs in S1 & S4. Scenario 8 has a different climate projection to the rest.

Impact of primary production and difference between scenarios of climate (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5) combined with MPA/EBFM management

The models driven here are making use of Earth System Model projections that account for changes in temperature, salinity, oxygen and primary production rates of phytoplankton. However, there is greater uncertainty in the forecast of primary production, so we also explore three of our scenarios (S1, 5, 8) with constant primary production post-2021 (i.e. S9, 10, 11). For the Archipelago Sea the pattern is similar to the Central Baltic Sea case study. The scenarios SQ and GS expect decline in the nutrient emissions that leads in decreased primary production, which cascades to the total biomass level (see also Figure 4.43).

Figure 4.43a. Time-series of biomass for key benthic groups for six scenarios, including additional MPAs in scenarios 5, 8, 10 and 11 but no change in MPAs in S1 & S9. Scenarios 8 and 11 have RCP8.5 climate projections.

Figure 4.43b. Time-series of biomass for key fish species for six scenarios with additional MPAs in scenarios 5, 8, 10 and 11 but no change in extent of MPAs in S1 & S9. Scenarios 8 and 11 have RCP8.5 climate projections.

Figure 4.43c. Time-series of biomass for mammals for six scenarios for six scenarios, including additional MPAs in scenarios 5, 8, 10 and 11 but no change in MPAs in S1 & S9. Scenarios 8 and 11 have RCP8.5 climate projections.

4.5 EwE results - Western Mediterranean Sea

Fisheries management

The Western Mediterranean simulations included fisheries restrictions due to MPAs and fisheries management initiatives in place or in future scenarios (Status Quo, Global Sustainability - GS - or National Enterprise - NE -) or, when present, due to offshore wind farms (Figure 4.44). Species were also impacted by the presence of shipping activity in scenarios with shipping and cumulative impacts (Figure 4.45).

Figure 4.44. Fishery restrictions due to proportional coverage of cells by fisheries management for the status quo (A) and Global Sustainability (B) scenarios, where the areas shown include Fully Protected Areas (FPAs), Highly Protected Areas (HPAs), Medium Protected Areas (MPAs), Gulf of Lions permanent and temporal restrictions, National Fisheries Restricted Areas (FRAs) and the restriction below 1000 m to bottom trawling for the whole region, and (C) wind farms with fixed turbines impacting selected gears and (D) floating turbines impacting all gears.

Figure 4.45. Shipping activity included in the analysis. (A) Route density regions, where main activity is located, (B) Shipping activity in 2023; (C) Shipping activity under Global Sustainability scenario in 2024; (D) Shipping activity under National Enterprise Scenario in 2024.

Overall, fishing effort restrictions within these protected areas lead to reductions in catch in protected areas, especially under Fisheries Sustainability and Global Sustainability scenarios, and potentially increases in catch in unprotected areas due to the displacement of fishing effort (Figure 4.46 and 4.47). Reductions in catches were smaller under the National Enterprise scenarios where protected areas were smaller (Figure 4.48). All fleets are excluded from FPAs while in HPAs artisanal and recreational fleets are allowed in.

Figure 4.46. Fishing effort in scenario 4 with RCP4.5 climate trajectory, additional turbines in 2030 and 2040 (fixed turbines - open polygons, floating turbines - hatched polygons) and 25% reduction in marine traffic by 2040. Maps show average distribution of effort standardised to the 2020s (left, showing percentage of effort in each grid cell of the total over the whole domain) followed by change per grid cell (increases and decreases per cell relative to 2020s) by 2030s, 2050 and 2090s for Bottom trawlers (A), Seiners and mid-water trawlers (B), Longliners (C) and Artisanal fleet (D).

Figure 4.47. The distribution of fishing effort in Scenario 7 with RCP4.5 climate trajectory, new Marine Protected Areas for Global Sustainability (Highly Protected Areas, HPA open polygons, and Fully Protected Areas, FPA hatched polygons) to meet the 30x30 commitment, plus a decrease in fishing effort post-2030 and with new wind turbines in 2030 and 2040 and a reduction in vessel speed by 2050. Maps are shown for Bottom trawlers (A), Seiners and mid-water trawlers (B), Longliners (C) and Artisanal fleet (D). The maps show the average distribution of effort in the 2020s reference period (left) followed by change in effort relative to the 2020s in 2030s, 2050 and 2090s.

Figure 4.48. The distribution of fishing effort for National Enterprise Scenario 8 with RCP4.5 climate trajectory, MPAs (Highly Protected Areas, HPA open polygons, and Fully Protected Areas, FPA hatched polygons) and the addition of wind turbines (to 2030 only) and an increase in marine traffic by 2040. Maps are shown for Bottom trawlers (A), Seiners and mid-water trawlers (B), Longliners (C) and Artisanal fleet (D). The maps show the average distribution of effort in the 2020s reference period (left) followed by change in effort relative to the 2020s in 2030s, 2050 and 2090s.

Overall change in the biomass of functional groups by scenario

The biomass trajectories for functional groups of the Western Mediterranean Sea model showed declines and increased in 2050 relative to the 2020s due to the negative and positive impacts of climate change and human interventions (Figure 4.49). Several fish and invertebrate species declined, such as small pelagic fish like European sardine or coastal fish such as common two-banded seabream, under status quo and cumulative impacts scenarios. These declines were partially reverted under fisheries sustainability and global sustainability scenarios (scenario S5 and S6), even when cumulative impacts of shipping and wind farms were included (scenario S7). The National enterprise scenario (S8) showed intermediate results. Those scenarios including the cumulative impacts of shipping and windfarms showed added effects on specific groups such as Common two-banded seabream or macrobenthos in comparison with the impact of fishing and management interventions (S2, S3 and

S4). On the long run, overall declines were less profound, while the impacts of management were still evident in the rebuilding of several organisms (Figure 4.50). The impacts of maintaining primary production constant showed impacts in specific groups, such as in groupers, white seabream, and common two-banded seabream.

Figure 4.49. Heatmap showing change in biomass of functional groups between 2050s and the 2020s for 11 scenarios in the Western Mediterranean Sea model.

Figure 4.50 Heatmap showing change in biomass of functional groups between 2090s and the 2020s for 11 scenarios in the Western Mediterranean Sea model.

The biomass trends of key species showed contrasting results between scenarios (Figure 4.51 to 4.55). For example, some fish species showed non-recoveries under status quo or cumulative effects (S1 and S4) but increases in biomass under Fisheries Sustainability (S5 and S10), and Global Sustainability with cumulative effects (S7). Under National Enterprise (S8 and S11), some species reacted positively increasing their biomass (European anchovy, European hake and Groupers). Fish did not show important changes between floating windfarm and fixed windfarm regions, except groupers, which seemed to be benefiting most from fixed windfarm regions under the Fisheries sustainability with cumulative effects, S5 (Figure 4.51). The response of key invertebrates was mixed (Figure 4.52). While some invertebrates increased under Fisheries Sustainability and Global Sustainability scenarios (such as Deep-water Rose shrimp and Purple sea urchin, S5 and S6), others did under cumulative effects (such as Blue and Red shrimp, European lobster and coastal benthic cephalopods, S4 and S8). Interestingly, Norway lobster seemed to benefit from cumulative effects of wind farms (Figure 4.52). Marine mammals also show mixed results (Figure 4.53). While some clearly benefited from Fisheries and Global Sustainability (such as bottlenose dolphins and monk seals), others showed larger biomass trajectories under status quo or cumulative effects, such as loggerhead turtles. Interestingly, the endangered monk seal was projected to slightly benefit in fixed windfarm regions (Figure 4.53). Seabirds, on the contrary, showed increasing trends under National Enterprise, probably due to increasing accessibility to discards, and endangered and pelagic seabirds showed declines in windfarm regions (Figure 4.54). Biomass trends of Habitat Forming Species showed contracting results overall, and also between floating and fixed windfarm regions (Figure 4.55). For example, seaweeds declined overall, although less within the fixed windfarm regions, while seagrass mainly increase in floating windfarm regions and decline in fixed ones.

Catch trends of key fish species showed contracting results (Figure 4.55), similar to biomass trends (Figure 4.51). Large increases of catches were predicted under status quo and national enterprise scenarios, except for European sardine. However, under Fisheries sustainability catches were predicted to increase, especially within windfarm regions and for pelagic species (Figure 4.56). The catch of invertebrate species was high specially under national enterprise and cumulative effects, and especially within fixed windfarm regions (Figure 4.57).

The overall changes in the ecosystem were studied when looking at system indicators (Figure 4.58). Under the Fisheries sustainability scenarios (S5 and S10), the IUCN species biomass, the predatory biomass and the total biomass were the largest in 2050 in comparison with 2020. On the contrary, biodiversity indicators showed little change between scenarios, although larger values were also shown for Fisheries sustainability scenarios. The MTI indicator declined with Fisheries sustainability.

Figure 4.51. Biomass of key fish species over time for 10 scenarios in the Western Mediterranean Sea.

Figure 4.52. Biomass of key invertebrate species over time for 10 scenarios in the Western Mediterranean Sea.

Figure 4.53. Biomass of mammals and turtle over time for 10 scenarios in the Western Mediterranean Sea.

Figure 4.54. Biomass of seabird species over time for 10 scenarios in the Western Mediterranean Sea.

Figure 4.55. Biomass of habitat forming species over time for 10 scenarios in the Western Mediterranean Sea.

Figure 4.56. Change in total catch of key fish species over time for 10 scenarios in the Western Mediterranean Sea.

Figure 4.57. Change in total catch of key fish species over time for 10 scenarios in the Western Mediterranean Sea.

Figure 4.59. Change in ecosystem indicators in 2050s relative to 2020s for 6 scenarios in the Western Mediterranean Sea.

Impact of offshore wind and shipping

The impact of offshore windfarms on seabirds was projected to be higher under the high impact scenario (Figure 4.60), especially for endangered and pelagic seabirds which reacted strongly to high levels of effects (Figure 4.60 and Table 4.26). This impact was larger in the regions with fixed wind turbines (42% decrease in biomass relative to scenario 1) than the regions with floating wind turbines

(36% decrease), but it was very low (<2% change in biomass relative to scenario 1) across the whole model domain.

Table 4.26. Sensitivity of seabird biomass to turbine impacts (collision and avoidance) along with key prey species biomass once standardised to Scenario 1 to exclude climate change impacts. Values give the percentage difference in biomass in the 2050s [$100 \times (S3_{bio} - S1_{bio})/S1_{bio}$] between Scenario 1 (Status quo) and the three variants of Scenario 3 (with turbines).

Scenario comparison	Windfarm Area	Pel. & end. Seabirds	Gulls & Cormorants.	Terns	Sardines	Anchovies	Macrozoop.
S1 vs S3 Low	Fixed turbines	-8.25	7.73	-1.41	-6.22	-0.75	-6.90
S1 vs S3 Medium		-25.45	-16.26	-19.08	-4.17	-0.13	-6.89
S1 vs S3 High		-42.11	-37.86	-36.64	-4.61	-0.09	-6.91
S1 vs S3 Low	Floating turbines	-10.22	-7.78	-9.39	-1.26	0.99	-1.22
S1 vs S3 Medium		-22.80	-19.32	-19.34	-1.47	0.82	-1.22
S1 vs S3 High		-35.61	-30.52	-30.08	-0.79	0.50	-1.22
S1 vs S3 Low	Western Mediterranean	0.77	0.36	-0.48	0.77	0.21	0.23
S1 vs S3 Medium		-0.05	0.08	-0.87	1.24	0.10	0.23
S1 vs S3 High		-0.86	-0.37	-1.36	0.84	0.19	0.23

Figure 4.60. Time-series of biomass for seabird functional groups resulting from the model driven by RCP4.5 with current fishing effort and marine protection in place and change in offshore wind turbines and shipping route density according to three scenarios: S3 (three levels of impact of turbines), S4 (with medium impacts of turbines and shipping) and S2 (medium impact of shipping and no impact of turbines).

Other organisms such as fish, invertebrates and marine mammals had mixed effects from different levels of windfarm impacts (Figure 4.61-63, and Tables 4.27-4.28) with decreases in groupers and monk seals but increases in coastal benthic cephalopods. The impact of shipping was low for seabirds (<4% difference in the 2020s relative to scenario 1 that did not include shipping routes) (Figure 4.60).

The greatest impacts of shipping were found for deep sea-cetacean feeders (up to 5% decrease in 2020s with a high response to shipping relative to S1) and Loggerhead turtles (up to 10% decrease in 2020s relative to S1) only showed small impacts (Figure 4.63 and Table 4.28).

Figure 4.61. Time-series of biomass for key functional groups of fish resulting from the model driven by RCP4.5 with current fishing effort and marine protection in place and change in offshore wind turbines and shipping route density according to three scenarios: S3 (three levels of impact of turbines), S4 (with medium impacts of turbines and shipping) and S2 (medium impact of shipping and no impact of turbines).

Figure 4.62. Time-series of biomass for key functional groups of benthic fauna resulting from the model driven by RCP4.5 with current fishing effort and marine protection in place and change in offshore wind turbines and shipping route density according to three scenarios: S3 (three levels of impact of turbines), S4 (with medium impacts of turbines and shipping) and S2 (medium impact of shipping and no impact of turbines).

Figure 4.63. Sensitivity of marine mammal biomass to shipping impacts (period before 2021) and reduction of shipping impacts (25% reduction between 2021-2040) under a changing climate (RCP4.5) with current fishing effort and marine protection in place. Change in human activities modelled according to scenario: S2 (three levels of shipping impact and no turbines), S4 (with medium impacts of turbines and shipping) and S3 (medium impact of turbines but no shipping).

Table 4.27 Percentage change in biomass of selected fish, turtles and mammal species through fisheries and foodweb responses to turbine impacts once standardised to Scenario 1 to exclude climate change impacts. Values give the percentage difference in biomass in the 2020s $[100 \times (S3bio - S1bio)/S1bio]$ between Scenario 1 (Status quo) and the three variants of Scenario 3 (with turbines). Note outputs for S3 with high and low responses of fish are identical for these groups.

Scenario comparison	Windfarm Area	Coastal benthic cephalopods	European hake adult	Groupers	Loggerhead turtles	Monk seals
S1 vs S3 Medium	Fixed turbines	1044.00	-4.34	-12.96	4.85	-6.05
S1 vs S3 Medium	Floating turbines	211.19	-0.07	-41.95	2.05	-12.06
S1 vs S3 Medium	Western Mediterranean	21.99	0.08	-33.49	-2.81	-6.53

Table 4.28. Sensitivity of mammal and turtle biomass to shipping impacts (collision and avoidance) once standardised to Scenario 1 to exclude climate change impacts. Values give the percentage difference in biomass in the 2020s $[100 \times (S2bio - S1bio)/S1bio]$ between Scenario 1 (Status quo) and the three variants of Scenario 2 (with shipping).

Scenario comparison	Bottlenose dolphins	Deep sea-cetacean feeders	Fin whale	Loggerhead turtles	Monk seals	Short-beaked common dolphin
S1 vs S2 SQ Low shipping	3	-3	2	-8	20	3
S1 vs S2 SQ Med shipping	3	-3	2	-8	17	3
S1 vs S2 SQ High shipping	1	-5	1	-10	9	1

Cumulative impact of shipping and offshore wind combined with EBFM measures, MPAs and restoration activities under a changing climate

Overall, the impact of cumulative effects of windfarms and shipping, on top of climate change and fisheries, were low for key fish species (Figure 4.64). The exceptions were groupers, which showed lower levels of biomass under status quo without cumulative impacts than with cumulative impacts (S1 and S4). Within the Global Sustainability scenarios (S6 and S7) the differences in projected biomass are minimal. In case of key invertebrate species, coastal benthic cephalopods seem to benefit from cumulative impacts (Figure 4.65), both inside windfarm regions and outside. On the contrary, other species such as purple sea urchin, seem to react to cumulative impacts both under status quo scenarios and sustainability scenarios. Top predators did not show strong effects of cumulative impacts (Figure 4.66), with the exception of loggerhead turtles and monk seals, which showed small differences between scenarios including the impact of shipping and offshore wind or not. Seabirds, on the contrary, showed larger impacts of cumulative shipping and offshore wind on top of status quo activities (Figure 4.67), especially endangered and pelagic seabirds.

Figure 4.64. Time-series of biomass for key functional groups of fish for six scenarios with additional MPAs in S5-8 but no change in extent of MPAs in S1 & S4. Scenario 8 has a difference climate projection to the rest.

Figure 4.65. Time-series of biomass for key benthic groups for six scenarios with additional MPAs in S5-8 but no change in extent of MPAs in S1 & S4. Scenario 8 has a different climate projection (RCP8.5) to the others (RCP4.5).

Figure 4.66. Time-series of biomass for key top predators for six scenarios with additional MPAs in S5-8 but no change in extent of MPAs in S1 & S4. Scenario 8 has a different climate projection to the rest and in this scenario shipping is increased between 2021 and 2050 by 33%.

Figure 4.67. Time-series of biomass for seabird groups for six scenarios with additional MPAs in S5-8 but no change in extent of MPAs in S1 & S4. Scenario 8 has a different climate projection (RCP8.5) to the others (RCP4.5).

Impact of primary production and difference between scenarios of climate (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5) combined with MPA/EBFM management

Due to the uncertainty in projections of primary production, it is relevant to investigate the impact of primary production dynamics in modelling simulations. Regarding key fish species (Figure 4.68), similar results were projected for both status quo scenarios (S1 and S9) and national enterprise (S8 and S11), while larger impacts are seen under Fisheries sustainability scenarios (S5 and S10) (Figure 4.68-70). These were especially relevant for groupers, which may reflect the impact of primary production in coastal areas and for coastal species. This is also observed for invertebrate species such as coastal benthic cephalopods and purple sea urchin (Figure 4.69). The impact of primary production dynamics into projections were also evident for loggerhead turtles and to a less extent for monk seals (Figure 4.70) but were less evident for other marine mammals (Figure 4.70).

Figure 4.68. Time-series of biomass for key fish species for six scenarios with additional MPAs in scenarios 5, 8, 10 and 11 but no change in extent of MPAs in S1 & S9. Scenarios 8 and 11 only use the RCP8.5 climate projection.

Figure 4.69. Time-series of biomass for key benthic groups for six scenarios, including additional MPAs in scenarios 5, 8, 10 and 11 but no change in MPAs in S1 & S9. Scenarios 8 and 11 only use the RCP8.5 climate projections.

Figure 4.70. Time-series of biomass for top predators for six scenarios, including additional MPAs in scenarios 5, 8, 10 and 11 but no change in MPAs in S1 & S9. Scenarios 8 and 11 only use the RCP8.5 climate projections.

4.6 EwE results - Bay of Biscay

Fisheries management

In each scenario, the fishing effort of the different fleets was reduced within the MPAs (Figure 4.71), and, where present, within offshore wind farms (Figure 4.72). Reductions in fishing effort leads to reductions in catch in those areas with fisheries restrictions and potentially increases in catch in unprotected areas due to the displacement of fishing effort (Figures 4.73, 4.74 and 4.75). In each scenario, high impacting fleets such as demersal trawl (e.g., French and Spanish demersal trawl) were excluded from the Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VMEs) recently declared (blue contour in the 2030 box in Figure 4.71). In the fisheries sustainability, global sustainability and national enterprise scenarios additional MPAs were added following the FutureMARES project scenarios (Coll et al., 2024) (Figures 4.74 and 4.75). All fishing fleets were excluded from Fully Protected Areas (FPAs), while trawl and purse seine fleets were excluded from Highly Protected Areas (HPAs) only allowing some fisheries to continue (including coastal and offshore fishing fleets, which include a large amount of passive fishing gears and métiers such as longlines, pots, traps and gillnets; and the recreational fishery).

Figure 4.71. Fishery restrictions due to current MPAs and future MPAs for the Global Sustainability and National Enterprise scenarios. Fully Protected Areas (FPAs) are coloured in blue and Highly Protected Areas (HPAs) in green.

Figure 4.72. Fishery restrictions due to proportional coverage of cells by wind farms with fixed turbines impacting selected gears (left) and floating turbines impacting all gears (middle).

Figure 4.73. Fishing effort in scenario 4 with RCP4.5 climate trajectory, additional turbines in 2030 and 2040 (fixed turbines - open polygons, floating turbines - hatched polygons) and 25% reduction in marine traffic by 2040. Maps show average distribution of effort standardised to the 2020s (left, showing percentage of effort in each grid cell of the total over the whole domain) followed by change per grid cell (increases and decreases per cell relative to 2020s) by 2030s, 2050 and 2090s for French demersal trawl, French purse seine, Spanish demersal trawl and Spanish purse sei.

Figure 4.74. The distribution of fishing effort in Scenario 7 with RCP4.5 climate trajectory, new MPAs for Global Sustainability (Highly Protected Areas, HPA open polygons, and Fully Protected Areas, FPA hatched polygons) to meet the 30x30 commitment, plus a decrease in fishing effort post-2030 and with new wind turbines in 2030 and 2040 and a reduction in vessel speed by 2050. Maps are shown for French demersal trawl, French purse seine, Spanish demersal trawl and Spanish purse seine. The maps show the average distribution of effort in the 2020s reference period (left) followed by change in effort relative to the 2020s in 2030s, 2050 and 2090s.

Figure 4.75. The distribution of fishing effort for National Enterprise Scenario 8 with RCP4.5 climate trajectory, MPAs (Highly Protected Areas, HPA open polygons, and Fully Protected Areas, FPA hatched polygons) and the addition of wind turbines (to 2030 only) and an increase in marine traffic by 2040. Maps are shown French demersal trawl, French purse seine, Spanish demersal trawl and Spanish purse seine. The maps show the average distribution of effort in the 2020s reference period (left) followed by change in effort relative to the 2020s in 2030s, 2050 and 2090s.

Overall change in the biomass of functional groups by scenario

The biomass trajectories for the functional groups of the Bay of Biscay model showed either declines or increases in the 2050s relative to the 2020s due to the negative and positive impacts of climate change and fisheries interventions (Figure 4.76). Several fish species declined, such as albacore, horse mackerel, common sole, flatfishes and large demersal fishes under scenarios of status quo (S1, S9, S2, S3 and S4). These declines were partially reverted under fisheries sustainability and global sustainability scenarios (S5 and S6), even when cumulative impacts of shipping and wind farms were included (S7). The National Enterprise scenario showed positive and negative impacts on these groups

and the cumulative impacts of shipping and windfarms were also negligible in comparison with the impact of fishing and management interventions (S8 and S11). For example, horse mackerel, common sole and large demersal fishes declined while albacore increased. By the 2090s, previous declines are generally more pronounced (Figure 4.77), especially in National Enterprise scenario due to the more extreme climate projection (RCP8.5).

Figure 4.76. Heatmap showing change in biomass of functional groups between 2050s and the 2020s for 11 scenarios for the Bay of Biscay.

Figure 4.77. Heatmap showing change in biomass of functional groups between 2090s and the 2020s for 11 scenarios for the Bay of Biscay.

The biomass trends of key species showed contrasting results between scenarios (Figure 4.78, 4.79 and 4.80). For example, some fish species (e.g., anglerfish, large hake, sardine and sea bass) showed non-recoveries (or even decreasing trends) under status quo or cumulative effects (S1 and S4), while they showed increasing trends under sustainable scenarios (S5, S6, S7 and S10) and decreasing trends under National Enterprise (S8 and S11) (Figure 4.78). On the contrary, anchovy showed increasing trends in all scenarios, particularly under National Enterprise with or without projected change in primary production (S8 and S11), while megrim presented a generally stable trend in each scenario (Figure 4.78). Fish groups did not show important changes between windfarm regions with either floating or fixed turbines and the whole domain, except for anchovy, anglerfish, large hake and megrim under National Enterprise (S8 and S11) (Figure 4.78). Under these scenarios (S8 and S11), these fish species presented significant decreasing trends in windfarm areas (mainly located in Spanish waters (Figure 4.72) at the beginning of the simulation period due to fisheries redistributions in the whole area. In National Enterprise (S8 and S11), Spanish and Basque fleets (important fleets in the region) were not allowed to operate in French waters (Figure 4.75).

Figure 4.78. Change in biomass of key fish species over time for 10 scenarios.

Marine mammals also showed mixed results (Figure 4.79). While the biomass of dolphins and whales increased post-2020 in sustainable scenarios with or without restoration and with or without cumulative effects of OWF and shipping (S5, S6 and S7), the groups decreased under National Enterprise scenarios (S8 and S11) (Figure 4.79). In scenarios without additional EBFM measures and with no new MPAs with cumulative effects of OWF and shipping (S3 and S4) or without (S1 and S9), dolphins presented stable trends in most scenarios, whales showed increasing trends (Figure 4.79). Interestingly, whales did not show significant changes between windfarms with floating turbines or fixed turbines or the whole domain, while dolphins presented significant decreasing trends in windfarm areas (mainly located in Spanish waters, Figure 4.72) at the beginning of the simulation period due to fisheries redistributions under National Enterprise (S8 and S11) (Figure 4.79).

Figure 4.79. Biomass of marine mammals over time for 10 scenarios.

Both functional groups of seabirds showed significant decreasing trends in status quo scenarios (S1, S3, S4 and S9) and a slightly decreasing trend in sustainable scenarios (S5, S6 and S7), while surface feeders seabirds presented an increasing trend under National Enterprise (S8 and S11) (Figure 4.80). Under sustainable scenarios, the trend is largely attributable to the decline of an important prey (i.e., discards) despite the bycatch of these species being mostly eliminated; while the better trajectories of seabird’s groups under National Enterprise is due to the reduction of the bycatch while maintaining their accessibility to discards. Regarding floating and fixed windfarm regions, our results showed an important impact of offshore windfarms on these groups, especially after 2050, when most of the offshore windfarms would be constructed (Figure 4.80, Table 4.28).

Figure 4.80. Biomass of seabird species over time for 10 scenarios.

The response of key invertebrates was mixed (Figure 4.81). While some invertebrates increased under sustainable scenarios (S5, S6 and S7) and decreased under National Enterprise (S8 and S11) such as bivalves, others presented large fluctuations with time, nevertheless the most negative trends occurred in the National Enterprise scenario for groups such as benthos feeders decapods and echinoderms (Figure 4.81). Remarkably, Norway lobster presented decreasing trends in all scenarios, especially under National Enterprise (Figure 4.81).

Figure 4.81. Change in biomass of invertebrate species over time for 10 scenarios.

Catch trends of key fish species show contrasting results, similar to biomass trends (Figure 4.82). Increases of catches are predicted in all scenarios for anchovy except under National Enterprise, although after a strong decline at the beginning of the simulation period its catches are predicted to increase (Figure 4.82). On the contrary, catches of anglerfish decreased in all scenarios. Catches of large hake are predicted to slightly increase in all scenarios except under National Enterprise. Regarding floating and fixed windfarm regions, our results showed important increases of catches of several target species such as anchovy, anglerfish, large hake, megrim and sardine, at the beginning of the simulation period under National Enterprise (due to fisheries redistributions), which lead to biomass declines in these regions (Figure 4.78) and, consequently to a decline in their catches (Figure 4.82). Our results also showed a strong decline of the catches of all species in these regions after 2050, when most of the offshore windfarms would be constructed (Figure 4.82).

Figure 4.82. Change in total catch of key fish species over time for 10 scenarios.

The overall changes in the ecosystem can be captured when looking at system indicators (Figure 4.83). Under the Fisheries Sustainability scenarios with and without change in primary production (S5 and S10), all the indicators except MTI presented the largest values in 2050 in comparison with 2020. Remarkably, the IUCN species biomass and the predatory biomass showed significant increases under the Fisheries Sustainability scenarios (S5 and S10) compared to other scenarios, while total biomass and Shannon biodiversity index presented minor differences between all scenarios. In addition, IUCN

species biomass and the predatory biomass presented the lowest values under status quo scenarios (S1 and S4). The Kempton’s Q index declined between 2020 and 2050 under status quo (S1 and S4) and National Enterprise with and without change in primary production (S8 and S11) scenarios, with the lowest values under National Enterprise without change in primary production. The MTI indicator declined under the Fisheries sustainability (S5 and S10) and National Enterprise (S8 and S11) scenarios between 2020 and 2050, with the largest declines under Fisheries Sustainability.

Figure 4.83. Change in ecosystem indicators relative to 2020s for 6 scenarios.

Impact of offshore wind turbines on functional group biomass

The impact of wind turbines on the biomass of functional groups could be explored by comparing the results from the three variants of scenario 3 with differing level of response to turbines by seabirds (i.e. high, medium and low avoidance response and mortality rate). Additionally, the comparison between scenario 3 and scenario 1 (the climate status-quo without turbines and shipping) standardises these impacts for the effects of climate change. Finally, the comparison between the cumulative effects scenario 4 (with medium responses to the impacts of turbines and shipping) and scenario 2 (no wind farms but a medium response to shipping) allowed us to reveal the synergy between the impact of shipping and wind farms. In all these scenarios (S1, S2, S3 and S4), the model is driven by the RCP4.5 climate projection with constant fishing effort in the future (equal to the most recent value) and keeping MPAs that are currently in place constant post-2023. New offshore wind turbines are added in both S3 and S4 between 2023 and 2050 according to the sustainability scenario (i.e. increasing coverage to 2050, with the majority of additions in 2050 (Figure 4.72)). In S4, the impact of shipping on marine mammals is constant prior to 2021, when a gradual linear decrease begins down to 75% of the 2021 level in 2040.

The biomass of each seabird group decreases with increasing levels of offshore wind coverage due to collisions of birds within the regions despite the avoidance functional response (Table 4.29). Relative to the status-quo Scenario 1, there is a decrease in the 2050s due to fixed turbines of between 13.9% and 52.5% of seabird functional group biomass in offshore wind farms and a similar impact due to floating turbines of between 13% and 53.4% of biomass in offshore wind farms (Table 4.29). The greatest impact in the 2050s relative to S1 is modelled on diving seabirds among farms with floating turbines in the high response scenario and smallest impact on surface-feeding seabirds among farms with floating turbines in the low response scenario (Table 4.29).

Table 4.29. Sensitivity of seabird biomass to turbine impacts (collision and avoidance) once standardised to Scenario 1 to exclude climate change impacts. Values give the percentage difference in biomass in the 2020s [$100 \times (S3_{bio} - S1_{bio})/S1_{bio}$] between Scenario 1 (Status quo) and the three variants of Scenario 3 (with turbines).

Scenario comparison	Windfarm area	Diving and pursuit divers seabirds	Surface feeders seabirds
S1 vs S3 Low	Fixed turbines	-27.8	-13.9
S1 vs S3 Medium		-43.0	-28.1
S1 vs S3 High		-52.5	-43.1
S1 vs S3 Low	Floating turbines	-26.9	-13.0
S1 vs S3 Medium		-42.9	-27.3
S1 vs S3 High		-53.4	-43.0
S1 vs S3 Low	Bay of Biscay	-0.6	-0.4
S1 vs S3 Medium		-0.9	-0.7
S1 vs S3 High		-1.1	-0.9

Minor changes were found due to predator-prey interactions and the displacement of fisheries and minor differences were found between the different levels of impacts (Table 4.30). The largest impacts were found for the biomass of anglerfish (3% higher in the fixed turbine areas and 2% higher in floating turbines areas in the 2050s than expected given the status-quo scenario, S1) (Table 4.30).

Table 4.30. Percentage change in biomass of selected fish species through fisheries and foodweb responses to turbine impacts once standardised to Scenario 1 to exclude climate change impacts. Values give the % difference in biomass in the 2020s [$100 \times (S3_{bio} - S1_{bio})/S1_{bio}$] between Scenario 1 (Status quo) and three variants of Scenario 3 (with turbines).

Scenario comparison	Windfarm Area	Sardine	Anchovy	Anglerfish	Sea bass	Large hake	Megrim
S1 vs S3 Low	Fixed turbines	0.3	0.1	3.2	-0.4	1.8	0.5
S1 vs S3 Medium		0.4	0.4	3.1	-0.3	2.5	0.5
S1 vs S3 High		0.5	0.7	3.1	-0.4	1.5	0.4
S1 vs S3 Low	Floating turbines	0.2	-0.3	2.4	-0.9	2.5	1.2
S1 vs S3 Medium		0.6	0.01	2.3	-0.8	-0.3	1.3
S1 vs S3 High		0.3	0.3	2.3	-0.8	1.0	1.1
S1 vs S3 Low	Bay of Biscay	0.4	-0.2	-0.6	-0.6	-1.3	-0.8
S1 vs S3 Medium		0.5	-0.2	-0.8	-0.5	-1.1	-0.8
S1 vs S3 High		0.5	-0.1	-0.7	-0.5	-1.1	-0.8

The local impact of offshore windfarms (both floating and fixed) on seabirds was significant in the three variants of scenario 3, with greater impact under the high response scenario (Figure 4.84a and Table 4.31). Although both functional groups of seabirds showed significant decreasing trends in biomass for the whole domain in the scenarios without additional MPAs or EBFM measures (S2, S3 and S4), the declining trend was weak in S2 (including shipping but without impact of offshore wind farms) and it was strong in the scenarios of offshore wind farms (S3) and the cumulative impacts (S4 with both shipping and offshore wind farms) (Figure 4.84a). These results highlight that the local impacts of offshore wind farms could affect the populations of these species at the regional sea level. On the other hand, no significant impact was observed on benthic invertebrates' groups (Figure 4.84b and Table 4.32). However, slight impacts were observed for fish species due to predator-prey interactions and the displacement of fisheries (Figure 4.84c, Table 4.33). For example, anglerfish and hake presented higher increases on their biomass within offshore wind farms (both floating and fixed) in S3 than S1 (Table 4.33). In addition, their biomass increases at the whole domain are lower in S3 than S1 (Table 4.33). Interestingly, while biomass increases has the same magnitude in S3 and S4 for anglerfish in all regions, biomass increases for hake are lower in no offshore wind farms, fixed turbines and the whole domain, while is higher in floating turbines (Table 4.33).

Figure 4.84a. Time-series of biomass for seabird groups from the model driven by RCP4.5 with current fishing effort and marine protection in place and change in cumulative effects according to 3 scenarios: S3 (three levels of impact of turbines), S4 (with medium impacts of turbines and shipping) and S2 (medium impact of shipping and no impact of turbines).

Figure 4.84b. Time-series of biomass for key fish groups from the model driven by RCP4.5 with current fishing effort and marine protection in place and change in cumulative effects according to 3 scenarios: S3 (three levels of impact of turbines), S4 (with medium impacts of turbines and shipping) and S2 (medium impact of shipping only).

Figure 4.84c. Time-series of biomass for key benthic fauna from the model driven by RCP4.5 with current fishing effort and marine protection in place and change in cumulative effects according to 3 scenarios: S3 (three levels of impact of turbines), S4 (with medium impacts of turbines and shipping) and S2 (medium impact of shipping and no impact of turbines).

Table 4.31. Percentage change between 2050s and 2020s in the biomass of seabirds in the status quo scenario 1, three variants of the OWF scenario 3 and in the status quo with cumulative effects scenario 4 with medium response to OWF and shipping by spatial region – where the offshore wind farm extent (for fixed turbines, floating turbines and no turbines) is set at the full modelled coverage in 2050 across all scenarios (including S1 where no turbines are implemented).

Change over time by scenario	Spatial region	Diving and pursuit divers seabirds	Surface feeders seabirds
S1 status quo (RCP4.5) and no change in human activities	no OWF region	-8.8	-7.9
	fixed turbines	-14.2	-14.7
	floating turbines	-20.6	-22.8
	Bay of Biscay	-9.1	-8.3
S3 status quo (RCP4.5) with low response to OWF	no OWF region	-8.3	-7.7
	fixed turbines	-37.1	-25.9
	floating turbines	-42.0	-32.9
	Bay of Biscay	-9.5	-8.5
S3 status quo (RCP4.5) with medium response to OWF	no OWF region	-7.9	-7.4
	fixed turbines	-49.8	-37.6
	floating turbines	-54.6	-43.8
	Bay of Biscay	-9.7	-8.7
S3 status quo (RCP4.5) with high response to OWF	no OWF region	-7.7	-7.1
	fixed turbines	-58.0	-50.2
	floating turbines	-63.0	-56.0
	Bay of Biscay	-9.8	-8.9
S4 status quo (RCP4.5) with cumulative effects to OWF and shipping (medium responses)	no OWF region	-7.8	-7.3
	fixed turbines	-49.8	-37.5
	floating turbines	-54.6	-43.8
	Bay of Biscay	-9.6	-8.6

Table 4.32. Percentage change between 2050s and 2020s in biomass of key benthic fauna in the status quo scenario 1, three variants of the OWF scenario 3 and in the status quo with cumulative effects scenario 4 with medium response to OWF and shipping by spatial region – where the offshore wind farm extent (for fixed turbines, floating turbines and no turbines) is set at the full modelled coverage in 2050 across all scenarios (including S1 where no turbines are implemented).

Change over time by scenario	Spatial region	Benthos feeders decapods	Bivalves	Detritus feeders decapods	Echinoderms	Norway lobster
S1 status quo (RCP4.5) and no change in human activities	no OWF region	-1.3	2.8	-1.4	-0.6	-1.1
	fixed turbines	-1.6	-0.5	-1.8	-0.9	-0.6
	floating turbines	-1.6	-3.2	-1.8	-1.6	-0.4
	Bay of Biscay	-1.3	2.5	-1.4	-0.6	-1.1
S3 status quo (RCP4.5) with medium response to OWF	no OWF region	-1.3	2.4	-1.3	-0.9	-1.2
	fixed turbines	-0.3	-6.9	-0.5	1.2	2.6
	floating turbines	-1.5	-4.9	-2.2	-0.3	0.3
	Bay of Biscay	-1.3	1.8	-1.3	-0.8	-1.0
S4 status quo (RCP4.5) with cumulative effects to OWF and shipping (medium responses)	no OWF region	-1.2	2.4	-1.3	-0.8	-1.2
	fixed turbines	-0.1	-6.8	-0.4	1.3	2.5
	floating turbines	-1.4	-4.8	-2.1	-0.2	0.4
	Bay of Biscay	-1.2	1.8	-1.3	-0.7	-1.1

Table 4.33. Percentage change between 2050s and 2020s in biomass of key fish species in the status quo scenario 1, three variants of the OWF scenario 3 and in the status quo with cumulative effects scenario 4 with medium response to OWF and shipping by spatial region – where the offshore wind farm extent (for fixed turbines, floating turbines and no turbines) is set at the full modelled coverage in 2050 across all scenarios (including S1 where no turbines are implemented).

Change over time by scenario	Spatial region	Anchovy	Anglerfish	Large hake	Megrim	Sardine	Sea bass
S1 status quo (RCP4.5) and no change in human activities	no OWF region	8.2	-3.4	7.7	16.2	0.8	-6.3
	fixed turbines	5.0	12.4	6.1	22.9	1.8	-3.6
	floating turbines	-14.9	14.3	-1.4	26.0	0.9	-5.9
	Bay of Biscay	7.9	-2.9	7.6	16.5	0.9	-6.2
S3 status quo (RCP4.5) with medium response to OWF	no OWF region	8.0	-3.9	6.8	15.5	1.0	-6.7
	fixed turbines	5.3	15.8	9.0	23.6	2.2	-3.9
	floating turbines	-14.8	16.9	0.0	27.6	1.1	-6.7
	Bay of Biscay	7.7	-3.3	6.8	15.8	1.1	-6.6
S4 status quo (RCP4.5) with cumulative effects to OWF and shipping (medium responses)	no OWF region	6.4	-3.9	5.4	15.7	1.2	-6.8
	fixed turbines	3.7	15.8	5.0	24.0	2.3	-4.1
	floating turbines	-15.1	16.6	2.5	27.8	0.8	-7.0
	Bay of Biscay	6.2	-3.3	5.4	16.1	1.3	-6.6

Impact of shipping

The impact of shipping on the biomass of functional groups could be explored by comparing the results from the three variants of Scenario 2 with differing the level of response to shipping by marine mammals (i.e. high, medium and low avoidance response and mortality rate). The period until 2021 has a constant level of shipping density while the simulation period shipping traffic is reduced by 25% 25% in 2040 respect 2019 levels. The impact of shipping on marine mammals was projected to be higher under the high impact scenario (Figure 4.85). The greatest impact was evident for dolphins (a 12% decrease in total biomass respect S1) (Table 4.34). The negative effect of high levels of shipping on dolphins in the shipping routes remains evident in the period 2021-2040 despite some recovery of dolphins is observed as traffic is reduced. Notably, across the whole Bay of Biscay domain, the reduction of shipping traffic leads to an overall increase of dolphins and whales, that is higher in the high impact scenario (Figure 4.85 and Table 4.35). This could be partially explained by the initial strong impact of shipping as a high initial impact may lead to a strong response as the impact is reduced. The introduction of offshore wind farms without shipping (S3) as well as the cumulative impact scenario (S4) indicates a negligible effect of offshore windfarms on marine mammals (Figure 4.85).

Figure 4.85. Sensitivity of marine mammal biomass to shipping impacts (period before 2021) and reduction of shipping impacts (25% reduction between 2021-2040) under a changing climate (RCP4.5) with current fishing effort and marine protection in place. Change in human activities modelled according to scenario: S2 (three levels of shipping impact and no turbines), S4 (with medium impacts of turbines and shipping) and S3 (medium impact of turbines but no shipping).

Table 4.34. Sensitivity of mammal biomass to shipping impacts (collision and avoidance) once standardised to the status-quo scenario to exclude climate change impacts. Values give the percentage difference in biomass between the scenario in the 2020s [$100 \times (S2_{bio} - S1_{bio})/S1_{bio}$] between Scenario 1 (Status quo) and the three variants of Scenario 2 (with shipping).

Scenario comparison for the Bay of Biscay	Whales	Dolphins
S1 vs S2 SQ Low shipping	-0.6	-5.1
S1 vs S2 SQ Med shipping	-1.1	-9.2
S1 vs S2 SQ High shipping	-1.7	-11.9

Table 4.35. Recovery of mammal biomass from shipping impacts (collision and avoidance) following reduction in shipping impacts by 25% by 2040 and in a warming climate (RCP4.5). Percentage change over time between 2050s and 2020s in the biomass of mammal species in three variants of the shipping S2 in the whole region and in the area impacted by shipping.

Scenario	Spatial region	Dolphins	Whales
S2 SQ Low shipping with 25% reduction in shipping by 2040	Shipping region	3.1	1.6
	Bay of Biscay	2.9	1.5
S2 SQ Med shipping with 25% reduction in shipping by 2040	Shipping region	5.7	3.0
	Bay of Biscay	4.9	2.3
S2 SQ High shipping with 25% reduction in shipping by 2040	Shipping region	9.0	4.7
	Bay of Biscay	7.1	3.2

Cumulative impact of shipping and offshore wind combined with EBFM measures, MPAs and restoration activities under a changing climate

The impact of climate change, shipping and offshore wind farms as well as different EBFM measures (reduction in bycatch, discards and fishing effort to meet Maximum Sustainable Yield), new MPA or restoration activities is clearly evident depending on the different organisms. For example, scenarios of shipping traffic reductions (S4, S5, S6 and S7) leads to biomass increases of marine mammals while scenarios of shipping traffic increases (S8) lead to biomass reductions of marine mammals (Figure 4.86a).

Both seabirds’ groups showed significant decreasing trends in status quo scenarios (S1 and S4) and a slightly decreasing trend in sustainable scenarios (S5, S6 and S7), while surface feeders seabirds presented an increasing trend under National Enterprise (S8) (Figure 4.86b). Under sustainable scenarios, the trend could be attributed to the decline of important prey (i.e., discards) despite the bycatch of these species being mostly eliminated; while the better trajectories of seabird’s groups under National Enterprise is probably due to the reduction of the bycatch while maintaining their accessibility to discards.

Figure 4.86a. Time-series of biomass for key mammal functional groups for six scenarios with additional marine protected areas in S5-8 but no change in extent of MPAs in S1 & S4. Scenario 8 has a different climate projection to the rest and in this scenario shipping is increased between 2021 and 2050 by 33%.

Figure 4.86b. Time-series of biomass for seabird functional groups for six scenarios with additional marine protected areas in S5-8 but no change in extent of MPAs in S1 & S4. Scenario 8 has a difference climate projection to the rest.

The biomass trends of key fish species showed that sustainable scenarios (S5, S6 and S7) leads to highest biomass in the long term (except anchovy and megrim) and indicated that cumulative impacts from shipping and offshore wind farms leads to small decreases that do not alter the benefits from

the introduction of MPAs and EBFM measures (Figure 4.86c). The worst outcomes for anglerfish, large hake, sardine and seabass are in the National Enterprise scenario (S8) due to the impact of climate change and increasing fishing effort (Figure 4.86c). The biomass trends of key invertebrate’s species showed a considerable year-to-year variability for most of the organisms (Figure 4.86d). However, under sustainable scenarios (S5, S6 and S7) bivalves and echinoderms increased and decreased under National Enterprise (S8) in the long term, while Norway lobster presented decreasing trends in all scenarios, specially under National Enterprise (Figure 4.86d).

Figure 4.86c. Time-series of biomass for key functional groups of fish for six scenarios with additional marine protected areas in S5-8 but no change in extent of MPAs in S1 & S4. Scenario 8 has a difference climate projection to the rest.

Figure 4.86d. Time-series of biomass for key functional groups of benthic fauna for six scenarios with additional marine protected areas in S5-8 but no change in extent of MPAs in S1 & S4. Scenario 8 has a different climate projection to the rest.

Impact of primary production and difference between scenarios of climate (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5) combined with MPA/EBFM management

The model of the Bay of Biscay ecosystem is driven by an ensemble modelling of different Earth System Model projections that account for changes in temperature and primary production rates of phytoplankton (Butenschön et al., 2024; Coll et al., 2024; Kristiansen et al., 2024). However, due to the uncertainty in projections of primary production, it is crucial to investigate the impact of primary production dynamics in future scenarios.

Regarding key invertebrates' species similar biomass levels at the end of the simulation were found, although higher biomasses were found for many species in S1 respect S9 (constant PP) (Figure 4.87a). In addition, the large year-to-year variability of these organism did not appear in constant PP scenarios, highlighting the importance of primary production dynamics on these organisms. Similarly, similar results of key fish species were projected in all contrasting scenarios, although it seems that a slight difference could be observed in status quo (S1 and S9) and sustainable scenarios (S5 and S10) (Figure 4.87b). On the contrary, it seems that the impact of primary production on marine mammals is evident (Figure 4.87c).

Figure 4.87a. Time-series of biomass for key benthic groups for six scenarios, including additional marine protected areas in scenarios 5, 8, 10 and 11 but no change in MPAs in S1 & S9. Scenarios 8 and 11 only use RCP8.5 climate projections.

Figure 4.87b. Time-series of biomass for key fish species for six scenarios with additional MPAs in scenarios 5, 8, 10 and 11 but no change in extent of MPAs in S1 & S9. Scenarios 8 and 11 only use RCP8.5 climate projections.

Figure 4.87c. Time-series of biomass for mammals for six scenarios for six scenarios, including additional MPAs in scenarios 5, 8, 10 and 11 but no change in MPAs in S1 & S9. Scenarios 8 and 11 only use RCP8.5 climate projections.

4.7 EwE results - Portuguese shelf

Fisheries management

In the scenarios analysed, fishing effort was reduced within MPAs and, where applicable, within offshore wind farms (Figures 4.88-4.89). These reductions led to decreased catches in areas with fisheries restrictions, while potentially increasing catches in unprotected areas due to the displacement of fishing effort (Figures 4.90-4.92). The extent of MPAs, the total restricted area, and the fleets affected varied by scenario. However, in all cases, fishing effort was reduced within existing MPAs, including the exclusion of purse-seine and bottom trawl fleets from the Arrábida MPA and the exclusion of bottom trawl and polyvalent fleets from the Berlengas MPA. In the Fisheries Sustainability, Global Sustainability, and National Enterprise scenarios, additional MPAs were introduced based on the FutureMARES project scenarios (Coll et al., 2024) (Figure 4.88). Fully Protected Areas (FPAs) prohibited all fishing activities, while Highly Protected Areas (HPAs) allowed only small-scale purse-seine and polyvalent fleet fisheries, with high-impact bottom trawl fleets excluded. For scenarios that modelled the impacts of offshore wind farms, fishing fleets were excluded from floating OWF areas (Figure 4.89).

Figure 4.88. Fishery restrictions due to current MPAs and future MPAs for the Global Sustainability and National Enterprise scenarios. Fully Protected Areas (FPAs) are coloured in blue and Highly Protected Areas (HPAs) in green.

Figure 4.89. Fishery restrictions due to proportional coverage of cells by wind farms (floating turbines) impacting all gears.

Figure 4.90. The distribution of fishing effort and projected change in scenario 4 with RCP4.5 climate trajectory, no new MPAs or no change in overall effort or fuel/fish prices, but with additional turbines in 2030 (floating turbines shown by hatched polygons) and a reduction in shipping speeds by 2040. Maps show bottom-trawl (top), multi-gear (polyvalent) (middle) and purse-seine (bottom) fleets. The maps show the average distribution of effort in the 2020s reference period (left) followed by change relative to the 2020s in 2030s, 2050 and 2090s.

Figure 4.91. The distribution of fishing effort in Scenario 7 with RCP4.5 climate trajectory, new Marine Protected Areas for Global Sustainability (Highly Protected Areas, HPA open polygons, and Fully Protected Areas, FPA hatched polygons) to meet the 30x30 commitment, plus a decrease in fishing effort post-2030 and with new wind turbines in 2030 and a reduction in vessel speed by 2050. Maps are shown for bottom-trawl (top), multi-gear (polyvalent) (middle) and purse-seine (bottom) fleets. The maps show the average distribution of effort in the 2020s reference period (left) followed by change in effort relative to the 2020s in 2030s, 2050 and 2090s.

Figure 4.92. The distribution of fishing effort in Scenario 8 with RCP4.5 climate trajectory, few and smaller Marine Protected Areas (Highly Protected Areas, HPA open polygons, and Fully Protected Areas, FPA hatched polygons) for National Enterprise with the addition of new wind turbines in 2030 and an increase in vessel speed by 2040. Maps are shown for bottom trawl (top), multi-gear (polyvalent) (middle) and purse-seine (bottom) fleet. The maps show the average distribution of effort in the 2020s reference period (left) followed by change in effort relative to the 2020s in 2030s, 2050 and 2090s.

Overall change in the biomass of functional groups by scenario

Across all scenarios, several functional groups—such as mackerel, chub mackerel, benthopelagic piscivores fish and horse mackerel—are projected to increase by 2050 compared to the 2020s, driven by the positive effects of climate change. Conversely, other groups—including squids, blue jack mackerel, demersal piscivores fish, striped dolphins, flatfish, benthic cephalopods, rays, adult sardines, benthopelagic invertivores fishes, hake, sharks, benthic organisms, and lower trophic groups—are expected to decline due to the negative impacts of climate change (Figure 4.93). These negative effects are most pronounced in the National Enterprise scenario, where the more extreme climate projection (RCP8.5) and increased fishing effort amplify biomass declines. In contrast, other scenarios—based on the milder RCP4.5 projection and lower fishing increases—show less severe impacts (Figure 4.93).

Figure 4.93 Heatmap showing change in biomass of functional groups between 2050s and the 2020s for 11 scenarios for the Portuguese shelf model.

By 2090, these trends continue, with more pronounced increases, particularly for pelagic species and some top predators, including seabirds and marine mammals (Figure 4.94). Differences between

scenarios remain subtle for most key species, except in the National Enterprise scenario (S8), where effects are most pronounced. In S8, adult sardine and ray biomasses drop to their lowest levels due to rising sea surface temperatures (for sardines) and reduced prey availability (Figure 4.95). In contrast, anchovy, horse mackerel, and mackerel initially decline in S8 by the 2050s but recover by the 2090s, likely due to food web dynamics, niche release from sardines, and increases in phytoplankton and zooplankton propagating through the ecosystem (Figure 4.95).

Figure 4.94 Heatmap showing change in biomass of functional groups between 2090s and the 2020s for 11 scenarios for the Portuguese shelf model.

Catch trends follow biomass patterns, increasing for species whose biomasses rise (anchovy, horse mackerel, mackerel) and decreasing for those in decline (Figure 4.96). However, catch differences between scenarios are more pronounced, with lower catches in Global Sustainability scenarios (S5, S6, S7, S10) and higher catches in National Enterprise scenarios (S8, S11) (Figure 4.96). Bycatch is also highest in the National Enterprise scenarios (Figure 4.97).

Ecosystem-wide changes are reflected in key indicators (Figure 4.98). While diversity metrics (Shannon Index and Kempton’s Q) and total system biomass increase across all scenarios, predator biomass

relative to prey and the Marine Trophic Index (MTI) decline, indicating structural shifts in the food web.

Figure 4.95 Biomass of key fish species over time for 10 scenarios for the Portuguese shelf.

Figure 4.96 Change in total catch of key fish species over time for 10 scenarios for the Portuguese shelf.

Figure 4.97 Bycatch of marine mammals over time for 10 scenarios for the Portuguese shelf.

Figure 4.98 Change in ecosystem indicators in 2050 relative to 2020s for 6 scenarios (no data for IUCN species B available).

Impact of offshore wind turbines on functional group biomass

Within the floating wind farm area, the biomass of the seabird group decreases with increasing levels of offshore wind coverage, due to bird collisions in the region, despite the avoidance functional response (Figure 4.99a). In contrast, this effect is not observed at the scale of the entire region (Figure 4.99a). Relative to the status-quo Scenario 1, there is a decrease in seabird functional group biomass in offshore wind farms during the 2050s, ranging from 17% to 52% due to the presence of floating turbines (Table 4.35). No substantial impact of windfarms was evident for key fish groups (Figure 4.99b) and the model did not show an increase in the biomass of macrozoobenthos and shrimp groups due to the reduction in fishing effort within the wind farms or the increase in artificial habitat from scour protection (Figure 4.99c). Additionally, the impact on benthic infaunal groups from the loss of physical habitat was negligible when compared to the expected biomass in Scenario 1 in the 2050s (Figure 4.99c). Changes were found due to predator-prey interactions and the displacement of fisheries, specifically for the biomass of sharks (7% higher in the floating turbine areas in 2050 compared to the status-quo scenario, S1), squids, and demersal piscivorous fish (3% higher in the floating turbine areas in 2050 compared to S1), as well as mackerel and hake (1–2% higher in the floating turbine areas in the 2050s compared to S1), and adult sardine (1% lower in floating turbine areas) (Tables 4.36 and 4.37). Overall, at the whole Portuguese shelf scale, the impact of turbines

relative to S1 in the 2050s was found to be slightly positive for squids (+2%) but marginally negative for mackerel, sharks, hake, and demersal piscivorous fish (-1%) (Tables 4.36 and 4.37).

Table 4.36. Sensitivity of seabird biomass to turbine impacts (collision and avoidance) along with key prey species biomass once standardised to Scenario 1 to exclude climate change impacts. Values give the percentage difference in biomass between scenarios in the 2050s [$100 \times (S3_{bio} - S1_{bio})/S1_{bio}$] between Scenario 1 (Status quo) and the three variants of Scenario 3 (with turbines).

Scenario comparison	Windfarm Area	Seabirds	Mackerel	Adult sardine	Chub mackerel
S1 vs S3 Low		-17	1	0	0
S1 vs S3 Medium	Floating turbines	-34	2	0	0
S1 vs S3 High		-52	2	-1	0
S1 vs S3 Low		-2	-1	0	0
S1 vs S3 Medium	Portuguese Shelf	-1	-1	0	0
S1 vs S3 High		-1	-1	0	0

Table 4.37. Percentage change in biomass of selected fish species through fisheries and foodweb responses to turbine impacts once standardised to the status-quo scenario to exclude climate change impacts. Values give the percentage difference in biomass in the 2050s [$100 \times (S3_{bio} - S1_{bio})/S1_{bio}$] between Scenario 1 (Status quo) and the three variants of Scenario 3 (with turbines). Note outputs for S3 with high and low responses of fish are identical for these groups.

Scenario comparison	Windfarm Area	Sharks	Squids	Demersal fish piscivores	Kelps	Hake
S1 vs S3 Medium	Floating turbines	7	3	3	2	1
S1 vs S3 Medium	Portuguese Shelf	-1	2	-1	0	-1

The local impact of floating offshore wind farms on seabirds was significant in all three variants of Scenario 3, with the highest impact in the high-impact scenario (Figure 4.99a and Table 4.38). Despite significant increasing trends in seabird biomass in the status-quo scenarios (S2, S3, and S4), the magnitude of increase in Scenario 1 (without the impact of offshore wind farms and shipping) was slightly larger (55%) than in the offshore wind farm and cumulative impact scenarios (S4), where increases ranged from 52% to 54% (Table 4.38, Figure 4.99a). These results suggest that the local impacts of offshore wind farms could primarily affect seabird populations at the regional level.

Figure 4.99a. Time-series of biomass for seabird functional groups resulting from the model driven by RCP4.5 with current fishing effort and marine protection in place and change in offshore wind turbines and shipping route density according to three scenarios: S3 (three levels of impact of turbines), S4 (with medium impacts of turbines and shipping) and S2 (medium impact of shipping and no impact of turbines).

Table 4.38. Percentage change between 2050s and 2020s in biomass of seabirds in the status quo scenario 1, three variants of the OWF scenario 3 and in the status quo with cumulative effects scenario 4 with medium response to OWF and shipping by spatial region – where the offshore wind farm extent (for fixed turbines, floating turbines and no turbines) is set at the full modelled coverage in 2050 across all scenarios (including S1 where no turbines are implemented).

Change over time by scenario	Spatial region	Seabirds
S1 status quo (RCP4.5) and no change in human activities	no OWF region	55.7
	floating turbines	45.2
	Portuguese Shelf	55.1
S3 status quo (RCP4.5) with low response to OWF	no OWF region	54.9
	floating turbines	20.1
	Portuguese Shelf	52.7
S3 status quo (RCP4.5) with medium response to OWF	no OWF region	57.0
	floating turbines	-4.0
	Portuguese Shelf	53.1
S3 status quo (RCP4.5) with high response to OWF	no OWF region	59.6
	floating turbines	-30.2
	Portuguese Shelf	53.8
S4 status quo (RCP4.5) with cumulative effects to OWF and shipping (medium responses)	no OWF region	56.0
	floating turbines	-4.8
	Portuguese Shelf	52.1

Figure 4.99b. Time-series of biomass for key fish from the model driven by RCP4.5 with current fishing effort and marine protection in place and change in cumulative impacts according to three scenarios: S3 (three levels of impact of turbines), S4 (with medium impacts of turbines and shipping) and S2 (medium impact of shipping and no impact of turbines).

Figure 4.99c. Time-series of biomass for key groups of benthic fauna from the model driven by RCP4.5 with current fishing effort and marine protection in place and change in cumulative impacts according to three scenarios: S3 (three levels of impact of turbines), S4 (with medium impacts of turbines and shipping) and S2 (medium impact of shipping and no impact of turbines, right column only).

On the other hand, no significant impact was observed on benthic groups from either the local or overall impact of floating offshore wind farms (Table 4.39). Only slight impacts on other species, such as mackerel and rays, were observed in 2050 when compared to the status-quo scenario (Table 4.40).

Table 4.39. Percentage change between 2050s and 2020s in biomass of key benthic fauna in the status quo scenario 1, three variants of the OWF scenario 3 and in the status quo with cumulative effects scenario 4 with medium response to OWF and shipping by spatial region – where the offshore wind farm extent (for fixed turbines, floating turbines and no turbines) is set at the full modelled coverage in 2050 across all scenarios (including S1 where no turbines are implemented).

Change over time by scenario	Spatial region	Macrozoobenthos	Shrimps	Suprabenthic inv
S1 status quo (RCP4.5) and no change in human activities	no OWF region	-2	-9	-2
	floating turbines	0	-11	-2
	Portuguese Shelf	-2	-9	-2
S3 status quo (RCP4.5) with medium response to OWF	no OWF region	-2	-9	-2
	floating turbines	0	-11	-2
	Portuguese Shelf	-2	-9	-2
S4 status quo (RCP4.5) with cumulative effects to OWF and shipping (medium responses)	no OWF region	-2	-9	-2
	floating turbines	0	-11	-2
	Portuguese Shelf	-2	-9	-2

Table 4.40. Percentage change between 2050s and 2020s in biomass of key fish species in the status quo scenario 1, three variants of the OWF scenario 3 and in the status quo with cumulative effects scenario 4 with medium response to OWF and shipping by spatial region – where the offshore wind farm extent (for fixed turbines, floating turbines and no turbines) is set at the full modelled coverage in 2050 across all scenarios (including S1 where no turbines are implemented).

Change over time by scenario	Spatial region	Adult sardine	Anchovy	Hake	Horse mackerel	Mackerel	Rays
S1 status quo (RCP4.5) and no change in human activities	no OWF region	-8	20	-4	44	162	-8
	floating turbines	-7	37	-8	100	886	-9
	Portuguese Shelf	-8	22	-5	49	184	-8
S3 status quo (RCP4.5) with medium response to OWF	no OWF region	-8	20	-5	43	158	-10
	floating turbines	-8	37	-7	100	901	-8
	Portuguese Shelf	-8	22	-5	49	181	-10
S4 status quo (RCP4.5) with cumulative effects to OWF and shipping (medium responses)	no OWF region	-8	20	-5	43	157	-10
	floating turbines	-10	37	-7	100	894	-8
	Portuguese Shelf	-8	22	-5	48	179	-10

Impact of shipping

Figure 4.100 illustrates the changes in biomass of marine mammal functional groups over time. Up until 2021, shipping density remains constant, meaning the differences between the three variants of Scenario 2 reflect the varying impacts of assumptions about collision risk and foraging disruptions due to avoidance behaviour. The sensitivity of marine mammals to these impacts is summarized in Table 4.41, showing that each group experiences the greatest effects under the high-shipping scenario. Among the marine mammals, the most significant impact is observed in striped dolphins, with a 6% decrease in total biomass, followed by a 4% decrease in harbour porpoise biomass (Table 4.41). The

impact on bottlenose dolphin and minke whales is smaller, with decrease in biomass of approximately 1% (Table 4.41). The recovery is shown in Table 4.42.

Between 2021 and 2040, shipping traffic is projected to decrease by 25%, leading to an increase in the biomass of common dolphins, bottlenose dolphins, and to lesser extent an increase for harbour porpoise relative to scenario S3 that simulate the sole impact of OWF (purple line, Figure 4.100). However, despite the reduction in shipping activity, the biomass of striped dolphin is predicted to decline relative to scenario S3. This decline may be attributed to reduced prey availability due to increased competition for prey with other marine mammals that were predicted to increase.

Figure 4.100. Sensitivity of marine mammal biomass to shipping impacts (period before 2021) and reduction of shipping impacts (25% reduction between 2021-2040) under a changing climate (RCP4.5) with current fishing effort and marine protection in place. Change in human activities modelled according to scenario: S2 (three levels of shipping impact and no turbines), S4 (with medium impacts of turbines and shipping) and S3 (medium impact of turbines but no shipping).

Table 4.41. Sensitivity of mammal biomass to shipping impacts (collision and avoidance) once standardised to Scenario 1 to exclude climate change impacts. Values give the percentage difference in biomass between the scenario in the 2020s [$100 \times (S2_{bio} - S1_{bio})/S1_{bio}$] between Scenario 1 (Status quo) and the three variants of Scenario 2 (with shipping).

Scenario comparison for Portuguese Shelf	Bottlenose dolphin	Common dolphin	Harbour porpoise	Minke whale	Striped dolphin
S1 vs S2 Low shipping	0	0	-2	-1	-2
S1 vs S3 Med shipping	0	0	-3	-1	-3
S1 vs S3 High shipping	-1	0	-4	-1	-6

Table 4.42. Recovery of mammal biomass from shipping impacts (collision and avoidance) following reduction in shipping impacts by 25% by 2040 and in a warming climate (RCP4.5). Percentage change over time between 2050s and 2020s in the biomass of mammal species in three variants of the shipping S2 in the whole region and in the area impacted by shipping.

Change over time by scenario	Spatial region	Bottlenose dolphin	Common dolphin	Harbour porpoise	Minke whale	Striped dolphin
S2 SQ Low shipping with 25% reduction in shipping by 2040	Shipping region	103	90	29	31	29
	Portuguese Shelf	75	85	23	30	23
S2 SQ Med shipping with 25% reduction in shipping by 2040	Shipping region	107	95	32	32	32
	Portuguese Shelf	77	89	25	30	25
S2 SQ High shipping with 25% reduction in shipping by 2040	Shipping region	111	101	36	33	-1
	Portuguese Shelf	79	94	27	30	-5

Cumulative impact of shipping and offshore wind combined with EBFM measures, MPAs and restoration activities under a changing climate

Across all marine mammal groups, the global sustainability scenarios (S5, which includes MPAs covering 30% of the Portuguese shelf by 2030 along with EBFM measures and cumulative effects; S6, which additionally incorporates restoration; and S7, which further includes cumulative impacts) lead to an overall increase in biomass within both floating wind farm regions and the entire domain compared to the S1 SQ scenario (Figure 4.101a). The positive effects on biomass are most pronounced for minke whales and striped dolphins in these scenarios (Figure 4.101a). In contrast, Scenario 8 (National Enterprise) under RCP8.5, where MPA implementation is limited and fishing effort is projected to increase, has the most negative impact on all marine mammal groups relative to the S1 SQ scenario (Figure 4.101a). Scenario 4, which includes increased offshore wind farm coverage, reduced shipping activity, and an RCP4.5 climate projection but lacks additional MPAs or EBFM measures, results in a biomass trajectory similar to S1 SQ for harbour porpoises and common dolphins. However, the impacts of wind farms and shipping are evident in the decline of minke whale and striped dolphin biomass (Figure 4.101a).

For the seabird functional group, the effects of MPAs, EBFM measures, and restoration in Scenario S6 are most pronounced within floating wind farm regions. This scenario shows the highest biomass compared to scenarios with cumulative effects (S7 and S5), highlighting the negative impact of offshore wind farms (OWFs) and shipping routes on seabirds (Figure 4.101b). Additionally, the compensatory and mitigating effects of MPAs and other EBFM measures are evident, as seabirds biomass levels in Scenarios S5, S6, and S7 are higher compared to Scenarios S4 and S8. The latter scenarios lack these measures (or have limited MPAs, as in the case of S8) while also experiencing the

cumulative impacts of shipping and OWFs (in S4) and, additionally, increased fishing effort (in S8) (Figure 4.101b).

Figure 4.101a. Time-series of biomass for key mammal functional groups for six scenarios with additional marine protected areas in S5-8 but no change in extent of MPAs in S1 & S4. Scenario 8 has a different climate projection to the rest and in this scenario shipping is increased between 2021 and 2050 by 33%.

Figure 4.101b. Time-series of biomass for seabird functional groups for six scenarios with additional marine protected areas in S5-8 but no change in extent of MPAs in S1 & S4. Scenario 8 has a different climate projection to the rest.

For all fish groups the national enterprise scenario (S8) results in the lowest biomass for sardine and rays until the end of the century, while other fish groups experience low biomass until the 2070s, after which they begin to recover (Figure 101c). This pattern highlights the negative effects of cumulative impacts, including offshore wind farms (OWFs), shipping, and increased fishing effort (Figure 4.101c). In contrast, the highest biomass levels for rays and mackerels are observed in global sustainability scenarios, which incorporate MPAs, EBFM measures, and restoration. However, for hake, horse mackerel, anchovy, and sardine, neither the benefits of MPAs and EBFM measures nor the impacts of OWFs or shipping are clearly evident (Figure 4.101c).

Figure 4.101c. Time-series of biomass for key functional groups of fish for six scenarios with additional marine protected areas in S5-8 but no change in extent of MPAs in S1 & S4. Scenario 8 has a different climate projection to the rest.

There is generally lower biomass for shrimps in the S8 scenario, while all benthic groups show higher biomass in the S7 scenario, which includes MPAs and EBFM measures but also accounts for cumulative impacts (Figure 4.101d). In contrast, other scenarios follow similar trends, suggesting that neither OWFs nor shipping have a significant effect on benthos groups (Figure 4.101d).

Figure 4.101d. Time-series of biomass for key functional groups of benthic fauna for six scenarios with additional marine protected areas in S5-8 but no change in extent of MPAs in S1 & S4. Scenario 8 has a different climate projection to the rest.

Impact of primary production and difference between scenarios of climate (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5) combined with MPA/EBFM management

The models of the Portugal Shelf ecosystem presented here are driven by Earth System Model projections that account for changes in temperature and primary production rates of phytoplankton (Butenschön et al., 2024; Coll et al., 2024; Kristiansen et al., 2024). In these scenarios, primary production is predicted to decline, but with significant uncertainty. To address this, we explore three alternative scenarios (S1, S5, S8) with constant primary production post-2021 (i.e., S9, S10, S11). In the Fisheries Sustainability scenario (S5), which follows the RCP4.5 climate trajectory, there is lower biomass for benthic groups compared to the scenario where primary production remains constant. In contrast, a similar effect is not clearly observed in the National Enterprise scenario (S8), as the large variability in benthic groups driven by the RCP8.5 primary production scenario makes it difficult to discern a clear pattern (Figure 4.102a). The effects of primary production in the RCP4.5 scenario (S5) are evident across all fish groups, leading to biomass declines when compared to the scenario with fixed primary production (S10, Figure 4.102b). These effects are more pronounced for lower trophic level groups. However, primary production has a less noticeable impact on fish groups in the status-quo and National Enterprise scenarios (Figure 4.102b). Similar trends are observed for mammals, with scenarios including primary production projections generally leading to lower biomass (Figure 4.102c).

Figure 4.102a. Time-series of biomass for key benthic groups for six scenarios, including additional marine protected areas in scenarios 5, 8, 10 and 11 but no change in MPAs in S1 & S9. Scenarios 8 and 11 have RCP8.5 climate projections.

Figure 4.102b. Time-series of biomass for key fish species for six scenarios with additional MPAs in scenarios 5, 8, 10 and 11 but no change in extent of MPAs in S1 & S9. Scenarios 8 and 11 only use RCP8.5 climate projections.

Figure 4.102c. Time-series of biomass for mammals for six scenarios for six scenarios, including additional MPAs in scenarios 5, 8, 10 and 11 but no change in MPAs in S1 & S9. Scenarios 8 and 11 only use RCP8.5 climate projections.

4.8 Discussion on ecosystem modelling of cumulative impacts

The impacts of shipping are often low across model scenarios with impacts on marine mammals and turtles that are localised to those regions with a high density of shipping routes and do not propagate widely through the ecosystem. The greatest impact was modelled for dolphins in the Bay of Biscay (a 9% reduction in biomass in the 2020s relative to the status quo) followed by Loggerhead turtles in the Mediterranean Sea (8% reduction) and all other impacts were modelled with $\leq 3\%$ change in biomass in the 2020s relative the status-quo scenario (with the same climate and fisheries management implemented) (Table 4.43). A positive effect was found for seals in the Archipelago Sea and for monk seals in the Mediterranean Sea due to a reduction in competition with other predators. However, the total biomass of marine mammals does decrease in the Mediterranean Sea and the positive effect for seals in the Archipelago Sea reverses for the high response scenario. The modelled reduction of marine shipping traffic in Scenario 2 (Table 4.44) does reduce impacts and provide more favourable outcomes by the 2050s for the impacted species of mammals and turtles, with the exception of the northern population of harbour seal in the North Sea that is not directly impacted by shipping. Similar results were found in the status-quo and sustainability scenarios (e.g. S5 and S7 in Table 4.45). In contrast, model projections indicate that a further increase in marine traffic without mitigation measures, i.e., in National Enterprise scenarios, would impact negatively populations of marine mammals and turtles

at a larger geographic scale and lead to reductions in some regions by the 2050s (North Sea and Bay of Biscay, Table 4.45). These results highlight that mitigations measures on shipping may play an important role to protect populations of marine mammals and turtles.

Table 4.43 Shipping impacts on top predator functional groups once standardised to Scenario 1 to exclude climate change impacts. Values give the percentage difference in biomass between the scenario in the 2020s [$100 \times (S2_{bio} - S1_{bio})/S1_{bio}$] between Scenario 1 (Status quo) and the Scenario 2 (with medium response to shipping).

Regional Sea	Functional group	%Change between scenarios in 2020s
Bay of Biscay	Dolphins	-9
Western Mediterranean	Loggerhead turtles	-8
Western Mediterranean	Deep sea-cetacean feeders	-3
Portuguese shelf	Harbour porpoise	-3
Portuguese shelf	Striped dolphin	-3
North Sea	Harbour porpoise	-2
North Sea	Harbour seals (S)	-2
North Sea	Minke whale	-1
Bay of Biscay	Whales	-1
Portuguese shelf	Minke whale	-1
North Sea	Grey seals	-1
North Sea	Harbour seals (N)	0
Portuguese shelf	Bottlenose dolphin	0
Portuguese shelf	Common dolphin	0
Central Baltic	Grey seals	<1
Western Mediterranean	Fin whale	2
Western Mediterranean	Bottlenose dolphins	3
Western Mediterranean	Short-beaked common dolphin	3
Archipelago Sea	Seals	12
Western Mediterranean	Monk seals	17

Table 4.44. Change in biomass of mammals and turtles between 2020s and 2050s as shipping traffic reduced (by 25% by 2040) with an RCP4.5 climate trajectory (Scenario 2) for the area impacted by shipping and the whole model domain

Regional Sea	Functional group	%Change in shipping region	%Change in whole domain
Western Mediterranean	Monk seals	129	68
Portuguese shelf	Bottlenose dolphin	107	77
Portuguese shelf	Common dolphin	95	89
Central Baltic	Grey seals	73	75
Western Mediterranean	Deep sea-cetacean feeders	69	67
North Sea	Grey seals	35	5
Archipelago Sea	Seals	34	34
Portuguese shelf	Minke whale	32	30
Portuguese shelf	Harbour porpoise	32	25
Portuguese shelf	Striped dolphin	32	25
Western Mediterranean	Bottlenose dolphins	26	26
Western Mediterranean	Loggerhead turtles	13	13
North Sea	Harbour seals (S)	11	8
Bay of Biscay	Whales	6	5
Western Mediterranean	Fin whale	5	3
Bay of Biscay	Dolphins	3	2
North Sea	Harbour porpoise	1	-2
Western Mediterranean	Short-beaked common dolphin	0	-14
North Sea	Minke whale	-5	-7
North Sea	Harbour seals (N)	-27	-4

Table 4.45. Percentage change in biomass of selected groups between 2020s and 2090s for Scenario 4, 7 and 9.

Regional Sea	Functional group	Change 2090s vs 2020 for the whole model domain		
		S4 Status-quo with cumulative effects (RCP4.5)	S7 Global Sustainability with cumulative effects (RCP4.5)	S8 National Enterprise with cumulative effects (RCP8.5)
Archipelago Sea	Cormorant	0	-0	0
	Perch	-14	-13	-22
	Benthivorous birds	0	-0	-0
	Sander	-28	-26	-2
	Herring	36	72	19
	Seals	99	108	87
Bay of Biscay	Diving & pursuit divers seabirds	-14	-3	-4
	Surface feeders seabirds	-12	-3	0
	Anchovy	17	33	84
	Sardine	-4	8	-16
	Dolphins	4	8	-3
	Whales	5	4	-3
Central Baltic	Fish-feeding birds	-26	-16	47
	Flounder	18	40	-78
	Sprat	-46	-46	12
	Cod	1,139	2,011	-83
	Herring	32	32	-31
	Grey seals	75	75	0
North Sea	Diving seabirds	-39	-35	-46
	Kittiwakes	-34	-34	-43
	Surface-feeding seabirds	-37	-45	-32
	Sprat	-1	20	-14
	Sandeel	-31	-29	-55
	Herring	-20	-15	-32
	Harbour porpoise	-4	1	-7
	Harbour seals (S)	-11	21	-9
	Minke whale	-14	-13	-18
	Grey seals	-15	-8	-32
Portuguese shelf	Harbour seals (N)	-13	-7	-11
	Seabirds	265	265	182
	Adult sardine	-25	-22	-26
	Chub mackerel	121	120	119
	Mackerel	179	182	161
	Harbour porpoise	25	27	24
	Striped dolphin	0	6	-8
	Minke whale	51	64	39
	Bottlenose dolphin	95	110	79
Common dolphin	120	123	141	
Western Mediterranean	Pel. & end. Seabirds	77	110	114
	Terns	146	74	201
	Gulls & Cormorants	199	226	289
	Sardines	37	247	69
	Anchovies	24	20	42
	Loggerhead turtles	41	-10	9
	Deep sea-cetacean feeders	186	205	177
	Fin whale	39	38	41
	Bottlenose dolphins	89	168	51
	Short-beaked common dolphin	11	41	12
	Monk seals	41	75	-23

Model results for the 2050s period showed that local impacts of turbines could affect the populations of seabird species locally with 61-64% decrease in biomass (relative to the status-quo scenario 1) of fish feeding birds in the Central Baltic Sea in offshore windfarms (fixed and floating) and 60-65% decrease in cormorants and Benthivorous birds in the Achipelago Sea in area with floating wind turbines. Smaller impacts were modelled at the regional sea level (<8% reduction in biomass in the 2050s compared to the status-quo scenario), with the greatest impact overall on fish-feeding birds in the Central Baltic Sea and kittiwakes and other surface-feeding birds in the North Sea (Table 4.46).

Table 4.46. Change in biomass of seabirds along with key fish prey species due to offshore windfarms (OWF) once standardised to Scenario 1 to exclude climate change impacts. Values give the percentage difference in biomass in the 2050s [$100 \times (S3bio - S1bio)/S1bio$] between Scenario 1 (Status quo) and Scenario 3 (with medium response to turbines).

Regional Sea	Functional group	%Change between scenarios in 2050s in OWF (fixed turbines)	%Change between scenarios in 2050s in OWF (floating turbines)	%Change between scenarios in 2050s in whole domain
Central Baltic	Fish-feeding birds	-61	-64	-8
Bay of Biscay	Diving and pursuit divers	-43	-43	-1
Archipelago Sea	Cormorant	-65	-42	<1
Portuguese shelf	Seabirds	NA	-34	-1
North Sea	Diving seabirds	-38	-33	-6
Bay of Biscay	Surface feeders seabirds	-28	-27	-1
North Sea	Kittiwakes	-27	-25	-7
North Sea	Surface-feeding seabirds	-27	-23	-7
W. Mediterranean	Pel. & endangered seabirds	-25	-23	0
Archipelago Sea	Perch	-24	-21	-3
W. Mediterranean	Terns	-19	-19	-1
W. Mediterranean	Gulls & Cormorants.	-16	-19	0
Archipelago Sea	Benthivorous birds	-60	-15	<1
North Sea	Sprat	2	-4	-1
Archipelago Sea	Sander	-4	-2	0
North Sea	Sandeel	0	-2	-1
W. Mediterranean	Sardines	-4	-1	1
Portuguese shelf	Adult sardine	NA	0	0
Portuguese shelf	Chub mackerel	NA	0	0
Bay of Biscay	Anchovy	0	0	0
Bay of Biscay	Sardine	0	1	1
W. Mediterranean	Anchovies	0	1	0
North Sea	Herring	2	2	1
Portuguese shelf	Mackerel	NA	2	-1
Central Baltic	Flounder	29	4	1
Central Baltic	Sprat	12	5	-5
Central Baltic	Cod	29	46	5
Archipelago Sea	Herring	35	55	10
Central Baltic	Herring	10	60	6

However, this does highlight that mitigation measures should be included when offshore wind farms are constructed. Furthermore, the increase in de-facto MPA's due to restrictions in fishery in the offshore windfarms areas is visible from our model results with projected increases in species of pelagic and demersal fish (selected species shown in Table 4.46). For sandeel in the North Sea, the reduction in fishing and seabird predation in the fixed turbine windfarm offsets the impact of the

modelled loss of habitat in the area. Increases in herring are modelled in the Central Baltic Sea, Archipelago Sea and North Sea, but decreases were found for perch in the Archipelago Sea. Results also show that the effects of sustainable fishing and protection through MPAs (Scenario 7) can overcome the cumulative impacts of shipping and turbines, and, as in FutureMARES, the effects of climate change can be, at least partially, mitigated by active management (including protection, restoration and fisheries sustainability) (Table 4.45).

5. General summary

Major advancements have been made by GES4SEAS in the assessment of tipping points and testing of cumulative impacts of pressures (climate, fisheries, offshore structures and shipping) across European seas. Regarding tipping points, the empirical case studies show that in many instances a precise time or level of pressure that leads to a shift in the ecosystem state was difficult to find. Nonetheless, ecosystem states across European seas have changed, meaning that, potentially, more gradual changes have occurred. Such gradual changes could have been engendered through the impact of pressures on different levels of ecosystem organization (e.g., species, habitats, trophic levels) that have then cascaded across trophic or non-trophic interactions over time and space, making for a more gradual impact across the ecosystem. Second, even if tipping points were identified, they tended to be species, habitat, or trophic level specific, and their effect on the overall ecosystem functioning and other processes remain mostly undetermined.

The MSFD requires coastal member states to evaluate environmental status and the impacts of pressures on ecosystems through cumulative impact assessments across European seas in order to implement effective management actions that improve the status of our seas. This requires a strong understanding of how ecosystem states and services are changing and how tipping points at certain levels of ecosystem organization cascade throughout ecosystems. In this Deliverable, we have developed and tested assessment methods and modelling tools and in the following Deliverable 5.3, we will assess what additional information gaps need to be filled to provide a fuller understanding of how European seas are continuing to change in relation to multiple pressures. This will include an evaluation of what additional ecosystem components or level of ecosystem organization need to be assessed together with those already studied in the current Deliverable. This will provide a broader understanding of changes in the ecosystem and how these changes relate to alterations in the environmental status and the provision of ecosystem services. Additionally, we will explore how the GES4SEAS toolbox can be used to combine cumulative impact assessment with the outputs from this work. We will attempt to integrate tipping point models into the toolbox to demonstrate where broader ecosystem state changes are possible in relation to pressure and what ecosystem services are likely to be impacted. For example, the cumulative impact assessment of pressures on ecosystem components and ecosystem services within a region (e.g., a Learning Site) can be combined with known information on which ecosystem components are prone to shift (as identified in the current deliverable), or have shifted over time, to estimate which other components are likely to be affected. In addition, the toolbox may provide a means of assessing the potential for similar impacts and ecosystem shifts to happen across different regions depending on the similarity between their

ecosystem components, pressures, and processes. Furthermore, the Ecospace model outputs from the scenarios developed here can be incorporated in the toolbox to demonstrate expected change in status and cumulative effects of pressures as a result of climate, fishing, fisheries management including Marine Protected Areas and the management of impacts from shipping and offshore wind turbines once accounting for food web effects. These model outputs can replace empirical datasets on current ecosystem components and pressures (including fishing fleet distributions, shipping and offshore wind) and combined with additional pressure information (e.g. pollution and invasive species) and ecosystem components not included explicitly in the Ecospace models to give a best available understanding of the wider implications of management for environmental status and cumulative effects.

6. References

6.1 Tipping points section references

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7. Appendices

7.1 Activity Footprints

Processing of shipping route data

Publicly available data (EMODnet_HA_EMSA_Route_Density_all_2019-2023_Yearly) were downloaded on 04 Oct 2024 from European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet) Human Activities web portal (<https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en/human-activities>). Specifically, the data processed was the file:

wid1000006-all_traffic-all_europe-yearly-20230101000000_20231231235959-tdm-grid.tif

The Route Density Map was created by European Maritime Safety Agency (www.emsa.europa.eu) in 2019 and revised 11 Sep 2024.

The density is estimated per 1x1 km cell using a method that restores the full route taken by ships from recorded positions by AIS and is able to infill areas with low data coverage.

Data is expressed as the total number of routes that cross each cell by year and incorporates data from cargo, fishing, passenger, tanker, and other vessels.

For further information see:

<https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/74eef9c6-13fe-4630-b935-f26871c8b661>

The map extends over all European seas so these data were standardised (relative to the maximum value in the dataset) and processed to provide comparable datasets (with values between 0 and 100) across the Ecospace model domains.

Figure A1. Processed Vessel track dataset: shipping routes in 2021 gridded by model domain. The maximum value in each area is (from left to right): Bay of Biscay 86, Central Baltic Sea 89, North Sea 99, Portuguese Coast 86, Western Mediterranean Sea 98 and Archipelago Sea 82.

Processing of offshore windfarm datasets

Three publicly available datasets were downloaded from European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet), the Portuguese Institute for the Sea and Atmosphere (IPMA) and the open repository for EU-funded research outputs (Zenodo):

1. Plausible 2050 offshore wind locations in the North Sea (Version 3) [Data set]. Zenodo. 26 Nov 2024. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14222865.
Downloaded 05 Dec 2024. Available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/14222865>
2. Áreas para implantação de parques eólicos marinhos: Revisão 01. 21 Nov. 2023. IPMA .
Downloaded 16 Oct 2024. Available at:
https://divgmwebgis.ipma.pt/layers/divgm_geonode_data:geonode:WindFarms_Offshore_Plan_Rev01
3. EMODnet Human Activities: Wind Farms (Points) and Wind Farms (polygons). Revision date 08 May 2024.
Downloaded 15 Oct 2024. Available at: <https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer>

These datasets and their limitations are detailed further below:

1) Plausible 2050 offshore wind locations in the North Sea

A wealth of data has been provided for the North Sea for the recent past (Martins 2023). Furthermore, a plausible projection to 2050 that could meet the generation targets proposed by countries surrounding the North Sea has been proposed (Waldman et al 2024). This projection provides a baseline expectation for the model studies in GES4SEAS and suggests that individual wind turbines are likely to grow in dimension over time (to rotor diameters of up to 300m) such that wind farm areas become less densely packed. These attributes are summarised to estimate the expected *density_of_turbines* and *turbine_capacity* for fixed and floating turbines in the years 2030, 2040 and 2050 which are then used to inform other models where regional sea data are not as rich.

Figure A2. Offshore wind locations by 2050 (left fixed and right floating) gridded for Ecospace

Section references

Martins, M.C.I. Carter, M.I. Rouse, S. Russell, D.J. (2023) Offshore energy structures in the North Sea: past, present and future. Mar. Pol., 152, 105629. doi:10.1016/j.marpol.2023.105629.

Waldman, S., Conor, G., Munro, P., Forster, R., Russell, D.J.F. Heriot-Watt University, 26 Nov 2024. Plausible 2050 offshore wind locations in the North Sea (Version 3) [Data set]. Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14222865. Available at <https://zenodo.org/records/14222865>

2) IPMA Polygons (Areas for implementation of offshore wind farms)

These data arise from the Allocation Plan for Offshore Renewable Energy – West Coast of the Mainland Subdivision (PAER) as developed for Public Consultation (Version October 2023) by the Directorate-General of Natural Resources, Safety and Maritime Services. The plan aims to achieve the government’s goal of having an installed capacity of 2GW and licensed capacity of 10GW by 2030. The areas developed are expected to be fulfilled by floating wind turbines exclusively due to the reduced impact expected on the seabed. The area covered by the polygons are given in the dataset, but the year of likely construction, the expected number of turbines and their densities are not. The missing year values are all assumed to be 2030 in the GES4SEAS data product and the number of turbines expected determined from the potential windfarm capacity (MW) and the likely average capacity of turbines in 2030 (set to 8 MW).

IPMA Data - Screenshot 16 Oct 2024

Áreas para implantação de parques eólicos marinhos: Revisão 01

Attribute Name	Label	Description
fid		
CostaMax		
CostaMin		
PotenciaMW		
PotenciaGW		
area_km2		
Fonte		
Nome		

https://divgmwebgis.ipma.pt/layers/divgm_geonode_data:geonode:WindFarms_Offshore_Plan_Rev01

Figure A3. Offshore floating wind farm locations by 2030 gridded for Ecospace

3) EMODnet (points and polygons)

Data on offshore wind farms in the European seas was originally created in 2014 by CETMAR, but it is updated every year. The data is the result of the aggregation and harmonization of datasets provided by several sources from Belgium, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Spain, Sweden and United Kingdom. Data are available for download from the EMODnet web portal (Human Activities) in two formats: points and polygons. The two files have differing levels of detail and spatial coverage as can be seen in the screenshots below. Furthermore, there is a great deal of relevant data required for the Ecosim modelling that is missing from the files. In particular, the point dataset generally does not indicate how many turbines are anticipated and over what spatial extent. In contrast, the polygon data represents the expected spatial extent of the wind farm but not the likely spatial coverage by turbines within the areas.

EMODnet Points (screenshot 15 October 2024)

EMODnet Polygons (screenshot 15 October 2024)

<https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/>

To combine the point data with the set of polygons from EMODnet the following steps were taken:

A. Windfarm area from EMODnet points

Create a set of **polygons** centred on the points but only occupying marine space (avoid land), where the **points are buffered** according to expected area covered by each farm.

We derive this **area** from the *number_of_turbines* in the EMODnet point dataset [labelled N_TURBINES in EMODnet] and a standard density of turbines (by type) derived from the Waldman et al 2024 dataset (see above).

If turbine type is missing, turbines are assumed to be fixed in depths <75m and floating in deeper waters. If year is also missing, we assume construction in 2040 if in depths <75m and in 2050 if in deeper waters

Turbine density [N per km ²] if not present			
	2030	2040	2050
Fixed <75m	0.91	0.33	n/a
Floating >75m	0.27	n/a	0.13

If N_TURBINES is also missing, but the overall capacity of the windfarm (POWER_MW) and the capacity per turbine are present, then we derive the windfarm **area** from the expected capacity using the formulae:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{number_of_turbines} &= (\text{POWER_MW} / \text{turbine_capacity}) \\ \text{area [sqkm]} &= \text{number_of_turbines} / \text{density_of_turbines} \end{aligned}$$

However, as there is typically no value for *turbine_capacity* in the EMODnet data, we use median estimates derived from the North Sea in the table below:

Turbine capacity [MW]	2030	2040	2050
fixed or floating turbine	8	17	27

As before, where year is missing in EMODnet assume 2040 in depth <75m and 2050 in deeper waters

For points with no or zero N_TURBINES and no or zero POWER_MW assume an **area** equal to median of the EMODnet polygon data = **90 sqkm**

- B.** Create a single layer with full extent of EMODnet polygon layers plus the new layer from A. If there is overlap between the downloaded polygon layer and layers created in A, the attributes in the downloaded polygon takes precedence.
- C.** Habitat information is added to the attribute table for the combined layer assuming the following estimates of habitat area per turbine, which is likely to be lost for infauna through construction or gained for epifauna through the addition of scour protection using the following standard buffers:

Median habitat [km ²]	Lost by pile-driving (infauna)	Gained by scour protection (epifauna)
Single fixed turbine	0.000079	0.001963
Single floating turbine	0.000001	0.000020

As before, if turbine type is missing assume fixed in depth <75m and floating in deeper waters.

Create **habitat lost** attribute: From B, determine approx. habitat lost in each farm equal to

$$\text{habitat lost} = \text{number_of_turbines} * (\pi * R^2)$$

where radius for fixed turbines is set to R=5 m

[so that area lost per fixed turbine = $\pi * (5^2) * 10^{-6} = 0.000079 \text{ km}^2$]

where radius for floating turbines is set to R=0.5 m

[so that area lost per floating turbine area = $\pi * (0.5^2) * 10^{-6} = 0.0000008 \text{ km}^2$]

Create **habitat gain** attribute: From B, determine approx. habitat gain in each farm equal to

$$\text{habitat gain} = \text{number_of_turbines} * (\pi * R^2)$$

where radius for fixed turbines is set to R=25 m

[so that area gained per fixed turbine = $\pi * (25^2) * 10^{-6} = 0.001963 \text{ km}^2$]

where radius for floating turbines is set to R=2.5 m

[so that area gained per floating turbine = $\pi * (2.5^2) * 10^{-6} = 0.00002 \text{ km}^2$]

D. Create a fishing permission layers - From B, buffer farm polygons with a 500 m exclusion zone and calculate 1 minus this area.

Finally, we grid the outcomes (and save as ascii files) for model domains with different resolutions further split using data on year and status.

Figure A4. Gridded offshore wind locations by 2050 (left fixed and right floating) based on EMODnet information.

7.2 Ecospace models

Model domain

North Sea CRS "WGS84 "epsg:4326"

$x_{\min} = -4, x_{\max} = 9$

$y_{\min} = 49, y_{\max} = 62.5$

resolution=0.25°

Western Mediterranean CRS "WGS84 "epsg:4326"

$x_{\min} = -5.6417, x_{\max} = 16.7$

$y_{\min} = 33.6, y_{\max} = 44.8936$

resolution=0.1667°

Bay of Biscay CRS "WGS84 "epsg:4326"

$x_{\min} = -9.633, x_{\max} = -0.508$

$y_{\min} = 43.283, y_{\max} = 48.033$

resolution=0.125°

Baltic Sea CRS "EPSG:3035"

$x_{\min} = 4535378, x_{\max} = 5435378$

$y_{\min} = 3432716, y_{\max} = 4308716$

resolution=4000 m

Archipelago Sea CRS "WGS84 "epsg:4326"

$x_{\min} = 452993.3, x_{\max} = 636253.3$

$y_{\min} = 6607815, y_{\max} = 6736845$

resolution=1870 m

Model setup

All models used software version: **ewe6.7.0.19025**

The model was the same as in FutureMARES but with additional Maps, Environmental drivers and Ecospace environmental responses (functions) and external datasets as follows:

Habitat layers in Ecospace/Maps for

- Fishing allowed [all cells = 1 in Ecospace base map]
- Artisanal fishing allowed [all cells = 1 in Ecospace base map]
- Wind Farm habitat gained [all cells = 0 in Ecospace base map]

In Ecospace table **Habitat fishery**, all fleets linked to “Fishing allowed” layers and selected fleets linked to “Artisanal fishing allowed”. The base Ecospace should alter fleet effort distribution through the cost layers.

In Ecospace table **Habitat foraging usage**, values of 1 were entered for epifaunal groups linking to habitat column “Wind Farm habitat gained”.

Environmental drivers in Ecospace/Maps with all grid cells = 0 in initial year unless the scenario calls for historic implementation of route density layer, overwritten with Spatial Temporal Framework (STF) over time

- Route Density
- Wind Farm area
- Wind Farm area with buffer
- Wind Farm habitat lost

In Ecospace tab **Apply foraging responses** functions were created for

1. seabirds linked to driver “Wind Farm area with buffer”,
2. mammals/turtles linked to “Route Density”
3. infauna linked to “Wind Farm habitat lost”.

In Ecospace tab **Apply mortality response** functions were created for

1. seabirds linked to driver “Wind Farm area”
2. mammals/turtles linked to “Route Density”

External data: Will require environment files (.asc) for **RCP4.5** or **RCP8.5** using datasets used in FutureMARES. Eight new datasets will be imported for

- three **Habitats** (Fishing allowed, Artisanal fishing allowed, Wind Farm habitat gained)
- four **Environmental drivers** (Route Density (two scenarios), Wind Farm area, Wind Farm area with buffer, Wind Farm habitat lost).

Regions for output and analysis

- Region maps were prepared for each model based on the coverage of OWF in 2050
- Cells without any coverage or with <=25% area coverage by OWF are set = 1

- Cells with >25% area coverage of fixed turbines = 2 and cells with >25% area coverage of floating turbines = 3
- For “**Status quo plus shipping**” use different regions where cell = 1 if route density is >30 and 0 otherwise

7.3 Ecospace - Summary of species associations and impacts

Note that positive and negative habitat effects of OWF can be included simultaneously if the group includes both infauna and epifauna. However, if the group is not dominated by infauna biomass, then simpler to focus on the positive effects on epifauna since this is a much larger effect than the smaller impact on infauna.

Model	FG No.	Functional group name	Epifauna habitat gained from OWF	Infauna lost habitat due to OWF	Habitat Forming Species (HFS) change due to OWF	Seabirds collision with wind turbines	Marine mammal and reptiles Shipping collision	Marine mammal and reptiles Shipping route avoidance
North Sea	1	Minke whales					x	x
	2	Harbour porpoise					x	x
	3	Harbour seals - north					x	x
	4	Harbour seals - south					x	x
	5	Grey seals					x	x
	6	Diving seabirds				x		
	7	Surface-feeding seabirds				x		
	8	Kittiwakes				x		
	30	Sandeels		x				
	46	Squid & cuttlefish	x					
	51	Large crabs	x					
	52	Nephrops	x					
	53	Epifaunal macrobenthos (mobile grazers)	x					
	54	Infaunal macrobenthos		x				
	56	Small mobile epifauna (swarming crustaceans)	x					
	57	Small infauna (polychaetes)		x				
	58	Sessile epifauna	x					
	59	Mussels	x					
	60	Oysters	x					
	61	Meiofauna		x				
Bay of Biscay	1	Diving and pursuit divers seabirds				x		
	2	Surface feeders seabirds				x		
	3	Baleen whales					x	x

Model	FG No.	Functional group name	Epifauna habitat gained from OWF	Infauna lost habitat due to OWF	Habitat Forming Species (HFS) change due to OWF	Seabirds collision with wind turbines	Marine mammal and reptiles Shipping collision	Marine mammal and reptiles Shipping route avoidance
	4	Toothed cetaceans and pinnepeds					x	x
	32	Benthic cephalopods	x					
	34	Norway lobster	x					
	37	Benthos feeders decapods	x					
	38	Detritus feeders decapods	x					
	39	Bivalves	x					
	40	Polychaetes	x	x				
	41	Suprabenthos	x	x				
	42	Echinoderms	x					
	43	Deep-sea corals			x			
	44	Other invertebrates	x	x				
Western Mediterranean	1	Bottlenose dolphins					x	x
	2	Striped dolphins					x	x
	3	Short-beaked common dolphin					x	x
	4	Fin whale					x	x
	5	Deep sea-cetacean feeders					x	x
	6	Monk seals					x	x
	7	Endangered and pelagic seabirds				x		
	8	Gulls and cormorants				x		
	9	Terns				x		
	10	Loggerhead turtles					x	x
	60	Coastal benthic cephalopods	x					
	63	Other benthic cephalopods	x					
	64	Bivalves	x	x				
	65	Gastropods	x					
	66	Deep-water rose shrimp	x					
	67	Blue and red shrimp	x					
	68	Giant red shrimp	x					
	69	Other commercial shrimps	x					

Model	FG No.	Functional group name	Epifauna habitat gained from OWF	Infauna lost habitat due to OWF	Habitat Forming Species (HFS) change due to OWF	Seabirds collision with wind turbines	Marine mammal and reptiles Shipping collision	Marine mammal and reptiles Shipping route avoidance
	70	No commercial shrimps	x					
	71	Norway lobster	x					
	72	European lobster	x					
	73	Other commercial decapods	x					
	74	Non-commercial decapods	x					
	75	Purple sea urchin	x					
	76	Other sea urchins	x					
	77	Sea cucumbers	x					
	78	Other macro-benthos	x	x				
	81	Red coral			x			
	82	Other corals and gorgonians			x			
	85	Suprabenthos	x	x				
	86	Mediterranean seagrass			x			
	87	Other seagrasses			x			
	88	Erected algae			x			
	89	Seaweeds	x					
Archipelago Sea	1	Seals					x	x
	2	Cormorant				x		
	9	Benthivorous birds				x		
	14	Rhithropanopeus harrisi	x					
	19	Predatory benthos	x					
	20	Invertebrate grazers	x					
	21	Mytilus trossulus	x					
	22	Benthic bivalves		x				
	23	Other benthos		x				
	26	Filamentous algae	x					
	25	Fucus vesiculosus				x		
Baltic Sea	1	Grey seal					x	x
	2	Fish-feeding birds				x		

Model	FG No.	Functional group name	Epifauna habitat gained from OWF	Infauna lost habitat due to OWF	Habitat Forming Species (HFS) change due to OWF	Seabirds collision with wind turbines	Marine mammal and reptiles Shipping collision	Marine mammal and reptiles Shipping route avoidance
	11	Saduria entomon	x					
	12	Mytilus sp.	x					
	13	Macoma b.		x				
	14	Oth.macrob	x	x				
	15	Meiobenthos		x				
Portuguese Shelf	1	Bottlenose dolphin					x	x
	2	Harbour porpoise					x	x
	3	Striped dolphin					x	x
	7	Common dolphin					x	x
	11	Minkle whale					x	x
	5	Seabirds				x		
	28	Shrimps	x					
	29	Macrozoobenthos	x	x				
	30	Suprabenthic inv	x					
33	Kelps				x			

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